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Deliverable D1.2: Report on search and rescue actions

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of Task 1.2 “Crises involving search and rescue operations” was for COSMIC to examine a series of European and international case studies of different types of crises in order to understand lessons learned in search and rescue operations. Partners conducted an examination of five different types of crises, during which partners described the nature of the case study, provided an understanding of the standard operating procedures in place (or lack of) and discussed the lessons learned for search and rescue actions from the crisis. Specific case studies examined in this report can be seen in the table below.

Table 1: Case studies included in this report

Man-made	2005 London attacks 2013 Boston attacks
Earthquake	1999 Greece 2010 Haiti
Floods/Storms	2010 Storm Xynthia – France 2005 Hurricane Katrina - USA
Extreme temperature	2003 France 2006 North America (California)
Wildfire	2007 Greece 2007 California

Findings from the examination of case studies suggest that in the majority of situations, with the exception of the heatwave in France in 2003, standard operating procedures would have been in place to ensure the appropriate organisations of response efforts. In some cases such as for instance, responding to man-made crises such as that in London, search and rescue operations were not aligned to a specific type of crisis, rather they were designed to respond to any major incident. In cases like the storm Xynthia in France the preparation and operation were insufficient to cope with the magnitude of the crisis. Partners analysis demonstrate that whilst standard operating procedures may have been in place prior to a crisis occurring, that is not to say that they will be optimally used or strictly followed, rather, as a crisis unfolds the demands of the crisis may call for an alternative response.

Partners also identified within the case studies a shortage of effort on the authorities’ part to draw conclusions, after the crisis had struck, on their own operating procedures. A self-examination of what went according to plan and what did not is valuable as long as the shortcomings that are identified are corrected and procedures are amended accordingly. The findings should also be readily available to the public so that they are well informed and prepared the next time a crisis strikes.

Key points from the examination of European and international case studies include:

- Some case studies demonstrated that authorities had communication difficulties, including experiencing issues with broadcasting capabilities during the immediate response to a crisis leading to difficulties with ensuring adequate communication between stakeholders.
- The contribution of new media was highlighted in the Boston 2013 attacks, particularly with regard to keeping members of the public up-to-date with relevant information.
- Some case studies demonstrated the lack of adequate information exchanged between different authorities, as well as between those involved in crisis response (including the news media) and members of the affected community. This lack of information was at times apparent during the preparation and response to crises, indicating the need for effective communication strategies at the different stages of a crisis.

- Some case studies revealed that it is necessary not just to have standard operating procedures in place, but also to use these procedures in planning and testing operations.
- The 2005 London bombings demonstrated the importance of tested standard operating procedures including ensuring the adequate management, coordination and support with the wider affected community, rather than solely those whom are directly injured/killed.
- The wildfire case study demonstrated the importance of cooperation between government actors and ordinary citizens in both the preparation stage of a crisis and the need for greater training to help aid the response to a potential crisis.
- The response to the Boston attacks in 2013 demonstrated the value of learning from other agencies (across the world) in having responded to acts of terrorism. They also highlighted the importance of extensive training and exercises in effective response capabilities involving multiple agencies.
- In some cases (in particular the case studies involving floods/storms and heatwaves) findings demonstrated that both authority measures and volunteers are involved in search and rescue operations. Accordingly, a well-organised response phase is not possible without one of those two parties.
- Greater attention needs to be focused on involving the community in the preparation and subsequent response efforts to different types of crises; this would be particularly valuable to crises such as floods/storms and heatwaves.

1 INTRODUCTION

In D1.2 partners will define and characterise search and rescue operations in the different crisis types as identified in D1.1 (that is flood, extreme temperature, storm, wildfire, earthquake and man-made crises). Search and rescue activities are carried out by professional responders from emergency services and governments from different levels, ranging from local level to EU level. Often these professional responders are assisted by or are confronted with ordinary citizens, responding in groups or as individuals, who make an important contribution to the overall response effectiveness. In this chapter partners will look more closely at how governments and emergency services have prepared for typical crises and show what kinds of search and rescue activities have to be executed in typical crisis situations. By describing which standard operating procedures were effective in typical crisis situations and the lessons that could be drawn, partners will bring together and produce valuable knowledge that will be used in follow-up deliverables of COSMIC.

1.1 GENERAL IMPACT OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF CRISIS

In D1.1 partners have found that citizens, critical infrastructure, the government and to a large extent, different types of businesses, are affected in the immediate aftermath of crisis.¹ In addition, partners showed that in typical crises facing Europe, those groups that are affected are highly likely to be similar, the primary difference is the extent of the impact on different groups, which is highly dependent on the scale of the crisis situation. Crises also affect the security and well-being of the citizen in multiple ways which span bodily and psychological health, destruction of communities and supporting infrastructure, loss of personal property, loss of life and historically, in extreme cases, the destruction of entire communities.

Partners found that in order to mitigate the threat, crises require monitoring, prediction, preparation, intervention plans and dedicated organisations. Partners showed how these mitigation efforts are approached within European Member States at the national and EU level by assessing relevant legislative frameworks, as well as by examining the Community Mechanism for Civil Protection and the GMES Emergency Response Service. In addition to assessing how the security of the citizen is guaranteed by the state, partners also demonstrated how security is guaranteed by international humanitarian organisations such as the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) and Civil Society (non-governmental) Organisations (CSOs), whose flexibility renders them very effective in many difficult occasions.

In addition to how different groups are affected by crises and how national and supranational governmental agencies respond to them, partners noted that individuals, organisations and societies are often quite resilient and able to organise themselves to respond to different types of crises.

- *Individuals*: Individual dynamics during crises are dependent on (citizen) preparation, (early) warning, and government interventions (or lack thereof) during the response and recovery phases of a crisis. The degree to which individuals are able to cope with

¹ Watson, Hayley, Kush Wadwha, Rachel Finn, Ioannis Kotsiopoulos, Angelos Yannopoulos, Jelle Groenendaal, Arjen Schmidt, David de Vries and Ira Helsloot, “Report on security crises with high societal impact, Deliverable 1.1 of the COSMIC project, July 2013.

- these unexpected crises largely depends on the skills, knowledge and resources they have developed over time, as well as their experience to previous crises.
- *Organisations*: During the response phase of a crisis, extending and emerging organisations are active. Some examples of disasters in the West demonstrate that some extending organisations take on other roles than they would normally be responsible for, at the same time, other organisations emerge to become responsible for new tasks.
 - *Society*: In the aftermath of a crisis two processes can be distinguished. In the first hours the ‘mobilisation of social support’ is visible, motivated by a form of altruism. When the proportion of victims to non-victims increases, the motivation of helpers decreases and the process of ‘deterioration of support’ begins. The affected society has to appeal to their own strengths and possibilities and are accordingly expanding their resilience. The main determining factors for community resilience include; economic development, social capital, sufficient information and communication and community competences.

1.2 PREVENTION, PREPARATION AND RESPONSE

As Boin and McConnell argue, the overwhelming tendency in both theory and practice is to view crisis management as a holistic process involving prevention, preparation, acute response and recovery.² Search and rescue is a part of the acute response phase and will be discussed in the response section.

Prevention

Prevention essentially means mitigating the risks (that is the likelihood that something goes wrong x impact of the event) in order to decrease the likelihood of occurrence and/or the impact when something goes wrong. According to Boin and McConnell, there are many successful instances of crisis prevention. For instance, the Dutch have built an elaborate defence system against the catastrophic potential of the North Sea. The segregation and destruction of birds harbouring the H5N1 bird flu virus has proved reasonably successful in preventing the spread of the disease to Western Europe and the Americas. However, as Boin & McConnell warn us, we should not believe that all risks can or could be prevented. The authors note that it is simply impossible to know every conceivable ‘worst case’ that may unfold. Those groups that seek to intentionally incite harm can become inventive beyond our imagining as the 2001 World Trade Center attacks have shown. The 2007 wildfires in Southern Europe as well as Southern California reminded us of nature’s power to produce swift devastation. Prevention requires that one knows the source and dynamics of threats, but the literature shows that this is impossible for most if not all organisations.³

Preparation

Preparation includes calamity arrangements with contingency plans as well as well-educated and trained emergency personnel and crisis management teams. Planning is helpful for determining what may happen when something goes wrong, and furthermore, what is needed in order to bring the situation back to a state of normalcy. Planning can assist in clarifying roles and responsibilities as well as in deciding which resources (in terms of materials, equipment and systems) are necessary and how they should be geographically allocated.

² Boin, A., and A. McConnell, Preparing for critical infrastructure breakdowns: the limits of crisis management and the need for resilience, *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*, Vol. 15, Issue 1, 2007, pp. 50-59.

³ Ibid.

Education and training is important for being able to perform search and rescue operations effectively when an incident – from a minor accident to a large-scale crisis situation – occurs. However, planning and training to typical crisis situations is no easy task. As Boin and McConnell state, how can we prepare for a phenomenon that by its very nature violates the very regular patterns upon which planners rely in order to prevent it?⁴ There are too many possible threats, which require planning and training. As a consequence, planners have to make choices informed by cost-benefit analysis and decide which threats will deserve attention and which will not. But the planning process itself has also some inherent difficulties. Boin and McConnell argued that planning requires multi-agency cooperation and coordination, which often strand in the realities of bureaucratic politics.⁵

Response – search and rescue

In the response to typical crisis situations the actual emergency work is done. Originally, search and rescue activities are concerned with locating, reaching, (medically) treating and safely extricating survivors. Search and rescue (SAR) refers to an emergency operation commenced to render aid to individuals believed to be in distress, ill or injured, and possibly lost.⁶ SAR may comprise water-rescue by the coastguard or lost walkers in a hostile outdoor environment, but is also concerned with deeply entombed survivors of collapsed structures (the latter is referred to as urban search and rescue – USAR). According to Lindell, in USAR incidents *crush syndrome* will kill most of those who are injured within about 24 hours. Consequently, the prompt response of local volunteers – either singly, in emergent groups, or in previously organised and trained SAR teams – is far more significant than the response of heavily equipped urban search and rescue teams because the latter generally take days to arrive even in domestic incidents.⁷ That is one of the most prominent complications for the efforts of international SAR teams. The delays are even greater in international incidents, where mobilization delays, long flights, and visa problems can cause even further delays. In this chapter, however, we define search and rescue as all activities concerned with the help of citizens directly or indirectly involved with a crisis situation. Some typical search and rescue activities may include: searching for victims, fire suppression, evacuation of affected areas, determination of casualties and identification of victims.

Recovery

Recovery includes all activities aimed at bringing the evolved situation back to normalcy, from rebuilding activities to provide compensation for damage. This phase also encompasses learning from (near-) disasters, providing feedback to other links in the chain and thus making societies less vulnerable to similar events in the future.⁸

1.3 REPORT OUTLINE

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ Heggie, T. W., & Amundson, M. E., Dead men walking: search and rescue in US National Parks. *Wilderness & Environmental Medicine*, Vol. 20, Issue, 3, 2009, pp. 244-249.

⁷ Lindell, M. K., Disaster studies. *Current Sociology*, 2013. See also Aguirre, B. E., *Planning, warning, evacuation, and search and rescue: a review of the social science research literature*, Hazard Reduction Recovery Center, 1994.

⁸ Boin, A., & McConnell, A., 2007.

The outline of the report can be summarised as follows. This report consists of seven chapters, with each chapter focusing on assessing particular types of crises; Chapter 2) man-made disasters, 3) earthquakes, 4) flood/storm, 5) extreme temperature and 6) wildfire. In each of these chapters, partners will describe the search and rescue operations in two different cases: one case of a typical crisis that took place within the EU and one that took place outside the EU (but this is often a quite similar Western industrial society largely comparable to an average EU member state).

Each case study is conducted by reviewing after action reports, policy documents and scientific literature. First, partners will describe why they have decided to choose these particular cases. What was the rationale? Second, in the description of the case the impacts of this type of crisis on individuals at the different phases of the crisis will be highlighted. Third, a description is given of the standard operating procedures that were in effect during the response to the events. Fourth, (when available) information is provided about how the standard operating procedures were applied and operated in practice. Fifth and finally, partners will identify lessons learnt for future operations and activities. These lessons can be existing lessons drawn by scholars or investigation committees as well as by the consortium based on the analysis of the case.

The conclusion of this report is presented in Chapter 7. In this chapter, partners will analyse the similarities and differences between different types of crises with regard to how they impact on individuals in society and standard operating procedures. In Task 1.1⁹ partners showed the importance of non-government actors like citizens, communities and business for a good and sufficient preparation on and response to disasters. Following, in this report partners aim to learn lessons out of examples and make recommendations to those actors for future situations. Following Task 1.2, in Task 1.3 partners will focus on the role of official emergency agencies in crises. Lessons about the cooperation and collaboration between those agencies (e.g., federal and local services) can function as a basis to compare the official instructions and prescriptions with.

⁹ Watson et al., 2013.

2 MAN-MADE CRISES

Chapter 2 will focus on examining search and rescue operations in relation to man-made crises. In order to do so, this chapter will assess search and rescue operations in relation to the protection of citizens by focusing on two case studies: 1) the 7 July 2005 London attacks and 2) the 15 April 2013 Boston attacks. Partners have chosen to focus their research on acts of terrorism within the category of man-made crises due to its high societal impact (as previously discussed in COSMIC D1.1 Report on security crises with high societal impact¹⁰).

The 2005 London attacks represent a European example of the need for search and rescue efforts to respond to an unexpected act of terror. This case study was selected by partners as a result of the availability of English evaluation reports, enabling our research in this report to benefit from known and documented lessons learned. In addition to examining a European case study on terrorism, partners have selected the 2013 Boston attacks for its international case study due to it being a more recent case study, and due to its wider relevance to the exploration of the contribution of new media that will be explored elsewhere in the COSMIC project.

In order to conduct this examination, partners assessed incident related evaluation reports, government policies on standard operating procedures, news articles and (other) scientific literature. This chapter will proceed by discussing each of the case studies individually, it will then proceed in the conclusion to conduct a horizontal analysis of the findings.

2.1 LONDON ATTACKS (2005)

The UK's capital, London, fell victim to several acts of terror on the 7 July 2005 (07/07). The attacks coincided with the success of the London 2012 Olympic bid (6 July 2005) and the G8 International Political Leaders Summit in Gleneagles, which discussed overseas development and the problem of climate change. At 08:50 BST on the 7 July 2005, the city of London's transportation network was attacked by four individuals. Three attacks occurred simultaneously on the London underground system: Russell Square via the Piccadilly line by Germaine Lindsay, aged 19; Aldgate via the Circle line, by Shehzad Tanweer, aged 24; and Edgware road also via the Circle line by Mohammad Sidique Khan, aged 30. A fourth attack took place an hour later, targeting a London public bus service at Tavistock Square and was committed by Hasib Hussain, aged 18.¹¹

These attacks caused 52 fatalities and 770 injuries.¹² In addition to these direct impacts, citizens indirectly caught up in the attacks may have experienced some form of psychological trauma. By its very nature, as identified by Nacos, an act of terror is designed to instil fear in the community at large¹³, by expanding its reach through publicity.¹⁴ Thus those impacted by

¹⁰ Watson, Hayley, Wadhwa, Kush, Finn, Rachel, Kotsiopoulos, Ioannis, Yannopoulos, Angelos, Groenendaal, Jelle, Schmidt, Arjen, de Vries, David and Helsloot, Ira, "Deliverable D1.1: Report on security crises with high societal impact", *Deliverable 1.1 of the COSMIC project*, 31 July 2013.

¹¹ BBC, "In-Depth: 7th July 2005 Bombings - What Happened", *BBC News Online*, http://news.BBC.co.uk/1/shared/spl/hi/uk/05/london_blasts/what_happened/html/

¹² Ibid.

¹³ Nacos, Brigitte Lebens, *Mass-mediated Terrorism the Central Role of the Media in Terrorism and Counterterrorism*, Rowman & Littlefield, Lanham, 2007.

¹⁴ Watson, Hayley, "Dependent Citizen Journalism and the Publicity of Terror", *Terrorism and Political Violence*, Vol. 24, No. 3, 2012, pp. 465–482.

an act of terror is not necessarily limited to those directly physically harmed, but in addition those indirectly exposed. A telephone survey of Londoners by Sheppard et al., shortly following the attacks revealed that for some individuals there were substantial levels of stress following the attacks.¹⁵ This was similarly reported by the 7 July London Committee report into the attacks which found that “hundreds” of individuals directly caught up in the attacks suffered psychological trauma.¹⁶

2.1.1 Standard operating procedures

At the time of the 07/07 attacks, the standard operating procedures for responding to an act of terrorism in the UK were defined by the 2004 Civil Contingences Act.¹⁷ The Civil Contingences Act 2004 was not restricted to responding to terrorism, but was a single framework, split into two parts for ensuring civil protection in the UK, and was therefore used to respond to any emergency that the UK may face. Within the present report, partners will focus on part one of the act; “Local arrangements for civil protection”.

Relevant to the 07/07 attacks are those stakeholders responsible for emergency preparedness and response at the local level. In part one of the act, stakeholders involved in emergency preparedness and response are split into two categories: 1) “organisations at the core of the response to most emergencies (the emergency services, local authorities, NHS bodies)” and 2) ‘co-operating bodies’ (e.g. the Health and Safety Executive, transport and utility companies). Category 1 responders are regarded to be essential for the full delivery of emergency preparedness and response. Category 2 responders have less duties, instead they are involved in co-operation and sharing activities with other category 1 and 2 responders.¹⁸

In preparing for emergencies, including those man-made crises such as acts of terrorism, the UK government have sought to ensure that its organisations have “well-practiced emergency plans in place”.¹⁹ The purpose of emergency plans are to, as far as possible, prevent emergencies from occurring. The extent to which the Civil Contingences Act can prevent a particular type of emergency such as that stemming from an act of terrorism is unclear, crucially emphasis is placed on the ability of stakeholders to respond to any emergency. In relation to preventing an act of terrorism in the UK, a range of preventative measures exist, from national intelligence operations to more specific awareness raising initiatives such as encouraging citizens to be “aware” and to report any suspicious activities.²⁰ As expressed in the 7 July Committee Report of the London attacks, “London had been warned repeatedly that an attack was inevitable: it was a question of when, not if”²¹ and thus, great emphasis was placed on the capital being prepared to deal with an unexpected crisis. Accordingly, in relation to the Civil Contingences Act, if an emergency did occur, “good planning should

¹⁵ Sheppard, Ben, G James Rubin, Jamie K Wardman, and Simon Wessely, “Terrorism and Dispelling the Myth of a Panic Prone Public”, *Journal of Public Health Policy*, Vol. 27, No. 3, 2006, pp. 219–249.

¹⁶ *Report of the 7 July Review Committee*, Greater London Authority, June 2006.

http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/shared/bsp/hi/pdfs/05_06_06_london_bombing.pdf.

¹⁷ Civil Contingences Act 2004, 2004.

http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2004/36/pdfs/ukpga_20040036_en.pdf.

¹⁸ Cabinet Office, “Preparation and planning for emergencies: responsibilities of responder agencies and others”, *Cabinet Office: Gov.UK*, 20 February 2013. <https://www.gov.uk/preparation-and-planning-for-emergencies-responsibilities-of-responder-agencies-and-others>

¹⁹ Ibid.

²⁰ “Terrorism and cyber attack”, *London.gov.uk*, no date. <http://www.london.gov.uk/mayor-assembly/mayor/london-resilience/risks/terrorism-and-cyber-attack>

²¹ Report of the 7 July Review Committee, June 2006.

reduce, control or mitigate the effects of the emergency”.²² Emphasis is therefore placed on the need for emergency plans to be constantly evolving; that they should be amended where necessary based on lessons learned as well as any other circumstances that might change.

For the British government, planning for an emergency involves a “cycle of activities”: 1) the development of a “risk profile” to determine priorities, 2) review and 3) revision, which then leads to the cycle re-starting. They argue that emergency plans should focus their attention on three groups of people: “the vulnerable, victims (including survivors, family and friends) and responder personnel”.²³ Emergency plans should also include mechanisms for arranging to “warn, inform and advise the public at the time of an emergency”. Furthermore, in the event of a “high profile” emergency, plans should consider how to respond to the media, the public and other interested parties. Plans should also consider the involvement of multiple organisations so as to ensure the most effective response to an emergency (e.g., between police, fire and ambulance organisations).²⁴

When preparing for an emergency, relevant stakeholders should also develop “recovery plans” to help reduce the effects of an emergency and assist with the long-term recovery efforts after an emergency.²⁵ In the event of an emergency, emergency plans should include a procedure for determining whether an emergency has occurred and for a nominated, trained individual to begin the effort, in collaboration with others to make this decision.

In relation to the civil protection of London, the London Emergency Services Liaison Panel (LESLP) have developed a major incident procedure manual.

Major incident procedure manual

The LESLP was formed in 1973 and is involved in the development of plans and procedures for responding to a major incident in London. LESLP is comprised of representatives from; “the Metropolitan Police Service, City of London Police, British Transport Police, the London Fire Brigade, the London Ambulance Service and local authorities. The Port of London Authority (PLA), Marine Coastguard, Royal Air Force (RAF), Military and voluntary sector are also represented. LESLP has the ability to invite representatives from other agencies into the group when required, dependent on the nature and type of incident”. The group meet every three months and is chaired by the Metropolitan Police’s “Public Order Branch”.²⁶

As part of their efforts, the LESLP have developed several editions of a major incident preparedness manual. The 2004 manual, and thus the manual in effect during the 07/07 attacks, describes the “agreed procedures and arrangements for the effective co-ordination of their joint effort”.²⁷ The manual provides “summaries of the responses and responsibilities of each of the emergency services at a major incident, as well as an outline of the support role offered by local authorities”.²⁸ A major incident, including an act of terrorism, is defined as: “... any emergency that requires the implementation of special arrangements by one or more of the emergency services and will generally include the involvement, either directly or

²² Cabinet Office, 2013.

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ *Major Incident Procedure Manual: Sixth Edition*, London Emergency Services Liaison Panel, 2004.

http://www.mawson.me.uk/wmercia/LESLP_Man.pdf. [p. 8]

²⁷ Ibid.

²⁸ Ibid.

indirectly, of large numbers of people”.²⁹ Any member of LESLP can declare an incident a major incident. Whilst the incident may not require a response from all members, other members should be placed on standby should their services be required.

According to the manual, most major incidents contain four stages: initial response, consolidation phase, recovery phase and the restoration of normality, as depicted in their figure (right):³⁰

Figure 1: Four stages of a major incident

In terms of a “general” approach to rescue operations in a major incident, the London Fire Brigade are responsible for the rescuing survivors, the London Ambulance Service are responsible for the care and transportation of casualties and the police are responsible for perimeter control as well as co-ordinating the emergency services, local authorities and other (relevant) agencies.³¹

When first attending the scene of an incident, the police, fire brigade and ambulance services all have a strict set of instructions for determining whether the scene they are faced with should be considered a major incident or not. Depending on the situation, personnel are not always able to immediately become involved in response efforts, rather they must begin to manage the situation and to report back to their various control centres to begin to co-ordinate response efforts. Once a scene has been secured and cordoned off appropriately (predominantly with the help of the police), a joint emergency services control centre is established by vehicles (from each of the emergency services) being located close to each other so as to establish close contact between emergency services for the management of a scene.³² As outlined in the manual, “it is important to emphasise that it is essential that the first supervising officers on scene from each of the emergency services liaise closely with each other at the earliest opportunity”.³³

Central to the response of a major incident is the effective functioning of communication systems. In responding to an incident different members of the emergency services have different forms of communication at their disposal. However, in the direct response of a major incident, the police are responsible for issuing radios to professional response groups at the scene of a major incident so that they can access a shared inter-agency command channel.³⁴ Also at the disposal of emergency services is the launch of “Access Overload Control” scheme. The scheme allows mobile telephone networks to limit access to their networks and to allow emergency services and other users (with appropriate mobile telephones) to have exclusive access to available channels.³⁵ Emergency services are also able to be supported by the Radio Amateur’s Emergency Network (RAYNET), “a nationwide voluntary group of United Kingdom government-licensed radio operators who are able to provide emergency radio communications to the emergency services, local authorities and central government departments”.³⁶

²⁹ Ibid., p. 10.

³⁰ Ibid., p. 11.

³¹ Ibid., p. 12.

³² Ibid., pp. 14-21.

³³ Ibid., p. 24.

³⁴ Ibid., p. 31.

³⁵ Ibid., p. 32.

³⁶ Ibid., p. 33.

Following a major incident, all those organisation involved in response efforts will be required to issue a join (agreed) statement for dissemination to the news media. The police (press staff) will be responsible for releasing a statement to the media. Crucially the manual makes it clear, that when involving an act of terrorism, “No information should be provided to the news media in relation to a terrorist incident without authority of the Anti-Terrorist Branch. A Metropolitan Police Service (MPS) aide mémoire outlines the policy”.³⁷

During the recovery stage of an incident, emergency services should appropriately and adequately handle the recovery and documentation of casualties. Casualties may fall into different groups, including; “uninjured, injured, dead or evacuees”.³⁸ Recovery efforts depend on the category that casualties may fall into, but all casualties should be documented. For instance those who are uninjured are witnesses and thus their details must be recorded by the police should they need to be spoken to at a later date, particularly in the investigation stage of a major incident.³⁹ In line with this, a “survivor reception centre” should be set up, where voluntary organisation can help comfort those affected. In addition this centre should serve as a place for “shelter, first-aid treatment, welfare support, communications and room for documentation”.⁴⁰ The police are responsible for providing security and a team for collecting information to be passed on to the casualty bureau, which would also be established by the police for collecting information on those involved in the incident.

The involvement of other groups, including local authorities, voluntary aid groups (e.g., British Red Cross, Salvation Army etc.), military, utility companies, the media etc. may be called upon to be of assistance in the response and recovery efforts but their level of involvement is dependent on the scale and impact of the incident.⁴¹

Restoration of normality is the final stage of managing a major incident and is the responsibility of the local authority, who plays a “leading role in the return to normality, the rehabilitation of the community and restoration of the environment in accordance with Home Office guidance contained in its booklet *Recovery: An Emergency Management Guide*”.⁴²

The recovery guide, published in January 2006⁴³, defines “recovery” as; “The process of restoring and rebuilding the community in the aftermath of an incident”.⁴⁴ The length of time of the recovery process is largely dependent on the extent of the incident and should be prepared for during the response stage of an emergency. As stated in the guide, the recovery process should form part of “day to day emergency management. The aim is to reach a point where additional demands on services have been reduced to the level at which they were before the incident occurred, often described as ‘a return to normality’. However the incident, and its effects, are likely to create a new ‘normality’, raising serious issues for the local authority”.⁴⁵ Recovery plans for emergency management should take into consideration various challenges including: rebuilding the community, managing the financial implications

³⁷ Ibid., p. 58.

³⁸ Ibid., p. 34.

³⁹ Ibid.

⁴⁰ Ibid., p. 38.

⁴¹ Ibid., pp. 49-59.

⁴² Ibid., p. 50.

⁴³ Partners were unable to locate recovery guides that were available prior to 2006.

⁴⁴ “Recovery: An emergency management guide”, *Home Office*, 1 January 2006.

<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/recovery-an-emergency-management-guide>

⁴⁵ Ibid., pp. 1-2.

of an emergency, managing the allocation and provision of resources, responding to the community's welfare needs and developing strategic issues (internal organisation of the local authority to deal with the recovery period).

Since 2004, the major incident manual has been amended twice, with an eighth edition currently in circulation.⁴⁶ Although briefly summarised here, the manual contains extensive guidance and instructions for specific co-ordination activities in the event of a major incident.

2.1.2 Lessons learned

As the 07/07 attacks took place over six years ago, time has passed enabling a series of studies and reports to be completed evaluating the emergency response efforts to the crisis. Accordingly, this sub-section will examine documented lessons learned regarding the emergency services response to the attacks. Partners will therefore focus on an extensive report completed by the 7 July Review Committee, of which several of its recommendations were reinforced by the Coroner's Inquest in 2011.⁴⁷

The Report of the 7 July Review Committee, published in June 2006 provides extensive detail concerning lessons learned from the 07/07 attacks.⁴⁸ The report praised the humanitarian response to the attacks as "astounding", with passengers, underground works, shop staff, office workers, hotel employees, passers-by doing all they could to help those affected, illustrating the importance of the involvement of the wider community in contributing to response efforts.

They also commended the work of the emergency services who had "all the relevant statutory organisations have their emergency plans in place, as indeed do many of the large non-statutory institutions. These plans have been tested, practised against and refined".⁴⁹ As stated in the report, what linked the different emergency services together was their abilities to perform their "service-specific" roles, meaning that they were able to meet the "needs of the service", which resulted in the lack of an "outward focus that took into account the needs of their client groups", those affected.

Elsewhere, as revealed in a study of the response to the attacks by Strom and Eyerman, the response to the attacks was comprehensive and complex, crucially, "major problems in emergency coordination were minimized because London officials had established relationships with one another and had practiced agreed-upon procedures. Consequently, everyone knew their roles and responsibilities; a command and control system was up and running quickly; and mutual aid agreements — planned out in advance — were successfully initiated and applied".⁵⁰

⁴⁶ *Major Incident Procedure Manual: Eighth Edition*, London Emergency Services Liaison Panel, 2012.

http://www.leslp.gov.uk/docs/major_incident_procedure_manual_8th_ed.pdf.

⁴⁷ Lady Justice Hallett, "Coroner's Inquest into the London bombings of the 7 July 2005", *Judicial Communications Office*, 6 May 2011.

<http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20120216072438/http://7julyinquests.independent.gov.uk/>

⁴⁸ *Report of the 7 July Review Committee*, 2006.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 1.

⁵⁰ Strom, Kevin, and Joe Eyerman, "Interagency Coordination: A Case Study of the 2005 London Train Bombings", *National Institute of Justice Journal*, Vol. 260, July 2008.

<http://www.nij.gov/journals/260/interagency-coordination.htm>.

Such a sentiment is further supported by the review of the response to the attacks by the London Regional Resilience Forum, who emphasised the positive impact that the four years of planning had had on an effective multi-agency response to the attacks.⁵¹ Furthermore they commended the efforts and coordination between agencies, as well as the actions of the transport staff involved in the immediate response to the attacks.

The focus of the committee report was on what could be improved in future incidents. As identified in their reporting of the findings, the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) revealed that three main findings had been unearthed: poor communications, the failure of emergency services to deal with survivors hampered emergency efforts in responding to the attacks and a shortage of medical supplies.⁵² In addition to these, the report provided extensive recommendations to help improve emergency response capabilities in future incidents. Further information relating to these three main issues is discussed below.

Poor communication

As with other⁵³ large-scale sudden emergencies, poor communication was found to hamper response and recovery efforts and was found to affect multiple working relationships during the unfolding attacks:

- Between emergency services, which affected the response and recovery efforts towards the attacks in London: “Communications within and between the emergency services did not stand up on 7 July. As a result, individual emergency service personnel at the affected Tube stations and at Tavistock Square could not communicate effectively, in some cases with each other, and in other cases with their control rooms”.⁵⁴ This was particularly evident with those responders that were unable to communicate underground, as only the British Transport Police were equipped with radios that were functional underground. This hampered the effectiveness of the emergency services, particularly with regard to how quickly they were able to assess the situation and declare the incidents as a major incident which would have then (according) to the standard operating procedures, been the point at which further liaison and communication amongst different organisations would have begun to take place.⁵⁵
- Accordingly, concern was also raised as to the immediacy to which a major incident, as defined by the LESLP major incident guide, was declared. Authors recommended that LESLP review its protocol so that as soon as one emergency provider declares a major incident, others put major incident procedures in place.⁵⁶
- There was also communication trouble between members of the public and train drivers, leaving them in the dark as to the on-going situation.⁵⁷ Authors recommended a “rapid rollout of facilities” to enable communication.⁵⁸
- Trouble with emergency services reliance on mobile phones for communication purposes.⁵⁹

⁵¹ “Looking back, moving forward: The Multi–Agency Debrief Lessons identified and progress since the terrorist events of 7 July 2005”, *London Regional Resilience Forum*, September 2006.

⁵² “7 July Report Highlights Failings”, *BBC*, 5 June 2006.

<http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/england/london/5046346.stm>

⁵³ See for instance: Groenendaal, Jelle, Helsloot, Ira and Scholtens, Astrid, “A Critical Examination of the Assumptions Regarding Centralized Coordination in Large-Scale Emergency Situations”, *Homeland Security & Emergency Management*, Vol. 10, No. 1, 2013, pp. 1–23.

⁵⁴ *Report of the 7 July Review Committee*, 2006, p. 120.

⁵⁵ Major Incident Procedure Manual: Sixth Edition, 2004.

⁵⁶ *Report of the 7 July Review Committee*, 2006, p. 128.

⁵⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 124.

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

- Communication issues were also faced between train drivers and their line controllers. Among other recommendations, the authors recommended that the London Underground, Metronet and Tubelines should speed up the implementation of their new radio system.⁶⁰
- Communication was also lacking between the emergency services and those not directly caught up in the attacks; recommendations included the better provision of basic and timely, regular advice and updated information to the public.⁶¹

Findings relating to the trouble with communication (of which were included in the committee report) were also extensively commented on by the multi-agency debrief carried out by the London Regional Resilience Forum. Crucially, they commented that whilst issues with telecommunications presented the greatest challenge, “they did not significantly affect the emergency services’ ability to respond effectively”.⁶²

Failure of emergency services to deal with survivors

A fundamental finding from the review regarding the response to the London attacks, was the lack of focus on adequately dealing with survivors:

The most striking failing in the response to the 7 July attacks was the lack of planning to care for people who survived and were traumatised by the attacks. Hundreds of people were left to wander off from the scenes. An estimated 1,000 adults and 2,000 of their children are likely to have suffered from post-traumatic stress as a result of their experiences on 7 July. 3,000 others are estimated to have been directly affected by the explosions. The majority of them are still not known to the authorities, are not part of any support network of survivors, and have been left to fend for themselves. Those who are known to the authorities in some cases received excellent care and support following 7 July. Others registered their details but received no follow-up contact, and no advice or information about the support that was available.⁶³

Although the documentation of casualties was an important component of the standard operating procedures, including the establishment of a survivors centre and a casualty bureau, findings from the review suggest that in the “heat of the moment”, this was not sufficient and was therefore in need of future improvements (demonstrating that whilst standard operating procedures may have been in place they are not always precisely followed). Recommendations included, for example; setting up a way of communicating with survivor’s as soon as possible, including the establishment of a survivor reception area to collect their personal details. These reception areas would also function as a means of initiating a form of support for those friends and families affected by an incident. In addition to improving the timely and accurate recording of information, emergency services and authorities were also advised to find a way to ensure the provision of accurate information to them (e.g., through a secure website, counselling services, information and guidance) and to protect them from outsiders (e.g., unwanted media attention, conspiracy theorists).⁶⁴

Shortage of medical supplies:

The report identified several problems regarding the provision of medical supplies at the affected locations. For instance, it recommended the provision of basic first aid kits of local

⁵⁹ Ibid., p. 42.

⁶⁰ Ibid., p. 125.

⁶¹ Ibid., pp. 134-135.

⁶² London Regional Resilience Forum, September 2006, p. 6.

⁶³ *Report of the 7 July Review Committee*, 2006, p. 20.

⁶⁴ Ibid., pp. 131-140. *Please note, these are just examples for illustrative purposes, for more comprehensive recommendations please see the full report.*

transport, including, tubes, trains and buses.⁶⁵ In addition, the authors recommended that in the event of a major incident, all hospitals in the vicinity of the incident, regardless of their status of emergency departments, should be placed on alert, should they be needed to respond to events.⁶⁶ The findings relating to the medical “readiness” in the event of a major incident points towards the need for greater involvement of medical personnel in the emergency planning of major incidents as run by the LESLP in London.

Following the various reviews that took place, the government produced a document that provided further information regarding what actions were currently taking place to address the lessons learned from the emergency response to the bombings, not just for any future incidents in London, but across the UK.⁶⁷ Focus was particularly focused on: “Better support to the bereaved and survivors, more resilient telecommunications networks, emergency service communications networks, underground communications, providing timely information to the public, keeping London moving safely and crisis co-ordination arrangements”.⁶⁸

Overall, they concluded that the 2004 Civil Contingences Act remained a significant “foundation for building resilience across the UK by providing a clear set of roles and responsibilities for local planners”.⁶⁹ However, that is not to say that without the act that emergency services would not have responded in an efficient manner. Crucially, it is not clear whether any plans or policies influenced the notable and commendable actions of members of the public in spontaneously assisting one another in the immediate aftermath of the attacks (as identified by the committee report).⁷⁰

Lessons learned from the attacks illustrated the (continued) importance of improved communications across different parties involved in responding and recovering from a major incident. They also stressed the need for introducing greater focus on survivors in emergency management plans, particularly in relation to the better recording of information and therefore the ability to manage and assist individuals caught up in an emergency. Thus whilst standard operation procedures may be in place that is not to say that they will be regimentally followed. As a final point, the review stressed the importance of the greater involvement of other relevant parties in emergency planning (e.g., hospitals, senior media officials etc.).

2.2 BOSTON ATTACKS (2013)

The 117th Boston Marathon which took place on the 15th April 2013 was marred by the explosion of two bombs at the finish line at approximately 14:50 EDT (Eastern Daylight Time).⁷¹ At this time, three-quarters of the runners had completed the race. The first bomb

⁶⁵ Ibid., p. 132.

⁶⁶ Ibid., p. 132.

⁶⁷ “Addressing Lessons From the Emergency Response to the 7 July 2005 London Bombings - What we learned and what we are doing about it”, *Crown Copyright*, 2006.

⁶⁸ Ibid., p. 1.

⁶⁹ Ibid., p. 21.

⁷⁰ *Report of the 7 July Review Committee*, 2006, p. 8.

⁷¹ Eligon, John, and Michael Cooper, “2 Bombs at Boston Marathon Kill at Least 3 and Injure More Than 100”, *The New York Times*, 15 April 2013. <http://www.nytimes.com/2013/04/16/us/explosions-reported-at-site-of-boston-marathon.html>.

had been placed in a rubbish bin on Boylston Street in the “heart of the city”.⁷² The second bomb detonated 13 seconds later “several hundred feet away”. The attacks resulted in three deaths and approximately 300 people injured.⁷³ Following police and FBI investigations, two brothers, Tamerlan and Dzhokhar Tsarnaev were captured within 102 hours of the attacks; Dzhokhar Tsarnaev pleaded guilty, whilst his brother, Tamerlan, was shot and later died in the lead up to their capture.⁷⁴

As with the attacks in London, the Boston attacks not only physically and psychologically affected those directly affected by the blast (i.e., through death or injury) but also affected those exposed to the situation, including for instance other spectators, runners and response personnel.⁷⁵ There were also, what turned out to be unrelated, bomb-related scares in other parts of Boston (e.g., a fire at the John F. Kennedy Presidential Library and Museum⁷⁶). In addition, in response to the attacks, security was heightened elsewhere in Boston, for instance the instigation of a no fly zone over Boston, as well as increases in security in other parts of the country (e.g., New York and Washington).⁷⁷ Concern was also raised over security of events outside of the US, for instance in relation to the (*then*) forthcoming London marathon which was due to take place on the 21st April 2013.⁷⁸

2.2.1 Standard operating procedures & performance

In order to identify the standard operating procedures and performance in the likelihood of an act of terror, partners have focused their efforts on understanding this in relation to the crisis management efforts of the Massachusetts Emergency Management Agency (MEMA) who were directly involved in responding to the Boston attacks.⁷⁹

In the event of a terrorist attack, MEMA have included on their website information regarding how individuals and families can prepare for an act of terror (e.g., taking precautions when travelling), as well as supplying viewers of the site with links for further information (e.g., American Red Cross, FEMA etc.).⁸⁰ The site also contains links to preparedness for small and local businesses to prepare themselves to respond to a crisis.⁸¹ In the event of an emergency, the Operations Division of MEMA maintains and operates the State Emergency Operations Center (SEOC), which serves as the “command and control centre for the Commonwealth

⁷² Ibid.

⁷³ Committee on Homeland Security and Governmental Affairs, “Lessons Learned from the Boston Marathon Bombings: Preparing for and Responding to the Attack”, *US Homeland Security and Governmental Affairs*, 10 July 2013. <http://www.hsgac.senate.gov/hearings/lessons-learned-from-the-boston-marathon-bombings-preparing-for-and-responding-to-the-attack>.

⁷⁴ Callahan, Kristin, “Lessons Learned from the Boston Bombings”, *UPI*, 11 July 2013.

http://www.upi.com/Top_News/US/2013/07/11/Lessons-learned-from-the-Boston-bombings/4741373575700/.

⁷⁵ Ritchie, Elspeth Cameron, “Mental Fallout from the Boston Bombings”, *Time*, 16 April 2013.

<http://nation.time.com/2013/04/16/mental-fallout-from-the-boston-bombings/>.

⁷⁶ Eligon and Cooper, 2013.

⁷⁷ Ibid.

⁷⁸ “3 Killed, More Than 140 Hurt in Boston Marathon Bombing”, CNN.com, 16 April 2013.

<http://news.blogs.cnn.com/2013/04/16/explosions-near-finish-of-boston-marathon-2/>.

⁷⁹ “MEMA Mission”, *The Massachusetts Emergency Management Agency*, 7 December 2004.

<http://www.mass.gov/eopss/agencies/mema/mema-mission.html>.

⁸⁰ “Terrorism”, *The Massachusetts Emergency Management Agency*, 27 January 2012.

<http://www.mass.gov/eopss/agencies/mema/ready-massachusetts/terrorism.html>.

⁸¹ “Business”, *The Massachusetts Emergency Management Agency*, 5 June 2013.

<http://www.mass.gov/eopss/agencies/mema/plan-prep/business/>.

during an emergency”. They are also responsible for coordinating the responses to any requests for aid from local authorities.⁸²

In addition to other units, MEMA contains a “Planning Unit” who works with a series of organisations (i.e., municipal, state, federal and volunteer) to focus efforts on emergency management planning issues. They do so by ensuring that different communities appropriately develop and maintain their “Comprehensive Emergency Plans” (CEMP) which should deal with the various stages of response, including: mitigation, preparedness, response and recovery. They also provide support for planning towards hazard-specific events such as an act of terror.⁸³ In the event of an incident such as an act of terrorism, response is coordinated through the protocols of the Incident Command System (ICS) and the National Incident Management System (NIMS) as co-ordinated and developed by the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA).⁸⁴

The purpose of NIMS is to provide a nationwide approach to the management of incidents regardless of the “cause, size, location or complexity”.⁸⁵ It is important to note that NIMS is not a response plan, nor is it a communication plan. Rather, NIMS is an organisation plan in an attempt to synthesise concepts, principles and procedures in the management of incidents. NIMS helps to convey best practices and lessons learned and encourages standardisation and interoperability between different agencies in the event of a crisis. NIMS focuses its attention on five areas: “preparedness, communications and information management, resource management, command management and ongoing management and maintenance”.⁸⁶

The ICS is part of the command management aspect of NIMS. It aims to ensure a standardised approach to the on-scene management of an incident. The approach: “Allows for the integration of facilities, equipment, personnel, procedures and communications operating within a common organizational structure; Enables a coordinated response among various jurisdictions and functional agencies, both public and private; Establishes common processes for planning and managing resources”.⁸⁷

MEMA – Response plan

The Massachusetts Comprehensive Emergency Management Plan (CEMP) provides a detailed plan for “integration and coordination of the emergency management activities of all levels of government, volunteer organizations, and the private sector in the Commonwealth of Massachusetts”.⁸⁸ CEMP follows the principles set out by ICS and NIMS.

In addition to supplying information on a range of different types of incidents, ranging from droughts and earthquakes to acts of terrorism, CEMP also supplies information relating to the roles and responsibilities of different groups (e.g., local vs. state). In addition, in relation to terrorism, as outlined in the plan, the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) are required to

⁸² Ibid.

⁸³ “Planning Unit”, *The Massachusetts Emergency Management Agency*, 7 December 2004. <http://www.mass.gov/eopss/agencies/mema/planning-unit.html>.

⁸⁴ “Incident Management”, *The Massachusetts Emergency Management Agency*, 13 May 2013. <http://www.mass.gov/eopss/home-sec-emerg-resp/response/incident-mgmt/>.

⁸⁵ FEMA, *National Incident Management Systems (NIMS) Overview*, 2011. https://s3-us-gov-west-1.amazonaws.com/dam-production/uploads/20130726-1853-25045-0014/nims_overview.pdf. [p. 2]

⁸⁶ Ibid., p. 5.

⁸⁷ “Incident Command System”, *FEMA*, no date. <http://www.fema.gov/incident-command-system>.

⁸⁸ Massachusetts Emergency Management Agency, *Massachusetts Comprehensive Emergency Management Plan*, January 2011. <http://www.mass.gov/eopss/docs/mema/cemp/macemp-basicplan-2011.pdf>. [p. 1]

take the main responsibility for criminal investigations surrounding an act of terror. MEMA are responsible for warning and notification services to a range of stakeholders in the event of a crisis.

In relation to response activities, CEMP sets out four goals: to obtain and maintain situational awareness of an incident, establish an “incident planning cycle”, mobilise and send out resources to affected areas based on four priorities (“life safety, incident stabilization, protection of infrastructure and property, preservation of the environment”⁸⁹), and lastly, to establish the transition from response to recovery. The following sequence of events are intended to take place in the event of an emergency:⁹⁰

Pre-Impact:

- MEMA constantly monitor for any potential events that could pose a risk.
- “If a potential threat is identified, MEMA will increase its readiness” by taking a series of measures (e.g., increase in monitoring activities, plans and procedures are reviewed, local, state and federal officials are briefed, communications are tested etc.)

Initial action:

- Activation of relevant bodies and operations (e.g., State and Regional Operations Centres).
- Briefing other officials
- Mobilisation of resources

Continuing action:

- Maintain communication with affected areas
- Continue briefing officials
- Coordinate any required need for additional assistance
- Initiate damage assessment teams

Demobilisation:

- Begin to release staff that are no longer required.

In addition to setting out the response sequence of events strategy, CEMP provides further information relating to who is responsible for declaring a state of emergency (i.e., different officials at the local, state and federal level). As well as details regarding the management of information and recovery actions.

Although only briefly discussed here, the full version of the CEMP contains extensive guidance and instructions for specific co-ordination activities in the event of an incident.

2.2.2 Lessons learned

On the 10th July 2013, the United States Senate, Committee on Homeland Security and Government Affairs, One Hundred Thirteenth Congress held the first session on lessons learned from the Boston marathon bombings.⁹¹ In the opening statement, chairman, Thomas

⁸⁹ Ibid., p. 20.

⁹⁰ Ibid., p. 23.

⁹¹ Committee on Homeland Security and Governmental Affairs, “Lessons Learned from the Boston Marathon Bombings: Preparing for and Responding to the Attack”, *US Homeland Security and Governmental Affairs*, 10

R. Carper made it clear that whilst response plans were well executed, saving many lives, lessons can be learned to deal with future incidents. The hearing involved a series of statements from different agencies of which key elements regarding any lessons learned will be summarised here.⁹²

As stated in his opening statement, Carper also emphasised that the timing of the Boston attacks with the marathon coincided with a period of time in which extensive planning and training had taken place to cater for response efforts to the marathon.⁹³

“The state, city and first responder community engaged in extensive planning to support the Marathon every year. This included preparing for mass casualties among the runners; maintaining a heavy police, EMS, first responder, and volunteer presence; and running a table top exercise each year prior to the event to practice responding to different types of scenarios”.

Crucially, it is important to point out that at this stage, lessons learned here are somewhat subjective and are largely positive. Nevertheless, in the (current) absence of further information, they do contribute to our understanding of what is perceived to “work” in responding to an act of terror.

FEMA – Richard Serino, Deputy Administrator

- The attacks demonstrated the need for a federal, state and local approach to crisis response to ensure close coordination across officials.
- Immediate response was not just carried out by authorities, but also by members of the public “bystanders and volunteers” played a fundamental role in assisting authorities. Here FEMA’s principles of “Whole Community”, that is collective emergency management, came into action (which is part of the National Preparedness System approach).⁹⁴
 - It is important to point out that at this stage it is unclear whether authorities actively pursued the inclusion of members of the public in responding to the events or whether this simply emerged. In their speech they did however, note the importance of future plans and training exercises involving citizen responders and therefore note the importance of cultivating additional response capabilities: “Plans, training and exercises must include strategies that ensure the health and safety of first responders and citizen responders, and training associated with the prevention and detection of secondary attacks”.⁹⁵
 - The extent to which citizen responders were incorporated is unclear. As identified by a news article in the New York Times, in the immediate aftermath of the attacks, one citizen, a physician was initially held back by the police from assisting but was subsequently allowed to help once she told them she was a medical professional, illustrating the potential lack of clarity over maintaining safety vs. engaging with the “whole community” approach.⁹⁶

July 2013. <http://www.hsgac.senate.gov/hearings/lessons-learned-from-the-boston-marathon-bombings-preparing-for-and-responding-to-the-attack>.

⁹² Ibid.

⁹³ Ibid., p. 4.

⁹⁴ Ibid., p. 3.

⁹⁵ Ibid., p. 16.

⁹⁶ Eligon, John, and Michael Cooper, “2 Blasts at Boston Marathon Kill at Least 3 and Injure More Than 100”, *The New York Times*, 15 April 2013. <http://www.nytimes.com/2013/04/16/us/explosions-reported-at-site-of-boston-marathon.html>.

- The attacks illustrated the importance of the adequate use of funds for emergency preparedness and response measures, including training initiatives.
 - There is a need for further funding to support FEMA’s approach to collective preparedness, as well as to conduct table-top exercises to bring a range of stakeholders together to help prepare for and increase their resilience to potential, future threats.
- Future priorities also lie with improving mass casualty planning, particularly in engaging with and to help train different types of responders (e.g., first responders as well as citizen responders).
- *MEMA – Kurt N. Schwarz, Director.*
- Emphasised the value of investments into local, state and federal homeland security since 2001 in positively influencing the response capabilities to the attacks.
 - “Within seconds of the bomb blasts at the finish line of the Boston Marathon, an array of personnel, resources and capabilities - many funded with federal homeland security grant dollars - were brought to bear to triage and care for the wounded, communicate with the public, provide situational awareness for decision makers, ensure the safety and security of the public and critical infrastructure, set up a joint command centre, and ultimately identify and apprehend the suspected terrorists”.⁹⁷
- The joint effort to respond to the attacks was illustrated by the inclusion of the Multi-agency coordination centre that had been set up to manage security and response to the marathon;
 - “On race day, an 80 person Multi-Agency Coordination Center - - a MACC -- was operational in the State’s Emergency Operations Center at the Massachusetts Emergency Management Agency. Representatives from Boston’s police, fire and EMS services, and public safety personnel from the other 7 cities and towns along the 26.2 mile course, were present in the MACC along with key state and federal public safety agencies... were deployed as part of an all-hazards operational plan”.⁹⁸
- Claimed interoperability to be a success;
 - “Over the years, millions of dollars have been invested under local, regional and state interoperability plans, and our investments in mutual aid channels, tactical channel plans, radio towers, new radios, and specialized training allowed first responders, as well as command level personnel, to effectively communicate by radio between agencies, between disciplines, and between jurisdictions”.⁹⁹
- Preparedness table-top exercises prior to the marathons helped authorities collaborate and, essentially, prepare for any potential threat to face the race. Such activities once again contributed to authorities capabilities in responding to the attacks.
- Emphasised the importance of the role of the public in contributing to response efforts.
- They are currently conducting a more extensive review in the form of an “After Action Report” of lessons learned and future action items in response to the attacks.¹⁰⁰

Boston Police Department – Edward F. Davis, Police Commissioner

⁹⁷ Committee on Homeland Security and Governmental Affairs, 2013, p. 18.

⁹⁸ Ibid., p. 20.

⁹⁹ Ibid., p. 22.

¹⁰⁰ Ibid., p. 24.

- Praised the response capabilities of authorities and members of the public at the scene of the attacks, emphasising the important role that all of these individuals played. Claimed that further effort by law enforcement agencies need to be developed so as to include the public in response efforts: “Law enforcement needs to continue to seek opportunities and new ways to encourage dialogue and cooperation with the community as we look to stop violent extremists.”¹⁰¹
- Praised the police investigation in apprehending those responsible, and cited the importance of “dedicated training, relationships already in place, an engaged and informed public, and an unprecedented level of coordination, cooperation¹⁰² and information sharing on the line by local, state and federal agencies”.
- The Boston police department learned the importance and value of engaging the community through social media, where communication played an important role in the immediate response to the attacks, as well as on-going investigations.
- Notes that information sharing needs to be improved when dealing with the threat of terrorism, particularly between the Boston Police Force and the Joint Terrorism Task Force.
- Noted the problems with communication at the scene of the attacks where the capacity of cell phone use was over-run, forcing authorities to exclusively rely on radios. Emphasised the need for law enforcement agencies to have access to “secure radio bandwidth in a public safety spectrum dedicated exclusively to public safety use now, as it is the only way to communicate during an event of this magnitude”.¹⁰³

RAND Office of External Affairs – Arthur L. Kellermann, Emergency Physician, Policy analyst

- Argued that bystanders played an important role in the initial response to the attacks.
- Officials in Boston had received extensive training in preparing and responding to a terrorist attack. Some pre-hospital and hospital-based responders had even attended a conference, “Tales of Our Cities” where they learnt how others (e.g., those in Mumbai, London and Madrid) had responded to terrorism.
- Boston’s hospitals had extensive disaster plans in place, contributing to their excellent response capabilities. There is a need for continued healthcare preparedness.

Whilst the committee did identify some important lessons learned from the attacks, many are somewhat subject and this is an on-going investigative process. In addition to further understanding how preparedness and response can be enhanced, later in the year the committee will also examine whether the attacks could have been prevented.

¹⁰¹ Ibid., p. 28.

¹⁰² Ibid., p. 27.

¹⁰³ Ibid., p. 30.

Overall, the 15 April 2013 attacks demonstrated the perceived importance of continued local, state and federal funding towards crisis response capabilities. Lessons learned from the attacks included the supposed importance of coordination for emergency response among federal, state and local officials. Whether intentionally encouraged or not, the Boston attacks also reinforced the use of a “whole community” approach to crisis management, where those members of the public at the scene of the attacks played a crucial role in both the immediate aftermath of the attacks and in the subsequent police investigation. The Boston Police emphasised the importance of effective communications in responding to a crisis, they noted that social media played a crucial role in enabling them to communicate and engage with the affected community. They also noted the failure of cell phone access in the immediate response to the attacks and stressed the importance for a secure radio bandwidth. Finally, lessons learned highlighted the importance of adequate preparedness, training and strategies for different authorities, particularly within healthcare.

2.3 CONCLUSION

The aim of this chapter has been to utilise two case studies, the 2005 London attacks and the 2013 Boston attacks, to try to understand lessons learned from emergency response capabilities. Due to the time scale of the incidents used within this chapter, lessons learned from the 2005 London attacks were of a much more detailed nature. This was not the case for the 2013 Boston attacks, as investigations and reviews on response capabilities are still underway. However, both incidents provided the consortium with some lessons learned that are central to the aims and goals of the COSMIC project. In particular, the consortium will be able to use the findings to understand potential gaps and good practices in response capabilities.

Communication

Both the London and Boston attacks revealed the importance of effective communication capabilities in a crisis situation. During each of the attacks, authorities were somewhat hampered by the failure of communication systems, particularly with regard to the failure of mobile phone (cell) networks. The failure in communication resulted in the need for dedicate and secure radio bandwidth to be available to responders to help co-ordinate response efforts. During the London attacks this was further hampered by the fact that the three out of four of the incidents took place on the underground system which served to further restrict communications. Whilst the London attacks demonstrated the need for better communication between authorities and members of the public both directly and indirectly caught up in the attacks, the Boston attacks demonstrated the importance of alternative resilient communication strategies, particularly, as will be further seen in D2.2, the use of social media in opening up communication between authorities and the public.

Both attacks also demonstrated that the initial emergency work is carried out effectively by professional responders and ordinary people without (as far as we currently know) intentional coordination. As the communication difficulties in both cases seem to be persistent problems also identified in many other large-scale crisis situations, it seems that the need for resilient communication should be a priority for the COSMIC project.

Preparedness

Whilst both case studies demonstrated the necessity of preparedness activities in responding to a mass casualty incident, the Boston attacks proved the importance of the use of funding and extensive training and table-top exercises to help prepare for an emergency, such as that where authorities learned from other countries experiences of responding to acts of terrorism. It is important to note that the action of the emergency services in responding to the London attacks were also benefited by extensive training and coordination preparedness exercises.

Both case studies also revealed that further attention needs to be placed on ensuring that adequate healthcare and response plans are in place in order to prepare and respond to future threats.

The public

Both attacks demonstrated that engagement with the public during response activities of an act of terrorism are pivotal. On the one hand, whilst it is not yet clear whether citizen responders were encouraged to contribute to the response efforts following the attacks, the Boston attacks revealed the importance of a “whole community” approach to response strategies; that is involving those caught up in a crisis in crisis management strategies. Similarly the heroic efforts of members of the public at the scene of the London attacks also contributed to the response overall efforts. On the other hand, the London bombings proved the importance of ensuring that authorities adequately manage the survivors of an attack, that is to ensure that communication channels are opened up and that survivors’ information is recorded for recovery purposes, both in terms of the police investigation and the long-term wellbeing of survivors.

The findings from this chapter are essential in understanding where potential weaknesses lie in adequately responding to a crisis. Central to COSMIC is the need for better communication strategies in a crisis situation particularly amongst organisations and for communicating with other stakeholders. Accordingly, in order to widen our understanding of the role of alternative communication strategies following an act of terror, partners will focus their efforts on lessons learned from communication activities following the Boston attacks during Task 2.2, as will be reported in Deliverable 2.2 “Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations” of the COSMIC project.

3 EARTHQUAKES

In Chapter 3 partners will focus their attention on two case studies involving the occurrence of an earthquake. These case studies are: 1) the 7th September 1999 Athens earthquake and 2) the 12th January 2010 Haiti earthquake. The information on the two case studies was collected by government policies on operating procedures, news articles and other scientific literature. Partners decided to focus their attention to the aforementioned crisis to stress the importance of a country having a well-structured preparedness plan, which includes valuable measures taken and actions performed when dealing with this type of crises.

Depending on their magnitude, earthquakes, may have severe short-term and long-term impacts on a society, its economy and the surrounding environment. For further information, please see Table 2 (below):¹⁰⁴

Table 2: Short and long term impacts of an earthquake.

	Social Impacts	Economic Impacts	Environmental Impacts
Short-term (immediate) Impacts	People may be killed or injured. Homes may be destroyed. Transport and communication links may be disrupted. Water pipes may burst and water supplies may be contaminated.	Shops and business may be destroyed. Looting may take place. The damage to transport and communication links can make trade difficult.	The built landscape may be destroyed. Fires can spread due to gas pipe explosions. Fires can damage areas of woodland. Landslides may occur. Tsunamis may cause flooding in coastal areas.
Long-term Impacts.	Disease may spread. People may have to be re-housed, sometimes in refugee camps.	The cost of rebuilding a settlement is high. Investment in the area may be focused only on repairing the damage caused by the earthquake. Income could be lost.	Important natural and human landmarks may be lost.

This chapter will investigate the two case studies in terms of national preparedness for such an event, operating procedures that were followed during the event and finally, lessons learned from each of these earthquakes.

3.1 ATHENS EARTHQUAKE (1999)

On the 7th of September 1999, Greece's capital, Athens, was hit by an earthquake, measuring 5.9 on the Richter scale. The earthquake's duration was around 15 seconds and the epicentre was located approximately 18 km to the northwest of the city centre.¹⁰⁵ The Athens

¹⁰⁴ BBC, "BBC - GCSE Bitesize: Effects of an earthquake", BBC GCSE Bitesize, no date. http://www.bbc.co.uk/schools/gcsebitesize/geography/natural_hazards/earthquakes_rev3.shtml

¹⁰⁵ Elenas, A., "Athens Earthquake of 7 September 1999: Intensity and Observed Damages". *ISSET Journal of Earthquake Technology*, Vol. 40, March 2003, pp. 77-97.

earthquake occurred only 21 days after a large earthquake in Izmit, Turkey, and there are claims that the second one was triggered by the first one.¹⁰⁶

The severe and heavy damage was concentrated in the areas of Ano Liosia, Axarnes and Thrakomakedones, at a distance of 6 to 12 km from the epicentre, but medium to heavy damage was also observed in scattered areas far away from the epicentre, such as Adames, N. Liosia, Western Metamorfofi, Anthoupoli, Dasos Xaidariou, Lioumi and Prosfygika of Aigaleo, although damage in these areas cannot be solely associated with the close distance from the epicentre.¹⁰⁷

The earthquake occurred at approximately 2:56 pm on a Tuesday and consequently, the majority of the people that died were at their workplace and were mainly found under the ruins of three factory facilities that were operational at the time of the quake. One of the factories, Ricomex, where 39 people died, can be seen in the figure below.¹⁰⁸ The total number of casualties was 143 while the number of the injured was about 1200.¹⁰⁹

Figure 2¹¹⁰: The Ricomex factory that cost the lives of 39 people.

The aftermath of the earthquake included the following outcomes:¹¹¹

- 2,700 buildings either collapsed or suffered major damages and had to be demolished while over 35,000 buildings suffered minor to average damage. Damage mainly occurred on illegal buildings, buildings with pilotis, buildings constructed on an inappropriate soil and finally buildings with subsequently uncontrolled interventions in the supporting structure.

¹⁰⁶ Papadopoulos, G., "The Athens, Greece, Earthquake (Ms 5.9) of 7 September 1999: An Event Triggered by the İzmit, Turkey, 17 August 1999 Earthquake?", *Seismological Society of America*, Vol. 92, No. 1, February 2002, pp. 312-321.

¹⁰⁷ European Centre on Prevention and Forecasting of Earthquakes, "Newsletter of the European Centre on Prevention and Forecasting of Earthquakes", Issue 3, December 1999, p.37. <http://ecpfe.oasp.gr/sites/default/files/NEWSLETTERNo3.pdf>

¹⁰⁸ Newsbomb, "13 years from the deadly Athens earthquake", *Newsbomb*, 2012. <http://www.newsbomb.gr/koinwnia/story/232232/13-hronia-apo-ton-foniko-seismo-tis-athinas>

¹⁰⁹ Ibid.

¹¹⁰ Arthrosyllektis Blogspot, "ΑΡΘΡΟΣΥΛΛΕΚΤΗΣ by Dyosmaraki (3): Ρικομέξ : 12 Χρόνια τους τρώνε την αποζημίωση", 2011. <http://arthrosyllektis.blogspot.gr/2011/02/12.html>

¹¹¹ Earthquake Planning and Protection Organisation (OASP), "Knowledge is protection", Athens, 2007. <http://www.oasp.gr/sites/default/files/Earthquake%20-%20Knowledge%20is%20protection.pdf>

- Of a total of 304 nurseries of Attica, 17 buildings were identified as being in red condition (unsuitable for use) and more than 60 buildings were identified as being in yellow condition (temporarily unsuitable for use).
- Repairs and reconstruction of buildings. The costs amounted to 183 million euro; 35 million euros for demolition costs, 78 million euros for transportable bungalows, 90 million euros to subsidize rent and 37 million euros for infrastructure projects.
- Problems with telecommunication occurred within the first 4 hours of the earthquake. Landlines and mobile phones were switched off (jammed) due to minor damages, but mainly due to heavy use of the network where everyone was trying to reach their friends and families to check if they were safe, or from neighbours of collapsed buildings who were trying to inform the emergency services about the incidents.
- An initiative by the Ministry of Health set up a programme of vaccinations against influenza for earthquake victims over the age of 65 and for children to protect vulnerable groups in the camps and assist them in dealing with the upcoming winter.

3.1.1 Standard operating procedures

The General Secretariat for Civil Protection (GSCP) identifies projects, actions and preparedness measures implemented in Greece for the mitigation and management of risks from crisis, including earthquakes. The GSCP's main purpose is to assign roles to all national bodies, such as the Ministry of Environment, the Ministry of Health, Civil Protection offices, local authorities, and provide guidance for coordinated action when dealing with any type of crises. The earthquake preparedness measures presented below were issued by GSCP in 2009 to ensure that all constructions were resistant to earthquakes (buildings and in general technical infrastructure such as water tanks and bridges). Due to timing, these measures only became operational after the 1999 earthquake.¹¹²

- Pre-seismic check of public buildings and community services such as hospitals and educational institutions.
- Liability adequacy tests and disposal procedures of materials and means for the temporary housing of the victims such as tents and bedding.
- Informing and educating citizens about self-protection measures against earthquakes.
- Education of the public on earthquake protection at home, at school and at work, and especially training of the community in ways of protection, in order to develop earthquake awareness.
- Upgrading of contingency planning for earthquakes according to the General Plan of Civil Protection "XENOKRATIS" in order to improve the response of the Civil Protection Mechanism after earthquake.
- Development and conduction of civil protection exercises for the efficient emergency response to an earthquake in order to evaluate the relevant planning while training all staff involved in such a crisis.
- Upfront determination and control of the premises organisation camps as well as of sites of refuge for citizens following an earthquake, based on the corresponding planning.

¹¹² General Secretariat for Civil Protection, "Civil Protection Planning and Actions to address the dangers of seismic events", 2009.

http://www.gscp.gr/ggpp_cms_files/dynamic/c126657/file/SxediasmNEOJul2009Seismon_el_GR.pdf

A year before the earthquake struck Athens, the Ministry of Internal Affairs approved a General Plan of Civil Protection with the codename Xenokratis.¹¹³ Its purpose was to develop an effective system to address catastrophic events and ensure the safety of civilians' lives, health and property. Specifically, Xenokratis provided the following much needed preparedness measures, which would be implemented by all national bodies, depending on the role they were assigned to in Xenokratis:¹¹⁴

- Identify the relevant departments and agencies as well as institutions which direct and coordinate the operational forces at all levels.
- Provide essential information to the pertinent authorities for the assessment of situations and risks, identification of vulnerable areas and subsequently the drawing up of specific projects within the framework of the basic project "Xenokratis" to deal with the corresponding risks.
- Guidelines are provided for:
 - the development of strategies and tactics,
 - the proper organisation and equipment of agencies,
 - configuration of an operational philosophy for timely mobilization, motivation, direction and coordination of manpower and resources.
- Potential logistics capabilities are defined for troubleshooting both operational forces, and the affected citizens.
- Finally, a communications system is forecasted providing an information flow between all services and agents involved in crisis management.

Xenokratis states that in order for all Civil Protection services to mobilize efficiently during a crisis, the following phases should be followed:¹¹⁵

- 1st Phase (Usual Readiness): This phase includes measures and actions of the State apparatus, which help prepare for the next phase actions. The first data and information referring to an occurrence or an imminent catastrophic event is evaluated to form a reliable estimate of the event's catastrophic magnitude. Communication systems and data flow channels are activated to support decision making between all relevant stakeholders. Means of civil protection are recorded and checked for adequacy and suitability.
- 2nd Phase (Increased Readiness): In case information from the previous phase is verified then a wider mobilization of the civil protection mechanism occurs at all levels. All executive and operational services are placed on full alert for the execution of their mission while at the same time taking preventive measures, where necessary.
- 3rd Phase (Immediate Mobilization/Intervention): After a catastrophic event has occurred, the full civil protection mechanism is activated by the GSCP. Gathering of information about the size and intensity of destruction is followed by an overall evaluation of the situation by the GSCP. Local authorities and civil protection bodies are in constant communication in order to coordinate all actions which will lead to the protection of civilians who managed to avoid injury and the rescue of any civilians who are in need of help.

¹¹³ Arthrosyllektis, 2011.

¹¹⁴ General Secretariat for Civil Protection (originally issued by State Printing Office), 2008. http://www.gscp.gr/ggpp_cms_files/dynamic/c60463/file/ypapofasi12992003xenokrati_el_GR.pdf

¹¹⁵ Arthrosyllektis, 2011.

- 4th Phase (Rehabilitation/Assistance): The last phase involves the immediate assistance to the affected population. Damages are evaluated by experts, decisions are made and measures are taken to repair the damage and ensure that similar damages can be prevented in the future.

Immediately after the earthquake in Athens in 1999, all human and material resources of the key response services were mobilised according to their roles assigned to them in Xenokratis. The National Emergency Operations Centre at General Secretariat for Civil Protection was activated, as well as the Operational Centres of critical Services, i.e., Fire Services, Earthquake Planning and Protection Organisation, National Centre for Emergency Health Care¹¹⁶.

Communications between disaster assessment teams and the Operation Centres were established soon after, through hand radios. Rescue teams from Cyprus, France, Germany, Hungary, Israel, Russian Federation, Switzerland and Turkey, arrived the next day in order to assist HRT and in search and rescue operations.

Information on the situation was difficult to obtain since cellular phones and landlines were blocked and initial feedback came from police and fire departments through their radio network. The media were also communicating a rough picture to the public via television and radio frequencies. They were also very helpful at informing people and in less than an hour after the earthquake official instructions were disseminated through the media on what people should do and not do during the emergency situation.¹¹⁷

3.1.2 Lessons learned

Unfortunately, Xenokratis had been active only for the year prior to the earthquake, but there was still not enough time available for the national response mechanism to be fully prepared for a major disaster. Bureaucracy and a very slow public mechanism that lacked the ability to adjust to such changes were the primary reasons for the slow implementation process of Xenokratis. This lack of preparedness led to miscommunication between the national bodies and the non-government organisations (NGO), both domestic (Hellenic Rescue Team - HRT) and foreign.¹¹⁸ This resulted in delays in information flow. Also, at the time of the earthquake, NGOs did not enjoy much appreciation, respect and trust from the national bodies, which meant that they would often be neglected in the information exchange. The result was that when the NGOs got to a collapsed building it was up to them to cooperate and coordinate a rescue operation since national bodies were either not present or when they were, they would have already engaged in the rescue mission without waiting for assistance that could probably not arrive in time.¹¹⁹

The Seismological Laboratory of the University of Athens, the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Forecasting of Earthquakes and Geodynamics National Observatory of Athens organised an event entitled "10 years of Athens earthquake: experiences and lessons learned, "which took place on the 3rd and 4th of December 2009, in the "Aristotle" auditorium of the

¹¹⁶ European Centre on Prevention and Forecasting of Earthquakes, "Newsletter of the European Centre on Prevention and Forecasting of Earthquakes", Issue 3, December 1999, p.40. <http://ecpfe.oasp.gr/sites/default/files/NEWSLETTERNo3.pdf>

¹¹⁷ Ibid.

¹¹⁸ Dedas, A., *Το παν είναι να θέλεις*, Thessaloniki, 2006.

¹¹⁹ Ibid.

Physics Department at the University of Athens. The purpose of the event was to review the experience and lessons learned from the Athens earthquake and other major earthquakes as well as to suggest future actions which could eliminate or at least minimise the dangers that are present when earthquakes strike. The findings are summarised below:¹²⁰

- The magnitude of an earthquake is not the sole factor culpable for major disasters and victims. The proximity of an earthquake's outbreak and the shallow focal depth plays also an important role to the outcome. Therefore, even intermediate - size earthquakes can cause disastrous results.
- Even relatively small active faults can cause casualties and heavy damage when located near highly populated areas.¹²¹
- The rupture directivity of the earthquake and local conditions (soil, topography) had a significant effect on the Athens earthquake.
- The need has emerged to develop and implement a dense and single common network of all seismological agencies and for the issuance of joint statements. This would eliminate the issuance of statements containing for example different magnitudes of the same earthquake, which might prove misleading both for the national services and the public.
- Until 1999, the seismic history of Athens was not negligible. Even in areas that are not the most seismically active, destructive earthquakes can occur, as in the cases of Athens and Kozani.
- The small and very short pre-seismic activity of the Athens earthquake did not leave room for utilization to alert the population. Moreover, the event of catastrophic earthquakes need not be accompanied by pre-seismic activity, as was confirmed by Kalamata earthquake later on.
- The devastation caused by the earthquake highlighted the problem of the continuous expansion of the urban fabric (without programming and design). As it was so aptly observed, "Athens hit the earthquake" and not "the earthquake hit Athens".

Unfortunately, no lessons learned are available concerning the search and rescue operations other than that the communication and trust between national bodies and NGOs should be established as the latter ones can provide the necessary resources to help with search and rescue missions. The future actions that were proposed during the previously mentioned event are described below, although they concentrate mostly on the scientific side of the crises.

- Mapping and evaluation active faults especially those identified near major cities.
- Maintain and enhance a single network of seismograph and accelerographs with dense coverage of Greece and real time data transmission.
- A single accepted speed model for the Greek area (representative of / based on the structure of each region).
- More detailed mapping of intense topographic anomalies in and around the built environment.
- Soil classification and characterization and seismic microzonation, at least for the case of plans for the expansion of a city.

¹²⁰ Associate Professor Vasiliki Kouskouna, Head of Seismology Lab, Faculty of Geology and Geo-Environment, National & Kapodistrian University of Athens, <http://www.geol.uoa.gr/attachments/article/285/earthquake1999.pdf>

¹²¹ Papadopoulos, G.A., Ganas A. and Pavlides, S.B., "The problem of seismic potential assessment: Case study of the unexpected earthquake of 7 September 1999 in Athens, Greece". *Earth Planets Space*, Vol. 54, 2002, pp. 9- 18.

- Necessity for additional study of the history of earthquakes due to the long period of recurrence in certain areas (e.g., Kozani, Athens).
- Continuous monitoring and evaluation of seismic activity, and focus on the spatiotemporal progress (further study the features of pre-seismic series).
- Seismic Early Warning System for the safety of network infrastructure utilities (e.g., natural gas) and the safety of industrial facilities (chemical, nuclear, etc.).
- Mapping vulnerability of existing important buildings and financial incentives to reinforce them.
- Creating registry of building manufacturers, quality control building materials.
- Integration of those conclusions in the next update of Anti-seismic Regulation.
- Educating citizens, with priority given to pupils and integrating relevant courses at school.

The 1999 Athens earthquake highlighted the need for preparedness measures to be implemented nationwide. Unfortunately, even though a year before the earthquake the Ministry of Internal Affairs approved a General Plan of Civil Protection with the codename Xenokratis, which provided the aforementioned measures, there was still not enough time available for the plan to be properly applied and for the national response mechanism to be set in full motion. Even if the lessons learned from the crisis concerned mainly geological findings such as that even intermediate sized earthquakes can have disastrous effects on a society if they are in close proximity to a highly populated area and if their focal depth is shallow, communication and trust between national bodies and NGOs should be improved in order to mitigate the effects of a future crisis.

3.2 HAITI EARTHQUAKE (2010)

The Haiti earthquake occurred on Tuesday, 12 January 2010, with a catastrophic magnitude of 7 on the Richter scale, making it the biggest earthquake to hit the region in over 200 years. Overall, 3,500,000 people were affected by the earthquake in some way, while 188,383 houses were badly damaged and 105,000 were completely destroyed.¹²² Unfortunately, the earthquake's epicentre was located approximately 25 km west of the country's capital Port-au-Prince, which suffered major damages in most of its buildings (see the figure below) and led to a death toll of 316,000 according to the Haitian government. Although this is a widely disputed number and is often thought of as deliberately inflated by the government in order to keep receiving international aid.¹²³

¹²² Disasters Emergency Committee, "HAITI EARTHQUAKE FACTS AND FIGURES", 2011. <http://www.dec.org.uk/haiti-earthquake-facts-and-figures>

¹²³ O'Connor, Maura, "Two Years Later, Haitian Earthquake Death Toll in Dispute", Columbia Journalism Review, 2012. http://www.cjr.org/behind_the_news/one_year_later_haitian_earthqu.php?page=all

Figure 3: Port-Au-Prince after the earthquake¹²⁴.

The earthquake left the country devastated, with 60 percent of government, administrative and economic infrastructure destroyed, as well as parliament and judicial sector buildings.¹²⁵ The country's economy was also badly affected with the total damages and losses estimated at US \$7.8 billion (US \$4.3 billion in physical damage and US \$3.5 in economic losses). The damages and losses are equivalent to more than 120 percent of Haiti's 2009 gross domestic product.¹²⁶

The primary and secondary effects of the earthquake are summarised in the table below:¹²⁷

Table 3: Primary and secondary effects of the Haiti earthquake.

Primary (caused directly by the earthquake)	Secondary (result from primary effects)
316,000 people were killed and 1 million people were made homeless. 3 million people were affected by the earthquake	1 in 5 people lost their jobs because so many buildings were destroyed. Haiti's largest industry, clothing was one of the worst affected
250,000 homes and 30,000 other buildings, including the President's Palace and 60% of government buildings, were either destroyed or badly damaged	The large number of deaths meant that hospitals and morgues became full and bodies then had to be piled up on the streets
Transport and communication links were also badly damaged by the earthquake	The large number of bodies meant that diseases, especially cholera, became a serious problem
Hospitals (50+) and schools (1,300+) were badly damaged, as was the airport's control	It was difficult getting aid into the area because of issues at the airport and

¹²⁴ Radio Netherlands Worldwide, "Haiti quake worst-ever disaster facing UN | Radio Netherlands Worldwide", 2010. <http://www.rnw.nl/english/article/haiti-quake-worst-ever-disaster-facing-un>

¹²⁵ U.N. Office of the Secretary General's Special Adviser, "Key Statistics | Haiti Relief", 2011. <http://www.lessonsfromhaiti.org/relief-and-recovery/key-statistics/>

¹²⁶ Ibid.

¹²⁷ Handy Geography, "Earthquake Case Study (Haiti – Poor) | Handy Geography", 2013. <http://handygeography.wordpress.com/gcse/the-restless-earth-revision-materials/earthquake-case-study-haiti-poor/>

tower	generally poor management of the situation
The main prison was destroyed and 4,000 inmates escaped	People were squashed into shanty towns or onto the streets because their homes had been destroyed leading to poor sanitation and health, and looting became a real problem

In order to deal with the aforementioned impacts, the international community launched an unprecedented and overwhelming response to aid the Haitian people. Immediately following the quake funds were released by the United Nations (\$10 million), Canada (\$4.8 million), European Commission (\$4.37 million) as well as other countries and organisations, ships, helicopters, transport planes, rescue teams and emergency relief equipment were sent to help the Haitian government execute search and rescue operations, provide food, safe water, shelter and medical care to the survivors.¹²⁸

In terms of economic help, most observers would agree that the international response to the quake was overwhelming. Haiti received an unprecedented amount of support: more than \$9bn in public and private donations. Official bilateral and multilateral donors pledged \$13 billion and, according to the UN Office of the Special Envoy for Haiti, almost 50% of these pledges (\$6 billion) have been disbursed. Private donations are estimated at \$3bn. Three years after the quake, there are still questions over how the funds were used, how many Haitians were reached, or whether the desired outcomes were achieved.¹²⁹

3.2.1 Standard operating procedures

Haiti, which has a long history of conflict, poor governance and crippling poverty, would not be able to organise their own national disaster mitigation and preparedness measures without external assistance. Examples of poor preparedness include the absence of any kind of building codes, meaning that most of the buildings in Haiti are not constructed for earthquake resistance and the use of poor construction materials.¹³⁰

Haiti's rudimentary National System for Risk and Disaster Management (SNGRD), prior to the 2010 earthquake, can be described as a network consisting of the Haitian government's Department of Civic Protections (DPC), regional support (CDEMA) and various civic groups, both international and local.¹³¹

CDEMA¹³² is the Caribbean Disaster Emergency Management Agency and it is a regional disaster management body formerly known as the Caribbean Disaster Emergency Response Agency (CDERA), whose website still hosts 12 situation reports on Haiti's earthquake,

¹²⁸ Huffington Post, "Haiti Earthquake: International Community Gives Millions In Aid", 2010. http://www.huffingtonpost.com/2010/01/13/international-aid-for-hai_n_422451.html

¹²⁹ Ramachandran, Vijaya and Julie Walz, "Haiti's earthquake generated a \$9bn response – where did the money go?", The Guardian, 2013. <http://www.theguardian.com/global-development/poverty-matters/2013/jan/14/haiti-earthquake-where-did-money-go>

¹³⁰ Inside Disaster, "Why Was the Destruction So Severe?", 2010. <http://insidedisaster.com/haiti/the-quake/why-was-the-destruction-so-severe>

¹³¹ National Preparedness Directorate, "Free College Courses, Textbooks, Materials - Academic Emergency Management and Related Courses", Federal Emergency Management Agency, 2013. <http://training.fema.gov/EMIWeb/edu/Comparative%20EM%20Book%20-%20Chapter%20-%20Haiti's%20Emergency%20Management%20System.doc>

¹³² Caribbean Disaster Emergency Management Agency, "What is CDEMA", 2013. http://www.cdema.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=89&Itemid=79

explaining in detail all the steps that were taken at the time to provide relief to the country.¹³³ Haiti is, among others, a participating state in that body.

CDEMA's main function is to respond to any disastrous event affecting any participating state, once a state requests such assistance. Other functions include the following:¹³⁴

- Mobilizing and coordinating disaster relief.
- Mitigating or eliminating, as far as practicable, the immediate consequences of disasters in Participating States.
- Providing immediate and coordinated response by means of emergency disaster relief to any affected Participating State.
- Securing, coordinating and providing to interested inter-governmental and non-governmental organisations reliable and comprehensive information on disasters affecting any Participating State.
- Encouraging –
 - the adoption of disaster loss reduction and mitigation policies and practices at the national and regional level.
 - cooperative arrangements and mechanisms to facilitate the development of a culture of disaster loss reduction
- Coordinating the establishment, enhancement and maintenance of adequate emergency disaster response capabilities among the Participating States.

CDEMA responds to any kind of disasters, such as earthquakes, floods, tropical hurricanes and landslides, and focuses heavily on preparedness against such environmental hazards. CDEMA has therefore included a variety of information on its website regarding the preparation and protection of homes and businesses against all possible threats.

The CDERA, UNDP (United Nations Development Programme) and USAID (United States Agency for International Development) collaborated and developed a plan for the integrated management of all natural and human-induced hazards in the region. The outcome of this collaboration was the Comprehensive Disaster Management (CDM) Strategy. The CDM Strategy aims to effectively manage all stages of the Disaster Management Cycle, which are: Prevention and Mitigation, Preparedness and Response, Recovery and Restoration/Rehabilitation. By June 2002 relevant agencies in the region adopted the CDM strategy framework¹³⁵, which was first submitted in June of 2001. The initial version of the framework¹³⁶ focused on a single goal, which was to promote sustainable development in the Caribbean. Furthermore, the framework's strategic objective was to integrate Comprehensive Disaster Management into the development processes of the CDERA's member countries realizing though that a realistic expectation of the plan would be that most, not all, of the member states would integrate disaster management into their developments plans and procedures.

¹³³ Caribbean Disaster Emergency Response Agency (CDERA), "CDERA News Centre Front Page > Haiti", 2010. <http://www.cdema.org/cgi-bin/cunews/exec/search.cgi?cat=56&template=index%2Fdefault.html&perpage=5&start=11>

¹³⁴ Caribbean Disaster Emergency Management Agency, "Activities of the Agency", 2013. http://www.cdema.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=358&Itemid=120

¹³⁵ The Caribbean Disaster Emergency Response Agency, "CDM Strategy and Programme Framework", 2009. http://www.cdema.org/index.php?option=com_joomdoc&task=doc_download&gid=7&Itemid=231

¹³⁶ Caribbean Disaster Emergency Management Agency, "Downloads | CMD Documents", 2009. http://www.cdema.org/index.php?option=com_joomdoc&task=doc_download&gid=4&Itemid=210

The overall planning period of the strategy was seven years and in order to organise the activities needed to achieve the strategic objective, five main intermediate results were defined.¹³⁷

- Stronger regional and national institutions to promote CDM.
- Research, education and training support for CDM.
- Major regional institutions and donors to incorporate CDM in their own programs and to promote CDM to their national members/clients.
- Preparedness, response and mitigation capability to be enhanced and integrated.
- Hazard information to be incorporated into development planning and decision making.

In 2007, the Enhanced CDM Strategy and Programme Framework 2007-2012 was issued.¹³⁸ Its purpose was “to strengthen regional, national and community level capacity for mitigation, management, and coordinated response to natural and technological hazards, and the effects of climate change”¹³⁹. The four priority outcomes that the Enhanced CDM Framework proposed are the following:

- Enhanced institutional support for CDM Program implementation at national and regional levels.
- An effective mechanism and programme for administering comprehensive disaster management knowledge has been established.
- Disaster Risk Management has been mainstreamed at national levels and incorporated into key sectors of national economies (including tourism, health, agriculture and nutrition).
- Enhanced community resilience in CDERA states/ territories to mitigate and respond to the adverse effects of climate change and disasters.

Their respective outputs derived from these four outcomes are presented in Table 44 (below).¹⁴⁰

3.2.2 Lessons learned

It is undeniable that the humanitarian aid provided by the international community to the Haitians was extensive. Food was provided to approximately four million people and 1.2 million were able to drink regular clean water while 1.5 million were placed in temporary shelters. The economic help has also reached Haitians in various forms. Agriculture and education were also assisted enabling school classes to start once again even without school buildings.^{141, 142}

Nonetheless, mistakes were made and there are many lessons to be learned from this disaster. With most of the local infrastructure destroyed, and the Haitians relying almost entirely on

¹³⁷ Ibid.

¹³⁸ Caribbean Disaster Emergency Management Agency, “Downloads | CMD Documents”, 2009. http://www.cdema.org/index.php?option=com_joomdoc&task=doc_download&gid=7&Itemid=210

¹³⁹ Ibid.

¹⁴⁰ Ibid.

¹⁴¹ Examiner.com, “Haiti earthquake relief efforts hampered by logistics problems - National Natural Disasters | Examiner.com”, 2010. <http://www.examiner.com/article/haiti-earthquake-relief-efforts-hampered-by-logistics-problems>

¹⁴² Holmes, J., “Learning the lessons of Haiti”, *HUMANITARIAN EXCHANGE MAGAZINE*, Issue 48, 2010, pp. 2-3. <http://www.odihpn.org/download/humanitarianexchange048>

external help, it was always going to be a difficult task coordinating such a vast relief operation and many challenges were to be faced. These challenges are discussed further below.

Table 4: Outcomes and Outputs of the Enhanced CDM Framework.

OUTCOME 1:	OUTCOME 2:	OUTCOME 3:	OUTCOME 4:
Enhanced institutional support for CDM Program implementation at national and regional levels	An effective mechanism and programme for management of comprehensive disaster management knowledge has been established	Disaster Risk Management has been mainstreamed at national levels and incorporated into key sectors of national economies (including tourism, health, agriculture and nutrition)	Enhanced community resilience in CDERA states/ territories to mitigate and respond to the adverse effects of climate change and disasters
↓	↓	↓	↓
OUTPUTS	OUTPUTS	OUTPUTS	OUTPUTS
<p>1.1 National Disaster Organizations are strengthened for supporting CDM implementation and a CDM program is developed for implementation at the national level</p> <p>1.2 CDERA CU is strengthened and restructured for effectively supporting the adoption of CDM in member countries</p> <p>1.3 Governments of participating states/ territories support CDM and have integrated CDM into national policies and strategies</p> <p>1.4 Donor programming integrates CDM into related environmental, climate change and disaster management programming in the region.</p> <p>1.5 Improved coordination at national and regional levels for disaster management</p> <p>1.6 System for CDM monitoring, evaluation and reporting being built</p>	<p>2.1 Establishment of a Regional Disaster Risk Reduction Network to include a Disaster Risk Reduction Centre and other centres of excellence for knowledge acquisition sharing and management in the region</p> <p>2.2 Infrastructure for fact-based policy and decision making is established /strengthened</p> <p>2.3 Improved understanding and local /community-based knowledge sharing on priority hazards</p> <p>2.4 Existing educational and training materials for Comprehensive Disaster Management are standardized in the region.</p> <p>2.5 A Strategy and curriculum for building a culture of safety is established in the region</p>	<p>3.1 CDM is recognized as the roadmap for building resilience and Decision-makers in the public and private sectors understand and take action on Disaster Risk Management</p> <p>3.2 Disaster Risk Management capacity enhanced for lead sector agencies, National and regional insurance entities, and financial institutions</p> <p>3.3 Hazard information and Disaster Risk Management is integrated into sectoral policies, laws, development planning and operations, and decision-making in tourism, health, agriculture and nutrition, planning and infrastructure</p> <p>3.4 Prevention, Mitigation, Preparedness, Response, recovery and Rehabilitation Procedures developed and Implemented in tourism, health, agriculture and nutrition, planning and infrastructure</p>	<p>4.1 Preparedness, response and mitigation capacity (technical and managerial) is enhanced among public, private and civil sector entities for local level management and response</p> <p>4.2 Improved coordination and collaboration between community disaster organizations and other research/data partners including climate change entities for undertaking comprehensive disaster management</p> <p>4.3 Communities more aware and knowledgeable on disaster management and related procedures including safer building techniques</p> <p>4.4 Standardized holistic and gender-sensitive community methodologies for natural and anthropogenic hazard identification and mapping, vulnerability and risk assessments, and recovery and rehabilitation procedures developed and applied in selected communities.</p> <p>4.5 Early Warning Systems for disaster risk reduction enhanced at the community and national levels</p>

Communication/Coordination

With all local communication mechanisms unavailable it was left to international bodies to organise and coordinate the relief efforts; and it was a slow start that required almost three days for aid from agencies and organisations from all over the world to reach Haiti. Lead agencies, such as United Nations’ Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), needed to provide more resources in order for communication and coordination to be more effective and efficient. That being said, the challenge of coordinating hundreds of humanitarian organisations, with not all of them being highly organised in their approach, was

huge and lead to the conclusion that “a new system of certification of capacity and experience needs to be looked at”.¹⁴³

Cooperation

Due to the absence of local infrastructure, humanitarians that arrived in Haiti needed the help of military entities operating in the area, particularly the United Nations Stabilization Mission in Haiti (MINUSTAH) but also units from the US and Canada, to facilitate the distribution of aid and assist in running local structures that were still operable, such as the airport or repairing the ones that were not, like the capital’s port. The cooperation of all these actors proved to be a great challenge and even though it was mostly successful, there is much room for improvement as long as more attention is paid to having all entities working together as a unit and not focusing on the humanitarian organisations themselves¹⁴⁴.

Sensitivity to local concerns

As soon as humanitarian organisations from all over the world arrived in Haiti, they were faced with chaotic conditions. It was only “logical” that they would base their efforts solely on their own capabilities and their evaluation of the situation while giving small, if any, importance to what locals had to say about what needed to be done. As it was proved though in the wake of the Indian Ocean tsunami five years ago, this kind of mentality leads to misjudgments about what is needed and errors in strategy, which may prove difficult to correct later on. The humanitarian community simply cannot afford not to work with national and local structures, to the fullest extent possible, however daunting and complex an operation may be.¹⁴⁵

Experience and knowledge

As it was mentioned earlier in the chapter, Haiti is a very poor country. Over half of its population of 10 million lives on less than US\$1 per day, and approximately 80% live on less than US\$2 per day.¹⁴⁶ The living standards are very low which made it even more difficult for the humanitarian organisations to distinguish between victims of the disaster and those, the majority of the Haitian population, who are suffering from a chronic form of deprivation. The challenge in this case is to focus all efforts on providing relief to the first group while understanding that longer-term recovery and development will help the second one.

Health

Even though the medical care that was provided to the Haitians was more than adequate, still not enough attention was paid for the prevention of epidemic, specifically a cholera outbreak which started in October of that year. Since August 2013, just over two years from the earthquake, it has killed at least 8,231 Haitians and hospitalized hundreds of thousands more while spreading to neighbouring countries including the Dominican Republic and Cuba.¹⁴⁷ Since the outbreak began in October 2010, more than 6% of Haitians have had the disease.¹⁴⁸

¹⁴³ Ibid.

¹⁴⁴ Ibid.

¹⁴⁵ Ibid.

¹⁴⁶ The World Bank, “Haiti Overview”, 2010. <http://www.worldbank.org/en/country/haiti/overview>

¹⁴⁷ Government of Haiti, Ministry of Health, 2013. http://www.mspp.gouv.ht/site/downloads/Rapport%20Web%2012.08_Avec_Courbes_Departementales.pdf

¹⁴⁸ Roos, Robert, "Cholera has struck more than 6% of Haitians", Center for Infectious Disease Research and Policy, 2013. <http://www.cidrap.umn.edu/news-perspective/2013/01/cholera-has-struck-more-6-haitians>

A recent report though suggests that the cholera outbreak in Haiti is tied to U.N. peacekeepers.¹⁴⁹ The report ties the arrival of a contingent of Nepalese peacemakers to an encampment in the village of Mirebalais to a dramatic increase in deaths from diarrhea and dehydration, which are symptoms of cholera. According to the report, the system of pipes that was built to expose of waste coming from the encampment presented “significant potential for contamination”.¹⁵⁰

Haiti was always going to face a difficult task in recovering from a major crisis, such as an earthquake, due to its long history of conflict, poor governance and crippling poverty. These conditions, along with the absence of any kind of building regulations, mean that most of the buildings in Haiti are not constructed for earthquake resistance. Moreover, the use of poor construction materials inhibited the process of developing any national disaster mitigation and preparedness measures without the use of external assistance.

The assistance given by the international community may have been extensive but more could have been done to improve communication, coordination and cooperation between international organisations and agencies arriving in Haiti. Also, more consideration should have been paid to local concerns while trying to utilise national and local structures to the country’s benefit, however difficult a task this may have been. In a country like Haiti where it is difficult to distinguish between the victims of the disaster and the chronically impoverished population, experience, tools and partnerships are needed to distribute aid to the most vulnerable ones. Finally, precautions should also be taken to ensure that conditions in the affected country are not made worse by visiting bodies, agencies and organisations.

3.3 CONCLUSION

This chapter focused on two case studies, the 1999 Athens earthquake and the 2010 Haiti earthquake, in order to provide some insight to response mechanisms and lessons learned from such crises. In the case of the 1999 Athens earthquake, even though Xenokratis, the national plan for civil protection, had been approved almost a year before the earthquake, there was still not enough time for the national mechanism to be fully prepared for such an event. As far as the Haitian crisis is concerned, rescue and relief operations may have been extensive but there was still room for improvement in certain areas such as the cooperation, coordination and communication of the actors involved. Specifically, the following findings will allow the consortium to research potential use of social media in favour of successful and effective rescue operations:

Communication

In both cases communication between humanitarian agencies and organisations could have been much more organised. National bodies in Athens could not provide important information to the NGOs that participated in the rescue operations and could also not facilitate the information flow between domestic and foreign organisations that needed to coordinate in

¹⁴⁹ Washington Post, “Cholera outbreak in Haiti tied to U.N. peacekeepers, report says”, 2013. http://articles.washingtonpost.com/2013-07-25/world/40861517_1_cholera-strain-cholera-epidemic-minustah

¹⁵⁰ Ibid.

order to achieve better results on the field. In Haiti on the other hand, the challenge of coordinating hundreds of humanitarian organisations was enormous and more resources could and should have been allocated by OCHA, especially in the initial phases of the operation, in order for rescue operations and information exchange to be more effective and efficient.

Preparedness

Both in Athens but much more in Haiti, preparedness levels were very low. In Athens, the Xenokratis plan for civil protection may had been active for almost a year but not enough measures were taken to ensure minimal damage in case of an earthquake. Haiti, due to its severe poverty and poor legislation concerning the construction of buildings, could not in any way have been prepared for such a devastating disaster.

The public

Both cases highlight the need for rescue teams to be able to communicate with the local population and exchange valuable information. A few hours after the Athens earthquake landlines and cellular communications were down due to network congestion; this lack of information input led to a considerable delay in the first response operations. In Haiti, the opposite phenomenon was observed; the humanitarian assistance community chose, in some cases, not to work with national and local structures and ignored their suggestions/information, something which might have led to false estimations of the existing conditions.

In this chapter partners tried to research potential shortcomings in search and rescue operations performed during the Athens and Haiti earthquakes. In both use cases, social media could have played an important role in mitigating those shortcomings, a feature which will be further analyzed in Task 2.2, resulting in Deliverable 2.2 “Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations” of the COSMIC project.

4 FLOODS AND STORMS

Chapter 4 will focus on outlining search and rescue procedures and operations in relation to storms and potential floods. Two different examples of floods will be examined: first, those stemming from Hurricane Katrina between 23 August and 30 August 2005, and second, the high water period and the following floods in parts of France, in 2010. Although these two crises may not seem comparable (because of the difference in magnitude in victims and damage), the core of the problem is the same. Citizens were confronted with changing weather circumstances, felt the threat upon their villages, houses and other properties and had to react under time pressure. Furthermore, European Member States can learn lessons from these examples, due to the similar circumstances and, at least partial, comparable legal and organisational systems. Both cases were crisis with a high societal impact. Although, the area affected by Katrina is accustomed to the presence of storms, tornados and hurricanes, the impact of this storm was enormous. Tens of thousands of citizens were evacuated to Northern states and many, have not returned.¹⁵¹ With that, Katrina developed into the costliest natural disaster faced by the USA.¹⁵² Floods in France are less frequent, so the damage and the number of victims from the storm Xynthia and the associated flood in 2010 was an unexpected event for the whole country.

In contrast to the types of crises described in the former chapters (like man-made crises), storms have some typical characteristics, which are essential for the efforts of search and rescue procedures and operations. First, floods are mostly creeping crises, that is to say, in many situations, there is a longer preparation phase than in the case of flash crises. In these cases, individuals' have time to take preparatory action (if not already taken after previous experiences with flooding) and even may evacuate in advance. Exceptions to this were the tsunamis in South-East Asia (December 2004, with more than 200,000 fatalities) and Japan (2011, with at least 12,000 deceased), which began more or less unannounced, leaving citizens in large areas no or barely any time to escape and protect their properties. Storms and floods can have a significant impact on humans but also on the local and national economy. As argued in chapter 3 of D 1.1, the European Commission stated, "of all types of natural disasters, flooding and storm events result in the greatest economic losses compared with other types of disasters in the EU (25% by flooding and 32% by storms)."¹⁵³

This chapter will focus on the different search and rescue procedures and actions in both cases. To give a complete view of the problems and complications with which search and rescue teams have to cope with during emergency situations, different relevant sources have been used; in addition to scientific literature partners have also examined official reports of ministries and those organisations involved in response efforts, as well as articles in newspapers. As with previous chapters, this chapter will first describe the two case studies, following which partners will provide a discussion of findings and a conclusion.

¹⁵¹ Light, Paul C., *The Katrina Effect on American Preparedness. A report on the lessons Americans learned in watching the Katrina catastrophe unfold*, New York University, (date unknown). <http://www.nyu.edu/ccpr/katrina-effect.pdf>

¹⁵² Rizzuto, Tracey E. & Laura K. Maloney, Organizing Chaos: Crisis Management in the Wake of Hurricane Katrina, *Professional Psychology: Research and Practice*, Vol. 39, Issue 1, 2008, pp. 77-85.

¹⁵³ European Commission, *An EU Strategy on adaptation to climate change. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the council, the European economic and social committee and the committee of the regions. Impact Assessment – Part 2*. Brussels. 16-4-2013. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2013:0216:FIN:EN:PDF>

4.1 HURRICANE KATRINA (2005)

After causing seven fatalities and vast material damage in the state of Florida, hurricane Katrina headed towards the Northwest to approach the city of New Orleans. On the morning of Monday, 29 August, Katrina made its second landfall, and moved inland into southeast Louisiana. Katrina, with winds exceeding 170 miles per hour, was one of the most powerful Atlantic storms ever, resulting the costliest natural disaster and one of the five deadliest hurricanes in the history of the United States. Ultimately, the storm and flood caused more than 80 billion dollars' worth of damage, more than 1800 people died as result of the flood or the direct consequences and the population of New Orleans was significantly reduced. Many people who escaped the disaster area found jobs in other parts of the US and never came back. In 2000 New Orleans had a population of 484,674, almost a year after Katrina, it declined to 223,388. Seven years after the event, the population has grown to an estimated 369,250 inhabitants.¹⁵⁴

4.1.1 Standard operating procedures

The vulnerability of New Orleans to storms and floods is well known. The city is situated seven feet below sea level on sinking clay soils, with the Mississippi River and Lake Pontchartrain at its borders. The city is also situated in a hurricane-prone area with storms and hurricanes coming from the Gulf of Mexico almost every year. In the last decades, the city had been sinking slowly farther below sea level, as the levees constructed upriver on the Mississippi prevented the replenishing of soils in the coastal wetlands that gave some protection to the city. Built to withstand Category 3 hurricanes, the levee system on which the city depended had not been adequately maintained, and requests for federal financing to reinforce the levees were repeatedly denied in recent years.¹⁵⁵

Disaster scholar Louise Comfort has described the policies that were in play during the threat of Hurricane Katrina.¹⁵⁶ According to her, two major policies were governing the response to the hurricane: the National Response Plan and the National Incident Management System. Both policies had undergone extensive review and had been accepted as part of the major reorganization of emergency management and security functions into the newly created Department of Homeland Security in January 2004.

The National Response Plan¹⁵⁷ was an adaptation of the former Federal Response Plan¹⁵⁸ that identified the roles and responsibilities of the 28 federal agencies in mobilising response to an actual disaster. The intent of the National Response Plan was to extend the design of interagency collaboration to state, county, and municipal levels of authority in response to a disaster. It was formally adopted in November 2004 in a major effort to improve coordination among levels of governmental jurisdiction in disaster response. The National Incident Management Plan (NIMS), adapted from the earlier Incident Command System initially developed by the U.S. Forest Service in response to recurring wildland fires in Southern California, created a common terminology and set of standards for disaster operations that

¹⁵⁴ United States Census Bureau, Referred to on the 13th of August 2013. <http://quickfacts.census.gov/qfd/states/22/2255000.html>

¹⁵⁵ Comfort, L.K., Cities at Risk: Hurricane Katrina and the Drowning of New Orleans. *Urban Affairs Review*, Vol. 41, Issue 4, 2006, pp. 501-516.

¹⁵⁶ Ibid.

¹⁵⁷ Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), *National Response Plan*, Washington, DC: Department of Homeland Security, 2004.

¹⁵⁸ Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), *Federal Response Plan*. Washington, DC: FEMA, 2000.

would be recognised and followed at each jurisdictional level. The intent was to develop a common method of training and practice that would allow the rapid mobilisation of a response system from different organisations and jurisdictions in disaster operations for a specific incident.

National Response Plan versus NIMS¹⁵⁹

The difference between the National Response Plan (NRP) and NIMS can be stated as follows: the NRP defines what needs to be done in a large-scale emergency event and the NIMS defines how to manage it. The NRP describes the structure and mechanisms for coordinating federal support during emergencies (or exercising direct federal authority).²⁴ It uses the framework of the NIMS to integrate federal government domestic prevention, protection, response, and recovery plans into a single operational plan for all hazards and all emergency response disciplines. The NRP describes operational procedures for federal support to state, local, and tribal emergency managers and defines situations in which federal authorities are to provide support and when federal authorities are to assume control. The NRP organizes capabilities, staffing, and equipment resources in terms of functions that are most likely to be needed during emergencies, such as communications or urban search and rescue, and spells out common processes and administrative requirements for executing the plan. The NRP consists of 5 components: the base plan, appendices, support annexes, emergency support annexes and incident annexes.

According to Comfort, Hurricane Katrina provided the first major test of national policies and procedures for disaster management since the establishment of the Department of Homeland Security.¹⁶⁰

Practice

Hurricane Katrina exposed many weaknesses regarding the procedures itself as well as the execution of the procedures. First, although he issued an order for an evacuation, Mayor Ray Nagin, did not follow the National Response Plan to use school buses to transport elderly and less resilient people out of the threatened area. Kathleen Blanco, the governor of Louisiana, was blamed for not deploying the Louisiana National Guard sooner.¹⁶¹ In fact she acted adequately by taking measures before the hurricane hit; among others, she asked for support from other states and for additional researches from the federal government. On the other hand, she did not declare a state of emergency. The critics on both the preparedness and the response of authorities were extensive; “The bureaucracy has murdered people in the greater New Orleans area”, said Aaron Broussard, president of Jefferson Parish. Similarly, Bill Owens, governor of Colorado, was of the opinion that “every one of those government levels could have done better”.¹⁶²

¹⁵⁹ United States, Congress, Select Bipartisan Committee to Investigate the Preparation for and Response to Hurricane Katrina and Davis, T., *A failure of initiative: Final report of the select bipartisan committee to investigate the preparation for and response to Hurricane Katrina*, US Government Printing Office. 2006. <http://katrina.house.gov>

¹⁶⁰ Comfort, L. K., Cities at Risk Hurricane Katrina and the Drowning of New Orleans, *Urban Affairs Review*, Vol. 41, Issue 4, 2006, 501-516.

¹⁶¹ United States. Congress. Select Bipartisan Committee to Investigate the Preparation for and Response to Hurricane Katrina and Davis, 2006.

¹⁶² Schneider, Sandra K., Administrative Breakdowns in the Governmental Response to Hurricane Katrina, *Public Administration Review*, Vol. 65, Issue 5, September/October 2005, pp. 515-516.

Research shows that there was a lack of preparedness among the citizens of Louisiana and in particular New Orleans, in the period before Hurricane Katrina. According to scholars, the government failed to inform the inhabitants of New Orleans sufficiently about the threat (perhaps as result of the underestimation of the threat by the authorities themselves).¹⁶³

The first response activities following Katrina began slowly; uncertainty and inconsistency were widespread. As the local government did not know what to do, the responses were delayed, which also delayed the request for additional forces and resources at the state and federal level.¹⁶⁴ Two days before the storm reached the coastline, Ray Nagin (the mayor of New Orleans) called for voluntary evacuation. One day later this message changed in the city's first ever whole-city mandatory evacuation order.¹⁶⁵ Due to the well working evacuations plans, more than 80% of the population succeeded fleeing out of the city before the storm reached land. However, some citizens did not manage to evacuate as were forced to stay in their houses. People, who were not able to evacuate, had the possibility to get support and shelter in the Louisiana Superdome, an American Football stadium. However, after some days the stadium, equipped to accommodate people for at most some hours, became a dirty place with a lot of problems. The electricity failed, the sewer also failed and the temperature within the closed stadium rose to more than thirty degrees Celsius.¹⁶⁶ "Last night was horrendous. I heard shouting, and drinks machines being smashed. There's no sanitation and it's so smelly. (...) The lights are broken in the loss which, as well as being disgusting, have become dangerous, so we now only go as a big group", one of the dismayed women described her situation on the fourth of seven days that she had to stay in the Superdome.¹⁶⁷ Others evacuated to hotels and other high-rise buildings.

Figure 4: Thousands of people tried to enter the Superdome

¹⁶³ Ibid.

¹⁶⁴ Schneider, 2005.

¹⁶⁵ Townsend, F., *The Federal Response to Hurricane Katrina Lessons Learned*, White House. 2006.

¹⁶⁶ United States. Congress. Select Bipartisan Committee to Investigate the Preparation for and Response to Hurricane Katrina and Davis, 2006.

¹⁶⁷ Experiences on a weblog of a survivor. <http://www.rockalily.com/blog/my-experience-in-the-superdome-during-hurricane-katrina.html>

About a week after the storm, on the 4th of September, the organised evacuation was initiated. Many citizens, some of them sitting and waiting on the roof of their houses to get saved by search and rescue teams, were ultimately evacuated by boats and helicopters. Initially, volunteers played an important role in the evacuation of those entrapped in the disaster area.

Days after Katrina hit New Orleans, the Pentagon sent five navy ships and eight maritime rescue teams to the affected region. The initial actions were overwhelmed by the dramatic conditions; the level of the water was too high, the circumstances too bad. The ships carried medical requirements, food, fuel and logistic materials to the area, and hovercrafts assisted in evacuating citizens; also a hospital ship was sent to care for the weak victims, especially older people. The population that stayed in New Orleans were the older people. The teams involved had a lot of trouble to arrange enough resources, including motorboats and helicopters to rescue those requiring assistance.¹⁶⁸

Statistics from the National Guard Bureau showed that approximately four thousand personnel from the Army and Air Force National Guard were sent to the affected area in Louisiana. The state of Mississippi had also mobilized approximately four thousand Army and Air Force Guard members to assist the involved teams in neighbour state Louisiana.

Explanations for the lack of governmental activity

The lack of activity by the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) can be explained by the shift in targets and objectives that this federal organisation made following the terrorist attacks of September 11, 2001. FEMA ‘shifted its focus away from natural disasters and toward the development of antiterrorism capabilities’.¹⁶⁹ After this structural change, whilst the organisation continued to distributing grants to state and local governments, about 75% of those grants were directed to counter-terrorism efforts instead of preparedness and response strategies in favour of mitigating the consequences of natural disasters.¹⁷⁰

The rescue coordination failed, because the power was out and there was a lack of sufficient information and communication services. Furthermore the radio equipment that did work was partly of a poor quality.¹⁷¹ So while communication is essential for a successful rescue procedure, the different actors who were concerned in the operation were unable to reach each other. In addition there was a lack of cooperation and collaboration between the search and rescue teams, and even when collaboration and cooperation was possible, the differences in priorities, experiences and abilities between local, regional and federal teams were enormous; they were looked at as they were foreigners.¹⁷²

The input from FEMA, who had sent more than ten teams to assist the local and regional teams with their search and rescue, were delayed to reach the area around New Orleans as a result of destroyed and overflowed roads which affected access: ‘It is not as simple as driving right up into the city of New Orleans and starting a rescue as we might be able to do in other disasters, such as an earthquake’, said a spokeswoman for the agency. The water in the streets

¹⁶⁸ United States. Congress. Select Bipartisan Committee to Investigate the Preparation for and Response to Hurricane Katrina and Davis, 2006.

¹⁶⁹ Schneider, 2005, p. 516.

¹⁷⁰ White, Josh & Peter Whoriskey, Planning, Response are Faulted, *Washington Post*, 2 September 2005.

¹⁷¹ Ibid.

¹⁷² Burns, Peter and Matthew O. Thomas, *The Failure of the Nonregime*, How Katrina Exposed New Orleans as a Regimeless City, *Urban Affairs Review*. Vol. 41, Issue 4, 2006, pp. 517-527.

and the difficulties for support teams to reach the affected areas can be considered as one of the most typical and complicated consequences of the specific disaster type ‘flood’.¹⁷³

Recovery

The economic, physical and psychological damage in and around New Orleans was extensive and ultimately incalculable. Besides the mortalities and injured victims, thousands of citizens lost family members, friends, their houses and other properties. In the hurricane-affected areas in Louisiana and Mississippi respectively 31% and 21% of the houses were damaged or, in a lot of cases, lost.¹⁷⁴ During Katrina and, less than a month later, following Hurricane Rita, the hospitals in the Gulf Coast area were tested and no less than 215 people died in these facilities.¹⁷⁵

Federal assistance was required to begin a National Health Service program for the Gulf coast region. The estimated amount of people in this region who needed mental health assistance was 500,000 residents and with an average cost of \$2,900 for the treating of a single person in Louisiana. In addition, local communities (not only within the affected states, but also beyond) need extra resources (particularly money) from both the federal government and the states. Rebuilding of the affected area involved more than the infrastructure of houses, roads and the defence measures of the coast zone, but also the mental and physical wellbeing of citizens.¹⁷⁶ Consequently, the healthcare system was an important aspect of recovery in the months and years following Katrina.

4.1.2 Lessons learned

One of the most important questions in the period after Katrina was why the government (local and federal) did not succeed in evacuating the majority of people out of the city. Different actors gave different explanations. Governor Haley Barbour (Mississippi) spoke about “hurricane fatigue”, whereby he meant that a lot of citizens would not evacuate because of the simple fact that they survived other storms or hurricanes in the past. Those experiences gave them the feeling that everybody was well prepared for a new crisis or disasters. Or: ‘Citizens who survive natural disasters in one season often fail to take actions that would mitigate their risk in future seasons.’¹⁷⁷ One of the hypotheses of Tinsley and Dillon is that people with near-miss information (highlighting how a disaster did not happen) will be less likely to take mitigating action for an impending hazard than people without this information. They verify this (and two other) hypothesis by thousand households from five affected areas, six months after Hurricane Lili, which hit the Louisiana coastline. (Interesting for this chapter is that those families were coming from the same region as the area that was affected by Katrina.)¹⁷⁸

¹⁷³ Schneider, 2005, p. 516.

¹⁷⁴ Almost 1.2 million homes damaged in 2005 hurricanes. Nation’s Building News. 19 June 2006. <http://www.nbnnews.com/NBN/issues/2006-06-19/Katrina+Recovery/2.html>

¹⁷⁵ Davis, R. and K. Johnson, Louisiana looks into 215 Katrina deaths, *USA Today*, 16 October 2005. http://www.usatoday.com/news/nation/2005-10-16-la-katrina-investigation_x.htm?csp-N009

¹⁷⁶ Weisler, Richard H., James G. Barbee and Mark H. Townsend, Mental Health and Recovery in the Gulf Coast After Hurricanes Katrina and Rita, *The Journal of the American Medical Association*, Vol.296, Issue 5, August 2006, pp. 585-588.

¹⁷⁷ Tinsley, Catherine H. and Robin L. Dillon, How Near-Miss Events Amplify or Attenuate Risky Decision Making, *Management Science*, Vol. 58, Issue 9, 2012, p. 1596.

¹⁷⁸ Tinsley and Dillon, 2012, pp. 1596 – 1613.

One of the conclusions is that people who are having near miss information are more willing to evacuate or take measures to mitigate the vulnerabilities of their properties than people who do not have that information. Otherwise the research found a significant difference between so called ‘vulnerable near misses’ and ‘resilient near misses’; people who know someone who had experience with problems caused by storm or flood vs. people who do not know those people. Those who know persons with experience with such a crisis, have less the willingness to take those preparation measures than those who do not know them.

Tracey E. Rizzuto and Laure K. Maloney, researchers from Louisiana, summarise five lessons learned for future situations following Hurricane Katrina.¹⁷⁹ Those lessons are mainly focussed on the preparation phase, one of the phases where many mistakes were made, due to the complicated organisational structures.

1) *Plan beyond the organisational boundaries.*

Though the planning of the internal operations can be good (and that was the case by the most of the organisations involved in the preparation for Katrina), other actors can frustrate your good efforts with inadequate planning. Only when the most people show self-sufficiency in the period before storm and flood, specific help and support organisations can focus on the groups that really need their help.

2) *Develop and exercise crisis contingencies.*

Different crisis management teams, like for crisis communication, decision-making and search and rescue, need to have a close collaboration. Firstly a common experience can strengthen the further the common approach; double efforts will be minimalized. Secondly, by training together (as a team), different actors will learn from each other. These exercises must be taken place periodically and during an evaluation the different team members must be confronted with possible improvements for the future.

3) *Embed leadership throughout the organisation.*

Good crisis response needs decision-making on different places within the organisation. As there is no time to waste when a disaster occurs, the distribution of power and influence between different actors enlarges the reaction time. That important knowledge for the response phase highlights the importance of allocating new responsibilities to existing roles. Employees have to get the opportunities to develop their (leadership) skills; if they have not, they won’t take responsibilities.

4) *Invest in employee-employer commitment.*

A lack of trust delays processes within an organisation, also in the preparation on and the response to crises or disasters. Trust is a key component for good communications, intra-organisational collaborations and decentralized decision-making.¹⁸⁰ It can create an atmosphere of solidarity and of doing a job together.

5) *Build a culture that can readily adapt to change.*

Of course, structures and formalized procedures are important to deal with the direct consequences of a crisis. But without the abilities to respond to new, unexpected and dynamic circumstances, it seems to be impossible to react on new situations. Like Edmondson, Bohmer and Pisano¹⁸¹ stress, leaders of organizations who promote dynamic and broad-minded attitudes, and who see crises more as opportunities instead as only as threats; they are more able to cope with such non-daily situations.

¹⁷⁹ Rizzuto and Maloney, 2008.

¹⁸⁰ Mishra, A., Organizational responses to crisis: The centrality of trust, *Roderick Kramer & Thomas Tyler (Eds.), Trust in organizations*, pp. 261-287, Newbury Park, CA: Sage, 1996.

¹⁸¹ Edmondson, A., R. Bohmer & G. Pisano, Disrupted routines: Team learning and new technology implementation in hospitals, *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Issue 46, 2001, pp. 685-716.

Regarding the lessons from above, it is important that organisations and individuals charged with the different phases of crisis management are able to adapt to new and evolving situations.

An important lesson for authorities is to take the threats of hurricanes seriously. Do not become overconfident. Experiences from the past are not always reliable predictions for future hurricanes. Inform citizens actively about the threat, even when the chance and its impact are highly uncertain. Information enables people to make choices on their own and hence stimulates self-reliant behaviour. Crucially, Katrina shows what happened when authorities omit to take action to prevent flooding. Prevention from water should be number one priority to cities that lay beneath sea level.

4.2 STORM XYNTHIA IN FRANCE (2010)

On the 28th of February 2010 the storm “Xynthia” hit the Atlantic coast of France. The storm caused major damage along the Iberian Peninsula, France, Germany and the Benelux countries. A total of 65 people were killed in Europe. Most of the fatalities, in total 47 of the casualties, were caused by the flood along the coasts of the Vendée and Charente Maritime in the western region of France. Most of the victims in France were counted in the villages of La-Faute-sur-Mer and L’Aiguillon-sur-Mer, where the direct consequences of the storm were highly visible: the water rose to 2.5 meters within half an hour. Authorities concluded that 79 people were injured, of which 7 seriously. Although many of those that were killed was a result of the flood, others died due to the effects of the storm including for instance, fallen trees.¹⁸²

The financial damage for both citizens and companies was enormous. Although it is extremely difficult to calculate exact figures, in the first days and weeks after the crisis, the French Senate presented a damage number of 2.5 billion euro’s. Examples of affected industries and sectors included the infrastructure for fisheries, agriculture, local government infrastructure and the tourist industry. For example, following the storm, French renters of yachts claimed millions of euros of damage restitution from their insurance organisations.¹⁸³

4.2.1 Standard operating procedures

As result of the thousands of kilometres of dikes and flood defences (approximately 10,000 to 13,000 kilometres), the prevention of areas for storms and floods and the mitigation of vulnerabilities is an important political question in France.¹⁸⁴ The reality shows that there is (and always has been) an enormous disintegration of responsibilities for the preservation and the qualities of the defences. According to scholars the management and maintenance of flood defences is the responsibility of the owner (of the agricultural plot) on which the structure is situated. However, no owner or manager is known for a large portion (hundreds of km) of these flood defences. The flood defence system also consists of structures and (rail) roads; for

¹⁸² Kolen, B., R. Slomp and S.N. Jonkman, The impacts of storm Xynthia February 27–28, 2010 in France: lessons for flood risk management, *Journal of Flood Risk Management*, Vol. 6, Issue 3, 2013, pp. 261-278.

¹⁸³ Ibid.

¹⁸⁴ Kolen, Bas, Robert Slomp, Wim van Balen, Teun Terpstra, Marcel Bottema and Stefan Nieuwenhuis. *Learning from French experiences with storm Xynthia. Damages after flood*, Ministerie van Verkeer en Waterstaat en HKV Consultants, 2010.

these, the legal status – related to flood protection – is not clear in all cases. Scholars arrived at the conclusion that there is a structural shortage of resources in France for management and maintenance including the lack of a proper management organisation.¹⁸⁵

Many different actors at different governmental levels are involved in the preparation and response to storms and floodings. Kolen et al. described the various policies that were into play during Xynthia.¹⁸⁶ In the administration layers, mayor (municipality), department prefect (SDIS) and zonal prefect (zonal headquarter) are responsible for crisis organisation in France. On top of this is the national level with Centre Opérationnel de Gestion Interministérielle des Crises (COGIC) led by the Ministry of Interior. Disaster prevention starts with French municipalities, which check the risks related to installations (industry, dams, etc.) and natural disasters (fire, avalanche, flood, etc.). If any risks are detected, municipalities have to formulate a Plan Particulier d'Intervention (PPI) for disasters involving installations and a Plan de Prévention de Risques Naturels (PPR) for natural disaster risks. Since 2004, a municipal contingency plan, Plan Communal de Sauvegarde is compulsory, in addition to a PPI or PPR, in case of external risks to improve preparation (Direction de la Défense et de la Sécurité Civiles, 2004).

Citizens are informed about the risks in their municipality in various registers, including the PPR and PPI. Mayors are obliged to place risk maps in public schools and public institutions. Small municipalities sometimes lack resources to provide more specific digital information. In addition, a recent interim report of a Senate Committee revealed that insufficient attention is paid to coastal floods in the PPRs and PPIs. The mayor is primarily responsible for the safety of persons and goods in his or her municipality. Based on an alarm from a prefect or otherwise, the mayor can retrieve real-time information about storm or flood threats using the flood alert maps (if available) and subsequently take measures and inform the public. Flood warnings by crisis organisations are based on forecasts made by hydrological/meteorological centres. A flood warning is a different warning than a warning for extreme weather conditions. In case of dangerous weather conditions (rain, wind and so on, but not a flood), the population and authorities are alerted through the 'Vigilance Météo' procedure by Météo-France (Ministère de l'Écologie, 2010a).

Practice

Immediately after the storm hit the regions of Vendée and Charente Maritime, volunteers from the French Red Cross mobilised. Neighbouring teams from Loire-Atlantique, Maine-et-Loire and Sarthe did assist, because the capacity in the affected areas was not sufficient to help all the victims and to preserve the dead bodies. First, they set up a shelter and took care of approximately one hundred people. One psychologist gave specific support to the victims who required assistance.¹⁸⁷

Volunteers were involved during different operations and activities. They were spread out over the region, and assisted in providing clothes, food, drinking water, medicines and hygiene kits. Furthermore they helped victims with more trivial (but at that moment not less important) things like cleaning their homes. Finally, they provide financial and psychological support; as for many people, the mental damage was larger than the physical damage. In

¹⁸⁵ Kolen, Slomp and Jonkman, 2013.

¹⁸⁶ Ibid.

¹⁸⁷ International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies, 2010.

<http://www.ifrc.org/en/nouvelles/nouvelles/europe/france/french-and-spanish-red-cross-respond-to-deadly-storm-xynthia/>

Spain, where Xynthia had the most impact in the province Guipúzcoa (Pays Basque) Red Cross volunteers participated in clearing and cleaning streets and sidewalks which were obstructed by fallen trees, in providing health services and the transportation of victims to hospitals, and in supporting firemen by helping putting out fires and to rescue people from damaged buildings.¹⁸⁸

Large numbers of volunteers and professional emergency workers were involved during the search and rescue operations in the first hours and days after Xynthia. In the area of Charente-Maritime and Vendée 3000 emergency workers were deployed (this amount includes the volunteers of for example the Red Cross, as described above). After a couple of days they get assistance from the army. The French Minister of Internal Affairs claimed that, in addition to specific emergency teams, 9,240 firemen were involved in the response efforts. They cleared the streets, put out fires and helped victims by rescuing them from their houses. They also helped with search efforts to check whether individuals had become trapped inside. In the area of Charente-Maritime there were 12,500 interventions in a one-week period, which equated to approximately one third of the number of interventions by emergency services in one year.

The majority of victims of Xynthia were occupants of a relatively elderly age. As the Vendée region is mainly a region where people enjoy their retirement, the share of elderly people in the total population was high. It may be no surprise that the majority of the fatalities were elderly.¹⁸⁹

The recovery of the infrastructure after Xynthia can be divided into three phases.¹⁹⁰

- Phase 1: In the first week after Xynthia, authorities and specialised teams worked hard to ensure that an additional flood would not hit the area on this scale again. There was a lot of repair work to do, not only on streets and buildings, but especially to improve the quality of the protecting infrastructure. The first recovery phase can be compared with first aid. The solutions made were not sufficient for the long term.
- Phase 2: The recovery measures in the second phase were more focused on safety for the future. Sea defences were restored, although on some places temporary solutions as cages with rocks were chosen above permanent walls.
- Phase 3: The phase of the permanent measures and of higher costs. The authorities of the region Charente-Maritime have estimate that the costs for a sufficient sea defence for the region will be around 200 million euro's. The national authorities estimated the total costs for a new coastal defence plan in all the vulnerable regions on 500 million dollars in six years (see below).

The national French floods management plan, presented by the French Minister for Environment and Sustainable Development and described by the PPRD¹⁹¹ is organised around four pillars, which are both focused on the infrastructure and on the awareness among citizens.

¹⁸⁸ Kolen, Slomp, Van Balen, Terpstra, Bottema and Nieuwenhuis, 2010.

¹⁸⁹ Xynthia related disaster at La Faute sur Mer (Vendée, France), A geopolitically and culturally driven disaster, challenging local management. Storm Surges Congress, Hamburg, 13- 17 September 2010. http://www.loicz.org/imperia/md/content/loicz/stormsurges/sessiong/7_pigeon.pdf

¹⁹⁰ Streeter, Michael, *Xynthia Storm One Year Later*, Coastal Care, 2011. <http://coastalcare.org/2011/03/storm-xynthia-a-year-later/>

¹⁹¹ PPRD (Prevention, preparedness response to natural and man-made disasters) South Programme, 2011. <http://www.preventionweb.net/english/professional/contacts/v.php?id=6147>

- *Proper urban development in high flood risk prone areas.*
Through restrictions for building in areas with a more than an average flood risk and an all-embracing plan for the design and implementation of prevention works, the authorities try to optimise the qualities of the coastal defence and minimise the danger for the future. Furthermore the different coastal municipalities and cities had to prepare their own prevention plans.
- *Improve floods forecasting, monitoring and early warning systems*
The actor involved in this pillar of the management plan is the French meteorological institute. With a special forecasting service, on the basis of sea and waves forecasts and the implementation of a system with the emergency colours green, orange and red citizens can be informed better about the risks in their region. Also the monitoring of the water level in the different rivers has to be improved.
- *Dam system reinforcements.*
In the period between 2011 and 2016, 1200 kilometre of dams at the coastline will be checked and improved. The same applies for the hydraulic works safety control services.
- *Development of a risk management culture at all levels.*
All the municipal emergency plans had to include a specific chapter with a focus on the prevention for storms and floods and their possible consequences. Furthermore there is a moral commitment for the authorities to create awareness among the population, and show examples where they can arrange to mitigate the associated vulnerabilities.

4.2.2 Lessons learned

As we saw in the case of Katrina and Xynthia, flood risk can be mitigated by reducing the likelihood of occurrence and by reducing the consequences and the impact. Better prevention, planning and disaster relief can mitigate the vulnerabilities of a specific area. Regarding the impact of Xynthia, experts from The Netherlands¹⁹² have formulated eight lessons for the future.¹⁹³ Although these lessons may have different value and utility for different countries, and it is always important to consider the special characteristics of each country, aspects are useful on the most places in the Western world.

- However even the best measures cannot guarantee that a disaster like a flood will not occur anymore, protection/prevention is essential to reduce the risks. Prevention is better than cure. Prevention measures can be expensive, but the material and immaterial damage plus the high number of people killed will trivialize those costs.
- Floods have to become well known risks. When warnings are not understandable for experts, they certain won't for laymen within the population. Then it is impossible and unrealistic to expect them to make the right preparations. The warnings in France were much too technical, and as a result of that the reactions were inadequate. Furthermore people were warned for a storm, not for a flood. (It should be noted that it is much easier to warn for a storm than for a possible flood and its consequences, since storms can be more easily predicted than the chance of a dike breach).

¹⁹² Due to the impact of high water for The Netherlands, Dutch scholars did extensive research to the response in France to the storm and flood of Xynthia. This study was more comprehensive than some studies out of France, because of that partners choose to use this Dutch study for this report.

¹⁹³ Kolen, Slomp, Van Balen, Terpstra, Bottema and Nieuwenhuis, 2010.

- It is important to place responsibility for flood defences on one central point. Fragmentation of the prevention management results often in discussions between actors involved and a lack of sustainability of the options chosen. In France, as Kolen et al. described, was ‘the funding for repairs and maintenance of flood defences very fragmented’.
- The introductions of risk zones, which have to be based on a few criteria and a set of possible floods, can help in reducing the vulnerabilities. Only when the applied rules are maintained, risk zones can be useful.
- The resilience of citizens is a decisive factor for the level in which the impact of a storm or flood can be minimalised. It is important to have an insight in the measures citizens take during different kind of crises.
- When a flood threatens, it is important to consider that not only one or a few points in the coastal defence will collapse. It is difficult to predict which locations dikes or other measures will fail and that makes it harder to be sufficiently prepared for a disaster such as Xynthia in France or Katrina in the US. Designers of contingency plans and disaster relief efforts should keep these characteristics of floods in mind, before they draft their plans.
- Only by having information about risks (based on change and effect) and possible consequences, is it possible to make decisions about disaster management. Different scenarios have to be reviewed before taking comprehensive and drastic measures, which may have an impact on a large part of the society. It should be acknowledged that ‘(1) there is always a lot of uncertainty, (2) the available information probably does not provide an accurate representation and (3) the implementation of measures is always a complex matter.’¹⁹⁴
- Models for prevention and planning cannot predict everything. Like every disaster (and maybe more than some other specific types of disasters) storms differ, in their magnitude, in their consequences and in their impact on a society. The lesson of Xynthia was that not only extreme wind speeds have to be considered, but also that the characteristics of the weather depressions can explain the condition and qualities of the coastal defence measures.

Preventing floods from happening is by far the most effective and efficient strategy in flood management. Xynthia shows that a fragmentary system of responsibilities for the maintenance and management of flood prevention measures is inapt and leads to vulnerabilities within crisis response. Therefore, one actor should be made responsible for flood management. In addition, communication about the threat should be timeless, explicit and simple. Particular attention should be devoted to the most vulnerable citizens (such as the elderly) in the possible affected areas. These groups should be provided with specific recommendations in order to stimulate and enhance self-resilience.

4.3 CONCLUSION

In this paragraph we summarise the similarities and differences between the two case studies. The storms Katrina and Xynthia and the subsequent floods occurred in different countries, with different political and governing systems and different structures. Furthermore the characteristics of the affected area are hardly comparable. However, there are clear

¹⁹⁴ Ibid.

similarities, which can help explain how response to and recovery from the disasters were formed. Below we describe three differences and three similarities.

Difference 1: The majority of the affected population in the Gulf Coast, living in the states Louisiana and Mississippi was relatively poor and from African-American origin (67% of the population of New Orleans, before the Hurricane and 60% after it).¹⁹⁵ The importance of these characteristics on the vulnerabilities of the citizens is that they were less prepared on storms and floods and that the quality of their houses was often insufficient to obstruct wind and water. On the other hand, the population in France was relatively white, rich, but also elderly. A lot of people moved to the Atlantic coast to enjoy their retirement. As a result of their age and their lack of willingness to evacuate, this group was particularly vulnerable to the effects of the storm and the flood.

Difference 2: The magnitude of damage and the number of fatalities and victims between Katrina and Xynthia differ. Those differences challenge the organisations affected in different ways. Although as result of the deficient preparation phase Xynthia meant a serious task for authorities, volunteers and other actors, the response and recovery phases after Katrina were much more comprehensive.

Difference 3: Where the failures in France concern mainly the preparation phase, victims were well cared for by support teams like the Red Cross. The response phase developed relative well. How different was the situation during and after Katrina? Lot of citizens did not get the help and support they needed, a lack of medicines, drinking water and other essential resources became visible and because of the disorder the city resulted in some situations of disorder.

There are also some similarities between Katrina and Xynthia:

Similarity 1: As we saw at the first described difference, both the inhabitants in the Golf Coast as the population at the Atlantic coast were vulnerable. The relatively high number of fatalities (although the number of victims during Katrina was much larger than during Xynthia) can among others be attributed to these characteristics. Authorities and search and rescue teams have to pay attention to the properties of an area or the demographics of the population before plans are made or actions are taken.

Similarity 2: Both in France and the United States, the preparation of the authorities for storms and floods of this magnitude was insufficient. Warnings were ignored, contingency plans were lacking. Consequently, citizens did not adequately prepare themselves. The survey in the United States demonstrates that even after Katrina, a large number of citizens said they did not think it was necessary or useful to prepare. So the resilience of the populations was not stimulated and consequently low.

Similarity 3: In the response phase a combination of authority measures and the willingness of volunteers is visible. The Red Cross is an important organisation in the first hours after a flood, but without coordination from the federal or state (in the case of France: region) authorities an affected area cannot be recovered and rebuilt. As organisations such as the Red Cross have the abilities to improvise and anticipate new situations, they are the right actors to

¹⁹⁵ Associated Press, *New Orleans Since Katrina: Before and After*, 27 August 2012. http://www.huffingtonpost.com/2012/08/27/new-orleans-since-katrina_n_1834696.html

use in the response phase. Governments and other authorities have a main role during the phases before and after disasters.

The examination of floods and storm in this chapter provide useful findings for the COSMIC project in that it becomes increasingly evident that that communication between governments and its citizens is of vital importance for the effectiveness of the overall response. When citizens are sufficiently informed about the threat, then they are able to take preparatory action and hence enhance their self-resilience. In addition, communication is also vital for gaining insight into the activities that individuals and voluntary groups take during and in the aftermath of storms and flooding. When these activities are likely to be effective, they can be supported by working together or stimulated by providing resources.

5 EXTREME TEMPERATURES

In this chapter we focus on two case studies concerning extreme temperatures. These include the 2003 European heatwave, focusing primarily on the country that suffered the most, France, and the 2006 North America heatwave, focusing mainly on the state of California, which was, at the time, affected the most. The two case studies were selected by partners to examine the need for local, inter-neighbourhood measures to be implemented in order to facilitate the assessment of vulnerable groups to extreme temperatures. The chapter will present some contextual information about each case study, analyse search and rescue operations that were performed during the time of the crisis and explore if any valuable lessons were learned after the occurrence of the heatwaves.

Even though many definitions of a heatwave exist¹⁹⁶, a heatwave is widely accepted to be a long period of continuous high temperatures usually accompanied by high humidity. Usually, a “long period” is defined by each country independently, for example in Denmark, the Danish Meteorological Institute defines a heatwave as a period of at least three consecutive days of which the average maximum temperature across more than fifty percent of the country exceeds 25 °C.¹⁹⁷ In Sweden on the other hand this period extends to at least five days with a daily maximum exceeding 25 °C.¹⁹⁸

Depending on their severity, heatwaves may have extensive social, economic and environmental effects in sectors such as public health, transportation, agriculture, and energy.¹⁹⁹ For example, this type of crises can lead to human losses, increased air pollution due to warmer air and higher energy costs from, for instance the use of air conditioning. Heatwaves are also known to have a deadlier effect in urban areas rather rural because of the so called urban heat island effect.²⁰⁰ This phenomenon refers to the fact that cities have a higher mean air temperature than their surroundings. It has been estimated that a city of one million people or more can be 1–3°C warmer than its surroundings. During the evening, the difference can be as high as 12°C.²⁰¹ The main causes of the phenomenon are associated with cities, “because their surfaces are characterized by low albedo, high impermeability and favourable thermal properties for the energy storage and heat release. Besides, many cities present narrow urban canyons with reduced sky view factors that tend to absorb and reemit the radiated energy from their surfaces”.²⁰²

5.1 FRANCE (2003)

The summer of 2003 was the warmest in Europe in recorded history. As shown in the figure below, central Europe, particularly France was affected by the unprecedented heatwave. The

¹⁹⁶ Meehl, George A. and Claudia Tebaldi, "More Intense, More Frequent, and Longer Lasting Heatwaves in the 21st Century". *Science*, Vol. 305 (5686), 2004, p. 994. Bibcode: <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2004Sci...305..994M>. doi:10.1126/science.1098704. PMID 15310900.

¹⁹⁷ Danish Meteorological Institute, "Danmark får varme- og hedeølge", 2008.

¹⁹⁸ Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute, "Värmeölja | Klimat | Kunskapsbanken | SMHI" (in Swedish). Smhi.se, 2013.

¹⁹⁹ David Myers, “Social and Environmental Effects of Urban Heat Islands”, Suite101.com. 2013. <http://suite101.com/article/social-and-environmental-effects-of-urban-heat-islands-a231573>

²⁰⁰ Ibid.

²⁰¹ United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), “Heat Island Effect | U.S. EPA”, 2013, <http://www.epa.gov/hiri/>

²⁰² Urbanheatislands.com, “Heat Island Types”, 2010. <http://www.urbanheatislands.com/heat-island-types>

figure (below) depicts the difference in land surface temperature, which is calculated by subtracting the average of all cloud free data during 2000, 2001, 2002 and 2004 from those measured in 2003, covering the date range of July 20 – August 20.²⁰³ The geographic regions which are shown in deep red were 10 degrees Celsius hotter in the summer of 2003 compared to other years.²⁰⁴

Figure 5: Visualization displaying land surface temperature data.²⁰⁵

France, as was previously mentioned, suffered the most during the heatwave with estimated deaths of 14,947 for the period of August 4 to August 18.²⁰⁶ Almost 80% of the people that died were over the age of 75 and almost 65% of them were women.²⁰⁷

The large number of deaths can mainly be attributed to the following factors:

- As the heatwave occurred during the month of August, when many citizens were on holidays, leaving most of the elderly alone at home.²⁰⁸
- France usually has mild summers without any major deviations in the mean high and low temperatures and certainly not for a period longer than three days. This means that both the government and the citizens did not feel the need to prepare and did not know

²⁰³ Blue Marble Research | Scientific Computation, Data Analysis and Visualization, “The European Heatwave of 2003 as seen from MODIS”, 2006. <http://bluemarble.ch/wordpress/2006/11/27/the-european-heat-wave-of-2003-as-seen-from-modis/>

²⁰⁴ Ibid.

²⁰⁵ Image by Reto Stöckli, Robert Simmon and David Herring, NASA Earth Observatory, based on data from the MODIS land team.

²⁰⁶ Assemblée Nationale, “Rapport de la commission d’enquête sur les conséquences sanitaires et sociales de la canicule”. No. 1455, tomes 1 & 2, 2004. <http://www.assemblee-nat.fr>

²⁰⁷ Fouillet, A. et al., “Excess mortality related to the August 2003 heatwave in France”, *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*, Vol. 80, Issue 1, 2010, pp 16-24.

²⁰⁸ Fraser, Matthew, “Holidays and Heatwaves: Ten Years After France”, 2013. <http://matthewfraserauthor.com/france/holidays-and-heat-waves-ten-years-after-frances-deadly-canicule-of-2003/>

how to deal with the upcoming phenomenon. No warnings were issued and no advice was communicated to citizens as to how to avoid dehydration and overheating, symptoms which most often lead to heat strokes. Some of the Parisians did not even have air conditioning units operating at their homes.²⁰⁹

The impacts of the heatwave on various sectors are summarised below:

Environment

The effects of the heatwave on the environment could mostly be observed via the wildfires that occurred in that same period. Vegetation during a heatwaves becomes highly flammable and during the 2003 heatwave a record-breaking incidence of spatially extensive wildfires was observed in European countries.²¹⁰

Agriculture

“In France, compared to 2002, the maize grain crop was reduced by 30% and fruit harvests declined by 25%. Winter crops (wheat) had nearly achieved maturity by the time of the heatwave and therefore suffered less yield reduction (21%) than summer crops. Forage production was reduced on average by 30% in France and hay and silage stocks for winter were partly used during the summer”²¹¹. Also, later studies showed that “the heatwave that struck Europe two years ago caused the biggest fall in agricultural output for 100 years”²¹².

Industry, settlement and society

The extremely high and consecutive temperatures that were observed during the heatwave caused stress on the nation’s economy, most noticeably on health, water supplies, food storage and energy systems. Electricity became scarce, construction productivity fell, and the cold storage systems of 25-30% of all food-related establishments were found to be inadequate. The punctuality of the French railways fell to 77%, from 87% a year before and €1 to €3 million were paid in additional compensation payments, an increase of 7-20% compared to the year before. Sales of clothing dropped by 8.9% lower than usual in August. Sales of bottled water on the other hand increased by 18%, and of ice-cream by 14%. Tourists were also found to be more in northern France but fewer in the south²¹³.

5.1.1 Standard operating procedures

Prior to the 2003 heatwave, no standard operating procedures were actually in effect, mostly because heatwaves were not considered to be of such high importance. Due to the 2003 European heatwaves, countries decided to adopt preventative actions for vulnerable

²⁰⁹ Ponds for Peace, "European Heatwave Kills More Than 70,000 « PONDS for PEACE.", 2013. <http://pondsforpeace.org/european-heat-wave-kills-more-than-70000/>

²¹⁰ Parry, M.L., O.F. Canziani, J.P. Palutikof, P.J. van der Linden and C.E. Hanson, “Cross-chapter case study”, *Climate Change 2007: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, pp. 843-868.

²¹¹ Ibid.

²¹² The Telegraph, Heatwave of 2003 caused worst crop slump for 100 years, 2005. <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/worldnews/europe/france/1498964/Heatwave-of-2003-caused-worst-crop-slump-for-100-years.html>

²¹³ Parry, M.L., O.F. Canziani, J.P. Palutikof, P.J. van der Linden and C.E. Hanson, “Cross-chapter case study”, *Climate Change 2007: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, pp. 843-868.

population groups, which led to the development of heat health-watch warning systems in several European countries including France.^{214,215}

Almost a year after the heatwave, the Mayor of Paris informed 400,000 Parisians, who were either elderly or severely handicapped, of a plan to target and protect the social groups who were the most vulnerable against a heatwave. He urged them to register with the Social Services Agency and benefit from direct phone contact and offers of special assistance in the event of another heatwave.²¹⁶ Two years later, about 13,000 people, mostly of them being 65 years and over, had registered.²¹⁷

On July 17th 2006, a heatwave warning was issued by the National Weather Institute and the plan was activated. In the next 11 days, all residents who had registered got a checkup call from the Social Services Agency and should they needed any assistance, a physician was sent to evaluate them and determine their health status. Almost 800 elderly people were evaluated during that period and 200 of them were called back because they were thought to be in a high risk. Also, about 30 people were transported to air-conditioned adult day centres and 18 benefited from urgent medical attention.

It is difficult to say whether the lower number of excess deaths during the 2006 heatwave was a result of the city's preparedness plan since the heatwave's characteristics differed substantially to the ones of the 2003 heatwave. Its duration and severity were lower but nevertheless, it is accurate to assume that at some level, the plan did manage to provide some kind of social network to the more isolated older people, who would have been otherwise in great risk of losing their lives. Based on a synthesis of studies about the 2003 heatwave, this is precisely what must be done.²¹⁸

France's national heatwave plan now has the following four levels.²¹⁹ The ministry of Social Affairs and Health ensures that the measures mentioned in those levels are implemented accordingly. The Ministry also ensures daily alerts are disseminated to the public of the risks of occurrence of extreme temperatures (*note, it is not clear "how" information is communicated to the public*).

Level 1 - seasonal surveillance

Seasonal surveillance, while on Level 1, is a green colour on the map of weather vigilance. This level is automatically activated from June 1 to August 31 of each year. In case of early or late heat, seasonal surveillance can be activated before June 1 or extended after August 31. During this summer period measures that are usually taken include the following:

- verification of operational systems,
- establishment of a meteorological and health monitoring device and
- activating the national emergency platform phone number.

²¹⁴ Ibid.

²¹⁵ Matthies, F. et al., "Guidance Heat-health action plans", 2008. http://www.euro.who.int/_data/assets/pdf_file/0006/95919/E91347.pdf

²¹⁶ Cadot, Emmanuelle, Victor G. Rodwin and Alfred Spira, "In the Heat of the Summer.", *J Urban Health*, Vol. 84, no. 4, 2007, pp. 466-468, doi:10.1007/s11524-007-9161-y

²¹⁷ Ibid.

²¹⁸ Ibid.

²¹⁹ Les niveaux d'alerte du Plan national canicule - Ministère des Affaires sociales et de la Santé - www.sante.gouv.fr, "Les niveaux d'alerte du Plan national canicule - Ministère des Affaires sociales et de la Santé", 2013. <http://www.sante.gouv.fr/les-niveaux-d-alerte-du-plan-national-canicule.html>

Level 2 - heat warning

Level 2 is actually a preparatory level for possible transition to Level 3. Different services are on standby and preparing for a heatwave alert while at the same time local communication activities are targeted to inform the public of a possible heatwave, especially during weekends and holidays.

Level 3 - heat alert

Based on the map of weather vigilance Météo-France (orange alert), the prefects of departments may trigger Level 3 - heatwave alert. The decision to trigger Level 3 - heatwave alert takes into account, where applicable, the local situation (level of pollution, population-factors such as large gatherings and others) and health indicators in line with the Regional Health Agencies (ARS). Once on Level 3, the heatwave National Heatwave Plan alert is activated, and the prefects of each individual department shall take all appropriate measures within the framework of the management plan of a Departmental Heatwave (GCD).²²⁰

While on level 3, all regional actors are informed of the intensity and duration of the phenomenon and all other relevant information that they should be aware of. Communication is enhanced between national bodies and all individuals who might be affected by the imminent crisis reminding them to take preventative actions against it such as staying hydrated by drinking a lot of fluids and taking shelter from the heat. Plans to welcome the elderly or disabled are also set in motion raising the permanence of ambulatory care facilities, Nursing Services At Home (SSIAD) and Services to Help and Support for Home (SAAD). Activation by the mayors of municipal registers with assistance to seniors and disabled and also measures for the homeless are implemented.

Level 4 - Maximum mobilization

On Level 4 - Maximum mobilization, which is a red weather alert, is activated by the Ministry. This level corresponds to a heatwave proved to be exceptional, very intense and durable, with the appearance of side effects in various sectors (drought, drinking water saturation hospitals or funeral, blackout, forest fires). This requires the implementation of special measures. If the crisis becomes intersectional, it requires maximum mobilization and coordination of the response of the state with the activation of the Interministerial Crisis Cell (CIC), which includes all departments²²¹.

5.1.2 Lessons learned

There were various lessons learned from the 2003 heatwave in France deriving from reports and literature that examined the European heatwave of 2003. They are summarised below:^{222, 223}

- Perhaps the most important lesson of the Paris heatwave is to promote inter-neighbourhood communication. Individuals within a neighbourhood should organize themselves and ensure that other members of their small community are aware of the dangers that a heatwave might produce. Therefore, the essential components of the heatwave preparedness plan should focus on individual risk factors, e.g., encouraging

²²⁰ Ibid.

²²¹ Ibid.

²²² Lagadec, P., "Understanding the French 2003 heatwave experience: Beyond the heat, a multi-layered challenge", *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis management*, Vol. 12, 2004, pp. 160–169.

²²³ Cadot, Emmanuelle, Victor G. Rodwin and Alfred Spira, "In the Heat of the Summer.", *J Urban Health*, Vol. 84, no. 4, 2007, pp. 466-468, doi:10.1007/s11524-007-9161-y

- older persons to drink more, offering special services to those who perceived themselves to be in need of assistance, and increasing medical surveillance of these individuals. In the future, more attention should focus on targeting some of the neighbourhoods that suffered disproportionate excess mortality.
- Heatwaves are not given enough attention but they “claim more lives each year than floods, tornadoes, and hurricanes combined. Heatwaves are a silent killer, mostly affecting the elderly, the very young, or the chronically ill.”²²⁴
 - Lack of communication between responsible bodies and individuals led to misinterpretations and miscalculations of the phenomenon by the latter.
 - National bodies and services should be able to detect even the faintest signal of a heatwave. Even weak signals should not be ignored and continuous monitoring of such a case should be ensured. It is the case when fear is too high, even strong signals are dismissed. “Before the events or in elegant presentations most officials would deny that observation, and praise their emergency response capacity; but, unfortunately, reality show that, during crises, lack of effective preparation drives to very strange, deaf and dumb behaviours”²²⁵.
 - National bodies should not lose focus of where the actual attention needs to be provided. Citizens flooding the hospitals should of course be taken care of but during critical conditions such as the ones occurring during a heatwave can often be misleading and influence people in charge into thinking that they have prevented a disaster; but in doing so the system fail to understand that those who reach the hospitals are the ones who survived, many others are probably dying at home.
 - Air conditioning units should be installed in all residences especially the ones that provide shelter to the elderly. “Installation of air conditioning systems in French homes could have saved lives of the 15,000 elderly people who perished in the August heatwave of 2003”.²²⁶

Until 2003, heatwaves were not considered to be a real threat in France and people, as well as government officials, did not think that any special measures should be taken in case such a phenomenon occurred. The French heatwave of 2003 highlighted the importance of a neighbourhood approach to response measures and actions. Most of the deaths occurring because of the heatwave can be attributed to lack of preparedness for such a disaster and lack of communication between the national bodies and the citizens but also between individuals themselves. Several homes did not have air conditioning units and that also contributed to the high number of deaths.

5.2 NORTH AMERICA (2006)

In the summer of 2006, North America was hit by a heatwave which lasted from July 15th to August 27th. The heatwaves’ course began in the centre of North America and the Midwest on July 15th, then moved to West Coast by July 21st before returning to central USA on July 28th.

²²⁴ Earth Policy Institute, “Plan B Updates - 29: Record Heatwave in Europe Takes 35,000 Lives - Far Greater Losses May Lie Ahead”, 2003. http://www.earth-policy.org/plan_b_updates/2003/update29

²²⁵ Ibid.

²²⁶ Fraser, Matthew, “Holidays and Heatwaves: Ten Years After France’s Deadly “Canicule” of 2003”, 2013. <http://matthewfraserauthor.com/france/holidays-and-heat-waves-ten-years-after-frances-deadly-canicule-of-2003/>

By August 4th the heatwave had reached the East Coast before moving to the South and Southeast United States on the 27th of August.^{227, 228}

The heatwave covered the biggest part of the USA and Canada, mainly Nevada and California, which had six consecutive days of 110 degree-plus Fahrenheit (43 °C) temperatures raising the average daily maximum temperature significantly. As seen in the figure below.

Figure 6: Average Daily Maximum Temperature in California during the 2006 heatwave and number of deaths related to heat by County.²²⁹

The heatwave brought a shortage of rainfall with, according to the National Ocean Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), “51 percent of the United States, mostly in the Plains states and southeast, was in moderate-to-extreme drought. This percentage ranks with the biggest droughts of the last 50 years”.²³⁰

A death toll of approximately 147 individuals, caused by high temperatures, was reported by the county’s coroners soon after the California heatwave. This figure however may have been underreported due to “a lack of a clear case definition and the multifactorial nature of heat-related mortality”.²³¹ The figure (above) depicts the official number of deaths related to heat by each California County. Apart for the aforementioned deaths, 16,166 excess visits to emergency doctors and 1,182 excess hospitalisations were recorded while the elderly, the sick

²²⁷ Richardson, Gabi, “2006 North American Heatwave”, prezi.com, 2013. <http://prezi.com/j34vysmicw-b/2006-north-american-heat-wave/>

²²⁸ Maureen K. Fleury, “North America Heatwave 2006”, suite101.com, 2013. <http://suite101.com/article/north-america-heat-wave-2006-a73990>

²²⁹ Department of Public Health, “Maps of Temperature and Related Factors in California”, 2012. http://www.ehib.org/page.jsp?page_key=174

²³⁰ National Ocean Atmospheric Administration, “NCDC: Climate of 2006 July”, 2006. <http://www.ncdc.noaa.gov/oa/climate/research/2006/jul/jul06.html>

²³¹ Ostro, B. D., L. A. Roth, R. S. Green, and R. Basu, “Estimating the mortality effect of the July 2006 California heatwave”. *Environ. Res.*, Vol. 109, 2009, pp. 614–619.

and the poor were found to be the groups that were at a greater risk during the heatwave.²³²,²³³,²³⁴ Moreover, isolated individuals were also at risk since “a lot of people don't realize when they're in the middle of a heatstroke, and they don't have anyone around to recognize that they're ill”.²³⁵

Effects of the 2006 heatwave were noticeable in various sectors, including:

Energy

The continuous use of air conditioning units and fans imposed a greater strain on the power grid and while temperatures soared, power transformers were damaged and the worst blackouts were experienced in Southern California.²³⁶ Discounts were being offered to businesses that curtail usage and Governor Arnold Schwarzenegger ordered state buildings to raise thermostats on air conditioning to preserve power.²³⁷

Environment

As it is the usual case with heatwaves, the high temperatures and dry conditions caused an outbreak of wildfires in the Rockies and the West Coast. Surprisingly though, despite the extensive damage by fire, it did not break the record which was set in 2002.²³⁸

Agriculture

California is the nation's leading milk producer and its multibillion-dollar agriculture was threatened by the heatwave at such a level that regulators had to allow dairy farmers to bury their dead animals on their own land instead of bringing them to special facilities for livestock carcasses which were heavily overloaded. In some areas, farmers were reporting mortality rates twice as high as normal. As identified by California Diaries, the state's largest milk cooperative, roughly 16,500 cows, 1 percent of the state's dairy herd, died from the heat. Moreover, according to the trade groups and dairy farmers in the region, the cows that did survive during that same period yielded 10 percent to 20 percent less milk than usual.

California, and state Farm Bureau Federation spokeswoman Ann Schmidt-Fogarty said production had fallen by 15 to 20 percent. She said that the peach crop would be the worst in 20 years and that cotton, pistachios, walnuts, avocados, plums and nectarines would also be affected.²³⁹

²³² Knowlton, K., M. Rotkin-Ellman, G. King, H. G. Margolis, D. Smith, G. Solomon, R. Trent, and P. English, “The 2006 California heatwave: Impacts on hospitalizations and emergency department visits”, *Environ. Health Perspect*, Vol. 117., 2009, pp. 61–67.

²³³ Basu, R., W. Y. Feng, and B. Ostro, “Characterizing temperature and mortality in nine California counties, 1999–2003”. *Epidemiol.* Vol. 19, 2008, pp. 138–145.

²³⁴ Paul English, “Epidemiology of Heat”, CA Dept of Public Health, 2013. http://ral.ucar.edu/csap/events/climatehealth/2013/docs/paul_english.pdf

²³⁵ Demian Bulwa and Matthai Chakko Kuruvila, “KILLER HEAT / At least 41 deaths blamed on high temperatures -- isolated, lower-income elderly are most at risk”, SFGate.com, 2006. <http://www.sfgate.com/news/article/KILLER-HEAT-At-least-41-deaths-blamed-on-high-2492222.php>

²³⁶ Maureen K. Fleury. “North America Heatwave 2006”, suite101.com, 2013. <http://suite101.com/article/north-america-heat-wave-2006-a73990>

²³⁷ USA Today, “Prolonged heatwave straining California power grid”, 2006. http://usatoday30.usatoday.com/weather/news/2006-07-24-heat-wave_x.htm

²³⁸ Maureen K. Fleury. “North America Heatwave 2006”, suite101.com, 2013. <http://suite101.com/article/north-america-heat-wave-2006-a73990>

²³⁹ John Pomfret, “130 Deaths Blamed on California Heatwave”, Washington Post, 2006. <http://www.washingtonpost.com/wp-dyn/content/article/2006/07/28/AR2006072801648.html>

5.2.1 Standard operating procedures

In an excessive heat emergency, as in all other disaster response in California, statewide coordination of resource support to local government is carried out through the Standardized Emergency Management System (SEMS). SEMS incorporates the use of the Incident Command System (ICS), California Disaster and Civil Defense Master Mutual Aid Agreement (MMAA), the Operational Area (OA) concept and multiagency or inter-agency coordination. SEMS is required to manage all responses to emergencies in California, unify all elements of emergency response into one and standardizes key elements.²⁴⁰

The state of California has composed a contingency plan for excessive heat emergencies which complements the State's main Emergency Plan.²⁴¹ This plan outlines the actions, shown in Table 55, the State of California will take in support of local government when an extreme temperature event is anticipated or has occurred. This plan also provides preparedness guidelines for all organisations in the preparation of their heat emergency response plans and other related activities.

²⁴⁰ Governor's Office of Emergency Services, "Standardized Emergency Management System", State of California, 2011. <http://www.calema.ca.gov/planningandpreparedness/pages/standardized-emergency-management-system.aspx>

²⁴¹ California Governor's Office of Emergency Services, "Heat", 2010. <http://www.calema.ca.gov/planningandpreparedness/pages/heat.aspx>

Table 5: Actions taken by the State of California’s various agencies during an extreme temperature event.

Department/ Agency	Responsibility
California State Warning Center (CSWC) (Cal EMA)	Statewide emergency notification
California Emergency Management Agency (Cal EMA)	Emergency management – all SEMS/NIMS functions – recovery programs
Cal EMA Law Enforcement Branch	Law enforcement / coroner operations
California Department of Aging (CDA)	Provide communication and assistance to senior and caregivers services
Business, Transportation & Housing Agency (BT&H)	Loan guarantees for farm & agriculture related enterprises
California National Guard (CNG)	Logistical support – armories
Community Services & Development (CSD)	Community Service Block Grants (CSBG), Low Income Home Energy Assistance Program (LIHEAP) – migrant programs
Department of Developmental Services (DDS)	Provide communication and assistance to Regional Centers and Developmental Centers who provide direct services and assistance to people with developmental disabilities; Advise Cal EMA on the needs of people with developmental disabilities
Department of Food and Agriculture (CDFA)	Agricultural livestock - pet issues - fairground facilities - link to agricultural commissioners & growers
Department of Health Care Services (DHCS)	Medi-Cal
Department of Public Health (CDPH)	Public health programs
Department of Housing & Community Development (HCD)	Housing programs
Department of Mental Health (DMH)	Crisis Counseling Immediate Services, Crisis Counseling Regular Program
Department of Rehabilitation (DOR)	Provide communication and assistance to the disability community
Department of Social Services (DSS)	CalWORKs cash aid (including immediate need), food stamp benefits (including expedited service and/or disaster food stamp benefits), food commodities programs, and coordination of state resource in support of local government. Oversight of community facilities responsible for the health and safety of vulnerable populations, and ARC shelters.
Department of Transportation (CalTrans)	Transportation – public works
Emergency Medical Services Authority (EMSA)	Emergency medical care
Employment Development Department (EDD)/ Workforce & Labor Development Agency	Unemployment insurance, disaster unemployment assistance, job training services
Franchise Tax Board (FTB)	Activating the 1-800 number call center

The plan recognises the need for the state to 1) communicate and coordinate with state agencies and local government, 2) mobilise resources and initiate actions in advance of local requests, and 3) support the local government’s actions according to the Standardized Emergency Management System (SEMS).²⁴²

²⁴² Ibid.

When the forecasters of the National Weather Service (NWS), based on certain criteria, predict a heatwave then NWS will issue a Special Weather Statement based on how far in advance of the event they are making the prediction. Specifically:²⁴³

- An Excessive Heat Outlook is issued by the NWS 3-7 days in advance of an event to give advance notice of the possibility of excessively hot conditions. Criteria match those of an Excessive Heat Warning. If predicted weather conditions continue to hold, an Outlook may become an Excessive Heat Watch.
- An Excessive Heat Watch is issued by the NWS 36-48 hours in advance of an event to give advance notice of the possibility of excessively hot conditions. Criteria match those of an Excessive Heat Warning.
- An Excessive Heat Warning is issued by the NWS 0-36 hours in advance of an excessive heat event that is expected to last 2 days or more.

The contingency plan recognises three phases of state response, which provide guidelines as to the preparation and response activities that should be carried out

Phase I - Seasonal Readiness

Phase I is activated during the hotter months, between May and August, and actions taken during this phase ensure the preparedness and increased readiness of the state. Specifically, actions in this phase are following:²⁴⁴

- Initial notification of key stakeholders, such as the Departments of Food and Agriculture and of Public Health.
- Review of existing plans, procedures, and resources.
- Verification of use/availability of key facilities.
- Updating / validating notification processes.
- Initiating awareness campaigns through the media or local agencies.
- Orientation and training to plans and procedures.

Phase II – Heat Alert

Various alerts can cause the activation of Phase II of the contingency plan. Specifically, heat-related special weather statements issued by either the National Weather Service or from one or more jurisdictions or credible predictions from other services concerning power outages, electrical blackouts or rotating blackouts may activate Phase II. At the same time information flow between local and state agencies is increased to support the following actions that are taken during Phase II:²⁴⁵

- Initial coordination call and periodic or daily calls as needed among the key state agencies and the potentially affected operational areas and regions with weather and power updates.
- Increasing public information efforts, such as releasing critical pre-scripted and public safety information and distributing excessive heat emergency pre-scripted educational materials.
- Contacting local public health and other officials, such as the California Emergency Management Agency and the Emergency Medical Services Authority, to ensure contact with those most vulnerable to excessive heat.
- Confirmation of roles, identify specific local needs.

²⁴³ Ibid.

²⁴⁴ Ibid.

²⁴⁵ Ibid.

- Confirm details of agency participation, staffing.
- Stand-by and activation (if needed) of state-owned facilities as cooling centres
- If cooling centres are open:
 - Activation of the toll-free information number.
 - Activation of the Heatwave Web Portal to include: maps of cooling facilities with information provided by local and state agencies; general information about measures to reduce the effects of excessive heat conditions; and links to the OA offices.

Phase III – Heat Emergency

When conditions in one or more operational areas pose a severe threat Phase III is activated. Conditions may include the notification of one or more jurisdictions which have proclaimed an emergency related to excessive heat, the abnormal animal mortality due to excessive heat, the excess numbers in human medical emergencies and mortality and the extended power outages during the expected excessive heat conditions.

Phase III efforts include urgent and comprehensive actions to complement and support local actions during the most severe heat event. These actions may include:²⁴⁶

- Coordinating calls will increase as needed.
- Activation of the State Operations Center (SOC).
- Fielding requests for mutual aid and state assistance.
- Mobilizing cooling centres.
- The Governor may declare a state of emergency in the affected area.

These aforementioned phases are activated based on the severity of the risk of heat to vulnerable populations, the general population, and animals. The direct involvement of state and local agencies to protect individuals increases with the severity of the risk.

The plan contains specific actions to be taken by the state in each of the three phases, and a checklist to guide local actions. The specific action steps include the following:²⁴⁷

- Coordinating among state and local agencies (all phases).
- Disseminating information (all phases).
- Preparing cooling centres to support local response efforts (phase II).
- Activating cooling centres (phases II and III).
- Directly contacting and monitoring those at risk (phases II and III).
- Transporting those at risk to cooling centres (phases II and III).
- Governor’s proclamation of a state of emergency (phase III).

5.2.2 Lessons learned

The following lessons, identified by Professor Eric Klinenberg of the Department of Sociology at the University of California, were learned from the California heatwave in 2006.²⁴⁸

²⁴⁶ Ibid.

²⁴⁷ Ibid.

²⁴⁸ Eric Klinenberg, “Why Heatwaves are so Deadly, and How California Can Prevent Future Disasters”, Missouri Public Service Commission, 2006. http://psc.mo.gov/CMSInternetData/Electric/Missouri%20Energy%20Task%20Force/August%2021,%202006/CA_heat_hearing_082106.pdf

- Better information flow should be achieved between local media and the public, which needs to be educated about which groups are in greater risk and how each one can protect themselves against the oncoming phenomenon.
- Simple measures such as exposure to air conditioning and constant hydration are often the difference between life and death. Authorities should make sure that isolated elderly, the mentally ill, the homeless and the poor are supported accordingly.
- Local media should also urge the citizens and community groups to check up on each other and especially the vulnerable.
- Cooling centres should be opened and spread in areas affected the most. Air conditioning should be available to all nursing homes and public housing. Ensure that the most vulnerable residents can get to cooling centres by providing transportation.
- Farm workers in particular should work by taking regular breaks, work in shaded areas, if possible, drink a lot of fluids and reduce their working hours during periods of highest heat.
- Compile registries containing the information of elderly, seniors living alone, people being treated for mental illnesses, single room occupancy hotels.
- Set up call centres, people will want to communicate and ask for advice.
- Use local agencies – community police, department on aging, emergency services – and perform routine visits to vulnerable groups during the heatwave.
- A high occurrence of heat related incidents at a county's hospitals should put all city agencies on alert.
- Local departments should cooperate and coordinate relief actions while mayors must command extra resources from city agencies when necessary.

Again, as was the case with the French heatwave in 2003, the North America heatwave that hit California in 2006 produced a high death toll due to lack of communication, information flow from the media to the public and the lack of neighbourhood togetherness. Local agencies should have been more involved in the process of informing the public of the imminent heatwave while also perform routine visits to the most vulnerable population. The groups that suffered the most were the elderly, the isolated and the poor, who had no way of both preparing for the heatwave and dealing with it when the time came. Further involvement from the local agencies would have also reduced the death toll by performing routine visits, asking around neighbourhoods and checking up on any residents who might belong to a high risk social group.

5.3 CONCLUSION

In this chapter the consortium presented two case studies, namely the French heatwave of 2003 and the California heatwave of 2006. There are a lot of similarities between the two use cases mainly as a result of the death toll observed in both cases was triggered by more or less the same factors. California did have a contingency plan which was followed when the disaster struck but as the findings point out, there is also significant room for improvement. That was not the case for France, which did not have a plan to begin with. Rescue operations would benefit by the findings mentioned below and the consortium will also have a chance in later deliverables to evaluate these findings and assess the possible use of social media in an effort to mitigate possible impacts caused by heatwaves.

Communication

In both cases, better communication between local agencies would have been instrumental in saving the lives of the individuals who were vulnerable to the heatwave. Also, the information flow between the agencies and the individuals living in the affected areas would have been more successful if the former engaged in actions such as visits to poorer parts of the state/city where residents might have not had the chance to be properly informed of the imminent heatwave. Finally, the media should communicate and stress the importance of the situation while offering advice on how to prepare and deal with the phenomenon.

Preparedness

The lack of sufficient preparedness measures also played a big role in the increase of excess deaths during the heatwave period in either case. The absence of registries, where information about the elderly, the poor and the disabled would be stored, meant that the local agencies in both cases did not know the number and the whereabouts of individuals vulnerable to extreme heat.

The public

Both heatwaves highlighted the need for neighbourhood members to be better organised when dealing with such crisis. Solidarity between those members of the public has the potential to be lifesaving during a heatwave than in any other kind of crisis. Most importantly though, the notion that a heatwave is a silent killer needs to be instilled in the public's mind so that in another occurrence, they would be more proactive in protecting their fellow citizens.

The COSMIC project will benefit from the findings of the two use cases described in this chapter. During heatwaves, information exchange is of paramount importance as valuable messages need to reach even the most isolated of the population. However, as will be seen in Task 2.2 of the COSMIC project, the means to which messages are communicated are not as direct as with other types of crises, largely because of the demographics of the affected community.

6 WILDFIRES

Wildfire is an essential element of the human experience on earth. It is an event from which humans have both benefited (e.g., fertile soil) and suffered (e.g., devastation of property and even entire communities).²⁴⁹ It can be regarded as a catastrophic natural event as well as the product of human modification of ecological and environmental conditions. As scholars have noted:

“Indigenous people used anthropocentric fire for many purposes besides warmth and cooking. Native people used fire to maintain ecosystems that promoted specific flora and fauna. Fires were set on a regular basis to promote grasses and provide forage for wildlife. Native Americans actively burned areas of forest and grasslands. Fire, having lost its wildness, became a tool of Greek and American agriculturalists. Pastoralists used fire to promote grass and forage, and farmers used fire to clear fields and reduce woody debris. Out-of-control fire signalled danger and the potential loss of property and the means of production. The potential loss of standing timber in forestlands rose from a maritime problem to national levels of concern for lumber and other forestland benefits such as watershed management and wildlife habitat.”²⁵⁰

However, the management of wild fires has become increasingly important in the latest decennia as the risks from catastrophic fires have risen. Wildfires (along with other natural disasters such as floods and earthquakes) constitute the most devastating natural disasters in the Euro-Mediterranean countries such as Portugal, Spain, Italy, France and Greece. In adverse climatic conditions predicted over the next decades, the wildfire problem may potentially intensify.²⁵¹ As wildfires cannot be completely prevented governmental authorities have to prepare for suppression as well as search and rescue activities. Accordingly, chapter 6 is concerned with suppression as well as search and rescue activities in relation to wildfires. Partners have chosen to focus on wildfires due to its high societal and ecological impact (as previously discussed in COSMIC D1.1 Report on security crises with high societal impact).²⁵² Two cases have been selected and analysed: 1) the 2007 Greece wildfires and 2) the 2007 Southern California wildfires. These two cases have been selected because they are well investigated and documented. Importantly, both cases provide a detailed understanding of all the relevant aspects that come into play when a society is confronted with large-scale wildfires and its devastating impact.

The case study analysis was conducted by assessing related reports, government policies on standard operating wildfire suppression procedures as well as search and rescue procedures, news articles and other scientific literature. This chapter will proceed by discussing each of the case studies individually. Subsequently the two case studies are compared, similarities and differences are identified and lessons are drawn for the COSMIC project.

²⁴⁹ Henderson, M., K. Kalabokidis, E. Marmaras, P. Konstantinidis and M. Marangudakis, M., Fire and society: a comparative analysis of wildfire in Greece and the United States, *Human Ecology Review*, Vol., 12, Issue 2, 2005, p. 169.

²⁵⁰ Ibid.

²⁵¹ Ibid.

²⁵² Watson, Hayley, Kush Wadhwa, Rachel Finn, Ioannis Kotsiopoulos, Angelos Yannopoulos, Jelle Groenendaal, Jelle, Arjen Schmidt, David de Vries, and Ira Helsloot, “Deliverable D1.1: Report on security crises with high societal impact”, *Deliverable 1.1 of the COSMIC project*, 31 July 2013.

6.1 GREECE WILDFIRES (2007)

In 2007 extreme weather events - exceptionally high summer temperatures following a winter drought - made the resinous pine forests in Greece more flammable than usual and created very favourable conditions for extensive fires. Combined with very strong winds in the summer these circumstances made large-scale and fast moving wildfires possible. The fire season of 2007 in Greece was the worst in recent history as it set new records with regard to damages and loss of life.

More than 270,000 hectares of vegetation burned and more than 110 villages were affected directly by the fire fronts. More than 4000 homes were totally or partially destroyed. Most important, a total of 84 people, mostly civilians, lost their lives in a series of fire related accidents.²⁵³ The most severe fires took place in the Peloponnese. The Olympia site, which is in Peloponnese, was also threatened by the blaze. The site and its popular museum were saved but all the forest area around it burned down. According to international assessment firm, Standard and Poor's, the total damages were estimated at €3 billion to €5 billion – the equivalent of 1.4% to 2.4% of the country's Gross National Product. Given the difficult situation and widespread damage, the Government of Greece declared a disaster situation and subsequently received support from 20 European Union Member States and neighbouring countries.²⁵⁴ The enormous fire disaster made headline news worldwide and, as the country came to terms with having battled an outbreak of some 3,000 forest blazes, people were left wondering about the causes and the circumstances that had led up to it.²⁵⁵

6.1.1 Standard operating procedures

Wildfires occur in Greece primarily due to complex interactions among biophysical and societal factors: temporal and spatial variability in climate and weather conditions, ecological conditions, land use patterns, and political-economic activities all contribute to influencing when, where, how often, and at what intensity these wildfires burn. Institutional structures and practices, spanning to local to international scales, are also influencing fire occurrence and impacts.²⁵⁶ All these variables have contributed to the occurrence and impact of Greece's 2007 wildfires.

Until the 1980s, wildfire risks were relatively limited since intensive agriculture kept rural areas in a good fuel free condition. However, by the late 1980s intensive agriculture had declined significantly, leaving fields and forests unattended. Furthermore, farmers and younger people moved to the city due to the attractive employment possibilities in the larger cities. Many mountain villages were largely abandoned, leaving just an elderly population there, who could do little to control vegetation. As a result, fuels increased dramatically in the 90s and 00s and any wildfires that occurred began to threaten wider and also populated

²⁵³ Xanthopoulos, G., D.X. Viegas and D. Caballero, The fatal fire entrapment of Artemida (Greece) 2007, *Recent Forest Fire Related Accidents in Europe*, JRC Scientific and Technical Reports, 2009, pp. 65-75.

²⁵⁴ "Russia, Europe and Near Asia: Greece", *US Forest Service, International Programs*, no date. <http://www.fs.fed.us/global/globe/europe/greece.htm>

²⁵⁵ Xanthopoulos, G., Who should be responsible for forest fires? Lessons from the Greek experience, in: A.González-Canán (Ed.), *Proceedings of the II International Symposium on Fire Economics, Planning, and Policy: A Global View*, Pacific Southwest Research Station, Forest Service, U.S. Department of Agriculture, Albany, CA, 2008, pp. 189-201.

²⁵⁶ Morehouse, B. J., M. Henderson, K. Kalabokidis and T. Iosifides, Wild Fire Governance: Perspectives from Greece. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, Vol. 13, Issue 4, 2011, pp. 349-371.

areas.²⁵⁷

In Greece, wildfire prevention management has a large history of institutional problems. Most of them are associated with the allocation of responsibility (and funding) for forest and fire management. From 1948 to 1998, the Forest Service, which resided then within the Ministry of Agriculture (now within the Ministry of Environment), was mandated to carry out integrated management of forests and forest fire.^{258 259} In 1998, in the wake of a series of extensive and intense wildfire episodes, the Greek national government shifted responsibility for firefighting to the Fire Service, which was part of the Ministry of Public Order. Most aspects of wildfire prevention remained with the Forest Service, which was reorganised into a regional structure without any provision for effective and consistent central coordination of activities across the country. For instance, since the shift of responsibility there were no trustworthy data gathered on forest fires and their causes. This was a major obstacle to the formulation of any effective forest fire prevention strategy. In addition, personnel at the Forest Service had started to retire at high rates without proportional new personnel, thus all in all, limiting its capability to successfully carry out research and fulfil all forest management and protection tasks (e.g., range management has been minimal and prescribed burning is only considered at a theoretical level). Furthermore, lack of technological know-how and adequate funding for fire prevention (e.g., fire detection, fuels management, road maintenance, law enforcement, education and training) worsen the situation. As a result, poorly managed forest ecosystems without any significant fire prevention and protection works worsen the wildfire problem in Greece, especially under the 2007 extreme weather events.²⁶⁰

Impact of EU membership

Joining the EU in 1981 is also identified as a key variable that affected the degree to which wildfire risks were mitigated ahead of the 2007 wildfires. According to some scholars, most crucial with regard to Greek fire prevention management is the Common Agricultural Policy or CAP.²⁶¹ CAP policies and practices have interfered with Greek policies. First, CAP's rules concerning agricultural crop choice and land use practices have impeded Greek fire prevention policies. Second, scholars identified that CAP lacks the sufficient authority to allow for adjustments to address issues such as fire risk.²⁶² For example, EU-driven price support increases have resulted in an increase in the total area under olive production in Greece. While abandonment of olive groves in some areas has been correctly linked to increased wildfire hazards, even well-tended groves may erupt in flames under high-stress conditions. This was also the case in the 2007 wildfires. EU policies encouraging olive production and homogeneous olive-grove landscapes that may lack adequate firebreaks may have actually increased the vulnerability of some rural citizens to the impact of wildfire.²⁶³ EU policies are also observed to pose impediments to the Forest Service's latitude of action. Prior to the time the EU regulations went into effect Forest Service employees were supported by national legislation. With Greek accession to the EU, the Forest Service had to comply with EU rules that prohibited them from carrying out such work on non-public lands'. Introduction of this institutional rule resulted in lack of institutional compatibility as well as

²⁵⁷ Xanthopoulos, 2008, pp. 189-201.

²⁵⁸ Ibid.

²⁵⁹ Morehouse, Henderson, Kalabokidis and Iosifides, 2011, pp. 349-371.

²⁶⁰ Xanthopoulos, 2008, pp. 189-201.

²⁶¹ Morehouse, Henderson, Kalabokidis and Iosifides, 2011, pp. 349-371.

²⁶² Ibid.

²⁶³ Ibid.

issues of remoteness between the super-national policies and on-the-ground practices. According to research these issues contribute to increased fire risk ahead of the 2007 wildfires.²⁶⁴

According to scholars the shift of responsibilities for wildfire management was driven more by politics than by science or structured planning activities.²⁶⁵ The institutional changes resulted in an overall shift of emphasis from forest fire prevention to fire suppression.²⁶⁶ In order to be able to suppress forest fires, the Greek Fire Corps (GFC) invested heavily in firefighting resources and materials. Consequently, GFC has grown significantly from 1998 to 2007. In 2005 there were more than 1000 officers and permanent firefighters, assisted by 5000 seasonal firefighters during the summer. The number of fire trucks has exceeded 1000 units of various types. Furthermore the GFC has acquired experience and its organisation has improved significantly. The aerial means in the country have become among the strongest in the world, compared to the size of the country.²⁶⁷

Prior to the 2007 wild fire season, there were many warning signals that predicted the possibility of extraordinary large-scale wild fires. The year 2007 was characterised by higher-than-average monthly temperatures, coupled with three heatwaves reaching record-breaking temperatures. Snow in winter was scarce and the little rain in Southern and central Greece warned of a difficult fire season ahead. In response to these warning signs, the Government took preparatory action and increased its firefighting capacity by adding heavy-lift and amphibian water-bombers.²⁶⁸

Despite the availability of more firefighting resources such as water-bombing aircrafts, fire trucks and firefighters, scholars identified several serious failures in the preparation to the 2007 wildfires. First, the Fire Service proved to be not adequately prepared and trained for its duties in fighting forest fires.²⁶⁹ The training and operational mode of the Fire Service in urban firefighting was principally concerned with the protection of humans and infrastructure rather than wildfires. Second, it became evident that no provision had been made for adequate cooperation between the personnel of the Forest and Fire Services at all levels. As a result, the knowledge and know-how of forest fighting tactics and risk from the Forest Service was not sufficiently used before and during the response to the wildfires.²⁷⁰ Third and interrelated, there appeared to be a lack of adequate knowledge and training to make best use of the best equipment available globally for forest firefighting purposes, which Greek State has accumulated in recent years.²⁷¹ Fourth, the Fire Service did not invest in resources that enable the monitoring of eventual re-start of suppressed fire. There was a lack of fire-observation towers, guarding and monitoring of forests as well as no access to satellite pictures that could enable firemen to quickly find the exact location of blazes.²⁷² Fifth, the local authorities and mass media offered little useful guidance to the Greek public prior and during the wildfire season. Little attention was been devoted to enhance self-reliance of citizens that lived in high

²⁶⁴ Ibid.

²⁶⁵ Ibid.

²⁶⁶ Xanthopoulos, G., Lessons learned from the dramatic fires of 2007 and 2009 in Greece, *Technical meeting of the fire service capacity for managing forest fires, Spain, 2009*.

²⁶⁷ Maditinos, Z. and C. Vassiliadis, Mega fires: can they be managed effectively?, *Disaster Prevention and Management*, Vol. 20, Issue 1, 2011, pp. 41-52.

²⁶⁸ Xanthopoulos, pp. 189-201.

²⁶⁹ Ibid.

²⁷⁰ Ibid.

²⁷¹ Ibid.

²⁷² Xanthopoulos, 2009.

risk areas. As a result, the public appeared to be largely unprepared for the self-protection measures it could take in the case of a large-scale wildfire.²⁷³

Practice

In late June 2007 a heatwave with temperatures exceeding 40 Celsius contributed to an early start of the fire season. By 28 August, mainly due to calmer winds, most wildfires were brought under control. In table 6 a summary is provided of the events from June till the end of August.²⁷⁴

Table 6: chronicle of events²⁷⁵

Date	Event
27 June 2007	A fire in the area of Magnesia, central Greece, burned the highly- visited Mount Pelion. Another large fire on 28 June erupted close by, this time in Agia on Mount Ossa, claiming two lives. A few hours later, a fire near Parnitha National Park in Attica spread towards Athens and the top of Parnitha mountain. Although stopped the next day, the fire burned more than 5,000 hectares of land, including two-thirds of the park's core.
1-15 July 2007	More fires started around the country. These were fought by aerial means but with increasing difficulty.
16 July 2007	At the base of Mount Hymettus in southeast Athens, a fire fanned by strong winds encroached on people's homes. Aerial firefighting units, consisting of Canadair water-bombers, Erickson helicopters and an MI-26 helicopter, controlled the spread of the fire
17 July 2007	A second heatwave hit the country, reaching 44°C in parts of central Greece and bringing with it a second round of disasters. Numerous fires erupted that escaped initial firefighting attacks and later grew into large blazes. One fire burned through the ancient Acropolis at Corinth, including large tracts of forest and agricultural cultivation, for three days.
24 July 2007	A fire started in a rubbish dump near the village of Kounina in the north Peloponnese. Although it was controlled quickly, it was not guarded properly, and so re-ignited the following morning. Initial air attacks were delayed (as other fires were in progress) and, aided by an inclined topography and a strong wind, the fire accelerated and burned, almost unobstructed, through the surrounding areas and mountain slopes. It burned for three days, killing three people and destroying over 70 homes in nine different villages. Some 30,000 hectares of land were obliterated. This fire, along with other major fires that occurred concurrently and which burned for more than a week – created a feeling among many that the firefighting mechanism of the country could not cope. In response, the Government requested help from the European Union, while, in parallel, it secured additional aerial firefighting means from Russia.
5 August 2007	In northwest Greece, much-needed storms extinguished numerous high-elevation fires that had been burning for more than ten days in the region. The rain saved that part of the country from suffering a similar fate to what was to follow in southern Greece.
16 August 2007	A fire started on the mountain of Penteli on the northeast boundary of the basin of Athens. Initial ground force attacks failed. Adverse weather and fire conditions led to a strong convection column developing, making an aerial attack impossible for at least two hours. By that time, the fire had already reached the suburbs of Athens, destroying tens of houses and over 800 hectares of land.
17-22 August 2007	For the first time on record, Greece was seeing a third heatwave – with temperatures of 40°C lasting for three days. Strong winds of 50-70km/hr and extremely low relative humidity levels of 8% to 20% created volatile fire conditions in the south of the country. As predicted, many fires erupted in the region. Faced with ineffective initial ground and air attacks, the fires quickly grew out of control.
23 August 2007	Two fires erupted in the southern Peloponnese; on Mount Parnon and on Mount Taygetos. Both fires raged out of control. The following day, a fire erupted near the towns of Oitylo and Areopolis, about 30km south of Taygetos. It resulted in six fatalities. However, the tragic news was soon overshadowed by massive fatalities in Ilia in the Peloponnese and also

²⁷³ Maditinos and Vassiliadis, 2011, pp. 41-52.

²⁷⁴ Adapted from Xanthopoulos, G. (2008). Greek lessons. FRM Journal. 8-12.

²⁷⁵ Ibid.

	on the island of Evia.
24 August 2007	As the relative humidity increased substantially, the wind calmed down and the temperature dropped, improving the conditions. Many locals, realizing that they could be rendered homeless if they abandoned their villages, refused to evacuate, staying instead to defend their homes. Forest Service officers and some locals applied firing-out or burn-out operations to attack the intense fires by removing unburned fuels between the control line and an advancing fire front. In addition, firebreaks were created by army vehicles, and crews from Cyprus openly used backfiring techniques, depriving the wildfires of fuel with which to burn. By that time, a huge aerial fleet – comprising 23 aeroplanes and 18 helicopters supplied by international aid – was operating in the skies of the Peloponnese and Evia to form the largest aerial firefighting fleet ever assembled in such a small area. Ground reinforcements were also substantial, reaching 400 firefighters and 16 vehicles. Help came from Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, France, Germany, Hungary, Israel, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and Turkey.
28 August 2007	Wildfires largely under control

The Artemida entrapment

One of the worst accidents that had a significant impact during the 2007 Greece Wildfire was the fatal entrapment of three seasonal fire fighters and a large group of civilians fleeing the fire near the village of Artemida in Ilia.²⁷⁶

The accident of Artemida was caused by a fire that started at about August 24, 2007, in the yard of a house in the small settlement of Paleohori. It was started by an elderly woman cooking on an open stove and was reported immediately to the fire service as a residential fire. However, as the fire caught on the vegetation close to the house it started accelerating and moving in a southwest direction fanned by a strong wind. Two water-bombers that were flying in the area were directed to the scene but unable to control the fire. The first village reached by the fire, at about 14:55, was Makistos at a distance of 1.7 km from Paleohori. The people there were caught by surprise. All but a handful left the village towards the nearby village of Artemida with the fire front running after them. The fire was spreading at an average speed of 5 km/h, enough to catch a walking man. An elderly brother and sister trying to save their donkey fled on foot but died when overtaken by the fire front. In the abandoned village most houses were destroyed or seriously damaged. Only 14 of the 60 homes did not suffer damages. Some of them were saved by the efforts of those who stayed behind and fought to save their property.²⁷⁷

The village of Artemida, was reached next by the fire at about 15:15. The people arriving from Makistos and most of the people of Artemida fled the village in two groups. There is some information that local policemen were the ones who urged the people to leave. The first group formed a convoy of cars and moved towards the town of Zaharo. The second group, at the road intersection at the end of the village, chose to drive to higher ground, towards the village of Smerna. They probably realized that the quick spread of the fire in the valley would cut-off the route to Zaharo. This group as well as the people who stayed in the village survived the fire. Some people of the group that moved towards Zaharo got entrapped by the rapidly spreading fire. These people refused to drive through the fire and were just waiting on the presence of firefighters. Unfortunately, the three seasonal firefighters, probably because of the quick fire spread and the extreme fire behaviour on the slope, failed to operate their hose and fight the flames adequately (although their truck was filled with water). When this

²⁷⁶ Xanthopoulos, Viegas and Caballero, 2011.

²⁷⁷ Ibid.

became evident it was too late for the people to escape. Some stayed in their cars on the road. They did not survive. Most of the people fled from the road, running uphill in the olive grove. The fire caught some of them as they were running uphill. The rest of this group managed to make it to the top of the small hill, but on the other side they found themselves surrounded by fire from three sides. Eleven of them were trapped when they reached a small stand of pine trees on a steep rocky outcrop. They were found at the base of the rock close to each other. The total number of victims reached twenty-three, including the three firefighters.²⁷⁸

Wildfire fighting in relation to EU

In the European Union, individual Member States have responsibility within their own territorial jurisdictions for managing wildfires. They manage their own assets and follow their national command systems. The European Commission provides support and operates as a coordinator among the Member States.²⁷⁹ In the case of wildfires, a participating member could request for additional resources from other EU member states. On July 24th 2007, Greece requested for the first time that year additional aerial support from other EU member states via the European Union Civil Protection Mechanism. In the days that past, multiple additional requests followed.

The European Union Civil Protection Mechanism²⁸⁰

In the 1990s there was some minor exchange of expertise on firefighting within the EU but little in the way of formal cooperation. The Community Civil Protection Mechanism (also referred to as the Mechanism) was established in 2001 and further strengthened in 2007 to fill this gap. It provided a new capacity for coordination for European member states. It currently plays a central role in the EU wildfire risk prevention and wildfire firefighting coordination at EU level. The Mechanism, which is managed by the European Commission, has several instruments for coping with wildfires.

First, the Mechanism has its own emergency coordination and information unit, the Monitoring and Information Centre (MIC). The MIC is concerned with the exchange of information and resources among participating Member States. The function of MIC is a) to provide a coordination platform for exchange of requests for assistance and offers resources among participating states; b) to be an agent for information exchange and dissemination on natural and man-made disasters worldwide and the Mechanism interventions and; c) to be a coordinator that identifies gaps and develops solutions on the basis of the information it receives and facilitates the pooling of resources where possible.²⁸¹ The MIC receives fire risk assessment information from the European Fire Information System (EFFIS). EFFIS is a comprehensive web-based platform covering the full cycle of forest fire management, from forest fire prevention and preparedness to post-fire damage analysis. The system provides information to over 30 countries in the European and Mediterranean regions and receives detailed information of forest fire events from 22 European countries. The system supports forest fire prevention and forest fire fighting in Europe through the provision of timely and reliable information on forest fires.²⁸²

Second, the Mechanism intermediates dissemination activities and exchange of best practices among Participating States and provides training programs and exercises to intervention teams. It organises informative activities, seminars, conferences and pilot projects. For instance, it provides access to the assets in the European Forest Fire Tactical Reserve (EUFFTR), a pilot

²⁷⁸ Ibid.

²⁷⁹ European Policy Evaluation Consortium, Study on wild fire fighting resources sharing models – Final Report. London, UK, 2010.

²⁸⁰ Ibid.

²⁸¹ Ibid.

²⁸² San-Miguel-Ayanz et al., Comprehensive Monitoring of Wildfires in Europe: The European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS), European Commission, Joint Research Centre Italy, 2012.

project designed to set up cooperation between Member States on combating forest fires during high-risk seasons.

Third, through the Mechanism, the European Commission is able to mobilise small teams of experts to the site of a wildfire, provide and distribute information during a wildfire, play a facilitating role in the coordination of assistance requests and offers from Participating States, coordinate with other actors at the international level and with other EU services and, last but not least, provide co-financing for the transport of assistance to the affected areas on the request of the offering Participating States. The Mechanism facilitates as well the process of drawing lessons after each wildfire season. The organisation of weekly video conferences with the Southern Participating States, prone to forest fires and owning aerial forest fighting assets, and of lessons learnt meetings with all Participating States feeds into the organization of the consequent operations.²⁸³

Governmental response failures

Investigations have identified several pitfalls regarding the response to the several forest fires between June and the end of August.^{284 285} There was an absence of a coordination plan as well as a command and control structure that suited the way humans make decisions under stressful, heavy and highly uncertain and dynamic conditions. During the firefighting operations, firefighter capacity and resources were unequally distributed across the many fires in the country. Ground firefighting was very ineffective and poorly coordinated, which can be attributed to an excessive number of top-ranking fire service officers being disbanded in March 2007. In addition, coordination between ground forces and aerial forces: aerial firefighting had a limited availability (due to multiple fires) and an inability to fight difficult fires. There was also heavy reliance on aerial means during initial firefighting attacks, leading to ground crew complacency. Quick fire acceleration and the lack of timely and adequate aerial support due to the large number of fires led to failure. Due to a lack of preparedness, there was almost total reliance by ground forces on water for extinguishing fires. Use of hand tools was limited, with no provision for alternative fire control, with no provision for alternative fire control. As a result, effectiveness in areas with few roads was generally limited.²⁸⁶

Strikingly and already noted above, the Greek authorities were unable to mobilise and enhance self-resilience of the Greek public that were confronted with the wildfire. Research showed that citizens did not take any appropriate action when the wildfires broke out. In certain places, blazes were expected to arrive within three to four days but people still did not take basic safety measures such as clearing their fields and groves from undergrowth. Old people refused to leave their homes. Additionally, owners of old houses offering no protection did nothing to improve their houses' resistance to a potential fire situation. This inaction is associated by researchers with poor citizens' training in fire prevention and confrontation.²⁸⁷

Research revealed that arsonists were responsible for more than half of the fires. Arsonists may have strong motives for starting blazes in Greece. In 2007, rising incomes had fuelled a construction boom. Demand was high for land near the sea to build second homes. Although the Greek law states that builders cannot put up homes on forest land, developers can work

²⁸³ European Policy Evaluation Consortium (2010), 2010.

²⁸⁴ Xanthopoulos, 2008, pp. 189-201.

²⁸⁵ Maditinos and Vassiliadis, 2011, pp. 41-52.

²⁸⁶ Xanthopoulos, 2008, pp. 189-201.

²⁸⁷ Maditinos and Vassiliadis, 2011, pp. 41-52.

around the rules.²⁸⁸ In addition, in 2007 Greece lacked a land registry covering the whole country. Therefore it is easy to have burnt land reclassified as farmland, which can then be sold for development. There was also an allegation by an article of the Economist²⁸⁹, that “in many places local officials are open to bribery to ease the issuing of planning permits without asking too many questions”. The same article also pointed at the practice of policy makers to offer legal ways for declaring amnesties for illegal buildings from time to time²⁹⁰. The remainder of the wildfires, according to Greek forestry officials, were caused by flaying sparks from electricity pylons or human carelessness. Seven people were arrested in the aftermath of the fires that struck Elis and Evia, an island in the Aegean Sea near Athens. According to news coverage, both the anti-terrorist squad and intelligence services joined the hunt for the arsonists.²⁹¹

Due to the elections in September, the Greek government were quick to come up with some financial assistance for those who were affected by the wildfires. For instance, the villagers from Elis received 13000 euro in cash, equivalent to more than a year’s income for most of the villagers. Few were grateful however; many who escaped from burning villages said in news coverage they felt the emergency services had let them down.²⁹² Interestingly, the wildfires played a significant role in the election period and were used by the opposition to blame the government for their failure in the response and preparation to the wildfire. Proponents of the government claimed that the opponents had organised a fire-raising campaign to discredit the party and damage its chances of being re-elected.²⁹³

6.1.2 Lessons learned

Unfortunately, partners were unable to discover the ‘official’ lessons learned formulated by Greek authorities, because these were not presented on the Internet or in other accessible documents. Therefore, partners draw the following lessons from the 2007 Greece wildfires based on their own understanding of the events:

- Without proper forest and wildfire management, it is impossible to mitigate and control the risks that are associated with wildfires. However, forest and wildland management are not activities that can be carried out by governmental organisations alone. Also citizens living in wildfire-prone areas need to take action by removing potential fuel and controlling vegetation.
- Most of the forest fires in Greece occur due to humans (by arson, by accident or due to inattention). Risk communication and information about wildfire prevention and preparedness are necessary to mobilise citizens to prevent the occurrence of fires in the wildfire season and to take preparatory action when (there is a likelihood to be) confronted with fire.
- Although sufficient availability of resources is vital for the successful suppression of wildfires, the 2007 Greece wildfires demonstrated that it is perhaps more important to consider how these resources are used.

²⁸⁸ The Economist, *Fighting Greek Fires*, August 28th 2007. <http://www.economist.com/node/9718557>

²⁸⁹ Ibid.

²⁹⁰ A recent example is law 4178/2013, passed in August 2013, which for a relatively low fine legalises illegal buildings

²⁹¹ The Economist, *Fighting Greek Fires*, August 28th 2007. <http://www.economist.com/node/9718557>

²⁹² Ibid.

²⁹³ Ibid.

- Self-reliance of citizens is of vital importance for their own chance of survival when confronted with wildfire. When large-scale populated areas are threatened by fire, the chance of survival depends heavily on the way citizens respond since emergency agencies are likely to have too little resources and means to save all those people who are at risk.

Specifically related to the The Artemida entrapment, scholars have identified the following lessons:²⁹⁴

- Evacuation of settlements in case of forest fires is not necessarily a good option. However, when an evacuation is done spontaneously, without planning, the results can be catastrophic especially if realised at the last moment.
- The best option seems to be to avoid remaining in the house for as long as possible. This is particularly true for the majority of homes in Greece and the rest of the Mediterranean region which are generally not built with flammable materials. There are no reports of lives lost for citizens that remained in their homes.
- Vegetation treatment for fire hazard reduction is a wise measure, especially close to settlements. Citizens as well as the state may find themselves in much better and safer condition in case of an extreme fire event such as the one experienced in the Peloponnese in August 2007.
- The people in fire prone countries need to be educated about forest fires, about the need and measures to prevent them, the risks they pose and the ways to protect themselves and their property.
- Firefighter safety training should be a priority for both professional and seasonal firefighters.

The 2007 Greek wildfire shows that without appropriate forest and wildfire management, it is impossible to mitigate and control the risks that are associated with wildfires. Therefore, (additional) investments in wildfire prevention are more effective and efficient than raising wildfire suppression capacities. In addition, the case shows that it is impossible to prevent wildfires from occurring since it largely is a human-induced activity (e.g., by arsonists). Therefore attention should be devoted to the fast discovery of small wildfires as well as appropriate ways to inform and warn citizens about the threat of wildfires.

6.2 CALIFORNIA WILDFIRES (2007)

In October 2007, Southern California (CA, USA) experienced a severe fire weather event characterised by intense, dry, gusty Santa Ana winds. This weather event drove a series of large-scale wildfires that took a devastating toll on people, property, natural resources and infrastructure.²⁹⁵

The wildfires had multiple causes. Several fires were triggered by power lines that had been damaged by high winds. One fire started when a semi-truck overturned. Another fire was suspected as having been deliberately caused; the suspect was shot and killed in flight by state

²⁹⁴ Xanthopoulos, Viegas and Caballero, 2011, pp. 65-75.

²⁹⁵ Kailes, J., Southern California Wildfires After Action Report, The California Foundation for Independent Living Centers and the Center for Disability Issues and the Health Professions at Western University of Health Sciences. 2008.

authorities. A ten year old boy admitted that he accidentally started the Buckweed Fire playing with matches. The causes of the remaining fires remained under investigation.²⁹⁶ The wildfires caused the largest evacuation in California's history, with over 20,000 people taking refuge in more than 50 emergency shelters and approximately half a million people were evacuated.²⁹⁷

The wildfires began in Malibu on October 20, 2007. Over the next 19 days more than 20 blazes ignited from a variety of causes in the region from Santa Barbara County to San Diego County's border with Mexico. The wildfires destroyed almost 1500 homes and burned over 500.000 acres of land. During the wildfire, 17 people lost their lives: 10 were killed by the fires outright, three were killed while evacuating, four died from other fire siege related causes and 140 firefighters and an unknown number of civilians were injured. Portions of the electrical power distribution network, telecommunications systems and even some community water sources were destroyed. Transportation was disrupted over a large area for several days, including numerous road closures. Both the Governor of California and the President of the United States personally toured the ongoing fires. Governor Schwarzenegger proclaimed a state of emergency in seven counties before the end of the first day. President Bush quickly declared a major disaster. While the total impact of the 2007 fire siege was less than the disastrous fires of 2003, it was unquestionably one of the most devastating wildfire events in the history of California.²⁹⁸ The raging fire was even visible from space.²⁹⁹ The last fire was fully contained on 9 November 2007.

6.2.1 Standard operating procedures

Demands for forest management and fire detection played a considerable role in the creation of the United States Forest Service. Created in 1906, the US Forest Service (USFS) became the primary forestland management agency in the country. Large areas of forestland from the Rocky Mountains west and smaller areas in the Appalachian Mountains were divided into national forests. The US Forest Service was charged with the scientific management of the lands within the national forest system. Fire detection and suppression were goals of the conservation agency.³⁰⁰

The US Forest Service sought to control the threat of wildfire. Over a period of several decades, the US Forest Service built lookout towers, developed tools and firefighting methods, hired seasonal crews, and focused its efforts on detecting and stopping wildfires. The policy was to protect the forest resources and prevent the destruction of lives and private property in proximity to the national forests.³⁰¹

The strict prevention and suppression of forest fires, mostly in order to ensure a generous timber supply to meet the rising demands of a growing population, altered the forest and ecosystem composition. As a result, the risks of large-scale destructive wildfires increased. Researchers argued that forest fires in the United States are now unusually destructive due to forest management policies and activities (e.g., to stop the use of preventive prescribed burns

²⁹⁶ Maditinos and Vassiliadis, 2011, pp. 41-52.

²⁹⁷ Keeley, J., H. Safford, C.J. Fotheringham, J. Franklin and M. Moritz, The 2007 Southern California Wildfires: Lessons in Complexity, *Journal of Forestry*, September 2009, pp. 287-296.

²⁹⁸ Cal Fire, the US Forest Service and OES, California fire Siege 2007: an overview, 2008. http://www.fire.ca.gov/fire_protection/fire_protection_2007_siege.php

²⁹⁹ http://www.nasa.gov/vision/earth/lookingatearth/socal_wildfires_oct07.html

³⁰⁰ Henderson, Kalabokidis, Marmaras, Konstantinidis and Marangudakis, (2005), p. 169.

³⁰¹ Ibid.

of forest, which is currently re-introduced however) over the last 100 years. Large-scale timber harvesting especially the removal of large trees has created large amounts of small diameter trees and woody debris and hence fuels. Coupled with drought, this leads to serious wildland risks. The fuel situation must however be placed in the context of the increasing popularity of residential building on the edges of national forests and wildlands. The population growth along the margins of public forests has increased dramatically due to the general increase of the US citizen population.³⁰²

Due to series of catastrophic wildfire incidents in the 80s, 90s and 00s, the challenges posed by wildfire have received increased policy responses at various levels of government. In 2000, a report recommending responses to severe, ongoing fire activity, reducing impacts of fires on rural communities and the environment, and ensuring sufficient fire-fighting resources in the future became the cornerstone of what is now known as the National Fire Plan (NFP).³⁰³ The interagency NFP community assistance grants provide a collaborative process for awarding funds for hazardous fuels reduction projects on nonfederal land to reduce wildfire threats.³⁰⁴

The National Firewise Communities Program (NFCP) is another program that advances community wildfire preparedness initiatives by forging an alliance between communities and the local agencies involved in mitigation.³⁰⁵ This approach emphasises local community responsibility for designing and maintaining safe communities through land-use planning, mitigation activities, collective decision-making, and effective response. In addition, a community may develop a community wildfire protection plan (CWPP) to address challenges such as local firefighting capability, need for defensible space around homes/subdivisions, and where and how to prioritise land management on federal and nonfederal land, in a way that brings about comprehensive and locally supported solutions.³⁰⁶

Monitoring wildfire risks with remote Automated Weather Stations

Throughout Southern California, Remote Automated Weather Stations (RAWS) are solar-powered weather stations strategically positioned throughout the United States, often in isolated areas. These units collect, store, and transmit important weather information on an hourly basis. RAWS sensors monitor: Wind speed and direction, wind gusts, precipitation, air temperatures, solar radiation, relative humidity, fuel moisture, soil moisture and temperature. In addition to fire weather, data collected from the more than 1,800 stations are used in numerous applications, including climatology, resource management, flood warning, noxious weed control, all-risk management, and air quality management.³⁰⁷

The State of California is going further by requiring defensible space and fire resistant construction. The State's defensible space program requires homeowners in high fire areas to maintain 100 feet of cleared vegetation away from the home. Local fire departments conduct inspections and if a homeowner is not in compliance the work may be done for them with the bill added as a lien on their property. While this program has been effective, enforcement is still difficult. Officials across the State inspected nearly 117,000 properties in 2005 and 2006 but issued only 160 defensible-space citations. According to research officials have admitted

³⁰² Ibid.

³⁰³ Bihari, M., E.M. Hamin and R.L. Ryan, Understanding the Role of Planners in Wildfire Preparedness and Mitigation, *ISRN Forestry*, 2012.

³⁰⁴ Ibid.

³⁰⁵ Ibid.

³⁰⁶ Ibid.

³⁰⁷ Cal Fire, the US Forest Service and OES, 2008.

that the program only passed in 2003, and that they are giving homeowners opportunity and time to comply voluntarily before they get much stricter. Building codes are also much stricter in California than they are in most other parts of the West. Most counties require fire resistant roofing and siding materials for new developments, and in some cases double-paned windows. However, very few areas have gone so far as to require retrofitting of existing homes.³⁰⁸

Shelter-in Place Communities³⁰⁹

Due to the likely occurrence of wildfires each year in southern California, citizens and local governments have set up fire resistant communities in some areas. In these communities all of the homes are constructed to withstand radiant heat and flying embers using concrete tile roofs, double-paned heat-resistant windows, and enclosed eaves. Stone and concrete culverts protect homes adjacent to canyons and other open space, and many of the swimming pools are equipped with valves to allow firefighters to draw water. A 200 foot greenbelt with fire-resistant landscaping rings the properties, and the development has been laid out with firefighter access and evacuation in mind. Fire officials were so confident that the community would survive the recent fires that they allowed residents to shelter in place as the fires approached. Most watched the fires from their lawns, hoses at the ready to extinguish any embers that managed to ignite anything on their property. Not a single home was destroyed in these fire resistant communities during the 2007 fires. Obviously, not everyone can afford to live in such community. According to the California Department of Forestry and Fire Protection, over 5 million homes in the State are in high to very high risk to wildfires, and 84% of those are in areas that could be designated wildland-urban interface. It is likely that many new developments will be built according to at least some of the ideas that guided construction of these fire resistant communities, but there are still a whole lot of existing homes and developments that will remain vulnerable.

Over 6,000 firefighters worked to fight the blazes in 2007. They were aided by units of the United States Armed Forces, United States National Guard, almost 3,000 prisoners convicted of non-violent crimes, and 60 firefighters from the Mexican cities of Tijuana and Tecate.³¹⁰ The Department of Defense contributed 12 engines for firefighting efforts. The National Guard called up 1,500 troops, with 17,000 available if needed; another 100 California National Guard medical personnel provided medical assistance. Six crews from the Navy's Helicopter Sea Combat Squadron 85 based at Naval Air Station North Island were assigned to battle the Witch Creek fire. Marine Corps Air Station Miramar contributed several aircraft as well as firefighting trucks to operations based in Ramona. One of the larger airtankers, the Martin Mars, sent through a private contract from its home in Port Alberni, British Columbia on 25 October, landing on Lake Elsinore in Riverside County, California. It has a 7,000 gallon capacity. Two other air tankers and their crews from Quebec worked on the fires, part of an annual three-month contract with the state of California.³¹¹

National assistance to local and state governments³¹²

The Federal Department of Homeland Security's National Response Plan uses Emergency Support Functions (ESF) as the primary mechanism to organise and provide assistance to local and state governments and tribal agencies. The purpose of the ESF is to provide the greatest possible access to the capabilities of the federal government, regardless of agency. The Stafford Act authorizes FEMA, a function of the Department of Homeland Security, to coordinate

³⁰⁸ McDaniel, J., *Southern California Fires: the Big Questions*. The Wildland Fire Lessons Learned Center, CA, 2007.

³⁰⁹ Ibid.

³¹⁰ Maditinos and Vassiliadis, 2011, pp. 41-52.

³¹¹ Ibid.

³¹² Cal Fire, the US Forest Service and OES, 2008.

support from across the federal agencies and certain non-government organizations. FEMA invokes one or more of the 15 ESFs to funnel resources to disasters and emergencies. During an ESF-4 declaration, the US Forest Service is the lead agency, and is tasked with coordinating the federally activated resources. On October 22, Governor Schwarzenegger requested a federal emergency declaration for the Southern California fire siege and FEMA activated ESF-4.

In order to synchronise all the activities conducted by the different actors in an appropriate way, a unified command system was established. On every fire where unified command was established at the local level and involved law enforcement during initial attack, evacuations were successfully conducted. Within six hours of ordering a national Incident Management Team (IMT), that team was beginning to set up an Incident Command Post (ICP) and initiate dialogue between county fire authorities and the national IMT.³¹³

Government agencies and volunteers worked together to mitigate the effects of the fires. With many businesses and schools closed, some people used their time off to help others. Officials estimated that 10,000 people were gathered at Qualcomm stadium, the largest shelter point in San Diego. Besides food, blankets and water, volunteers provided toys for children, massages, and a live rock and roll band performance. Community Emergency Report Teams, in various cities, received their first activation since the program's inception in this region. Trained volunteers provided assistance ranging from coordinating relief, to acting as a fire department auxiliary.³¹⁴

Evacuations

As already noted the 2007 fires forced hundreds of thousands of residents to evacuate. It triggered numerous road closures, and prompted school officials to cancel classes throughout the region. According to investigations evacuees quickly filled all available hotel rooms, poured into shelters, pitched tents in parking lots, or slept in their cars. Many were able to stay with nearby friends or relatives. Four days into the siege, the number of citizens displaced was estimated at nearly a million. Many major roads were closed, including Interstate-15 and Interstate-5. In San Diego County alone, the residents of at least 11 nursing homes were evacuated, and in Orange County, a jail housing 900 inmates required evacuation. Overall, local agencies and residents conducted themselves in a safe, orderly manner, following the instructions of firefighters and law enforcement officials. During the October fire siege, the Reverse 911 system was employed on a large scale, and was key to reaching thousands of citizens. Previous evacuation communications, such as those employed in the 2003 fire siege, depended on residents watching the news, listening to radio broadcasts or waiting for a personal visit from law enforcement officials giving evacuation orders. The Reverse 911 system³¹⁵ contacted nearly 200,000 citizens with recorded phone messages relevant to their communities.³¹⁶

Information search and provision behaviour by citizens³¹⁷

³¹³ Maditinos, Z., Vassiliadis, C., "Mega fires: can they be managed effectively?", *Disaster Prevention and Management*, Vol. 20 Iss: 1, 2011, pp.41 – 52

³¹⁴ Ibid.

³¹⁵ A call system used by public safety organizations in the United States to communicate with groups of people in a defined geographic area. The system uses a database of telephone numbers and associated addresses, which, when tied into geographic information systems (GIS), can be used to deliver recorded emergency notifications to a selected set of telephone service subscribers.

³¹⁶ Cal Fire, the US Forest Service and OES, 2008.

³¹⁷ Sutton, J., L. Palen and I. Shklovski, Backchannels on the front lines: Emergent uses of social media in the 2007 southern California wildfires, *Proceedings of the 5th International ISCRAM Conference*, 2008 May, pp. 624-632, Washington, DC.

Research has investigated the way citizens during the 2007 Southern California wildfires acquired and shared information about the threat: “The majority of our questionnaire respondents indicated that they sought information using mobile phones to contact friends or family (54%); through information portals and websites advertised in traditional media (76%); by accessing alternative news sources and individual blogs (38%); through discussions on various web forums (15%); from photo-sharing sites such as Flickr or Picasa (10%). Just less than 10% of our respondents used Twitter, in spite of the active media coverage on the topic. However, most of those who did use it said they discovered this technology during the wildfires. This kind of technology adoption during disasters to accommodate needs has been previously observed in prior unpublished research with text messaging during Hurricane Katrina. Although the majority of our respondents simply reported searching for information on-line, more than a third (36%) reported posting information or participating in discussion groups on-line. In fact our respondents reported exchanging information through posting and active discussions with others via text messaging (20%), discussion boards or community online forums (16%), posting on personal blogs (9%), sharing photos on sites such as Flickr or Picasa (8%), and broadcasting via Twitter (4%).

6.2.2 Lessons learned

The 2007 wildfires had large-scale impacts for Southern California. The state’s environment, the local economy and society were seriously damaged by this catastrophe. While the number of acres damaged and the number of buildings destroyed in 2007 is less than those burned in 2003, the economic and emotional damage to those personally affected was no less significant.³¹⁸ Governor Arnold Schwarzenegger called on the Blue Ribbon Task Force to assess the next steps to take at federal, state and local levels of government to prevent and fight future fires. Additionally, the Governor asked the task force to review the Governor’s Blue Ribbon Fire Commission’s recommendations, generated after the 2003 fires, to evaluate if the recommendations are still the best and most effective ways in preventing and fighting fires.

Scholars have drawn the following lessons from the 2007 Southern California wildfires³¹⁹:

- According to an in-depth investigation to the fire causes, better fire prevention is of paramount importance to prevent wildfires such as the one in 2007. This may include consideration of better restrictions on use of machinery in wildland areas during severe fire weather, placement of power lines underground in corridors of known Santa Ana winds, more conspicuous arson patrols during Santa Ana wind events, or barriers along roadsides. Fires in southern California require strategic thinking that links causal factors with necessary fire management responses. In many cases the most likely factors altering future fire impacts and outcomes are under community control and require greater attention to zoning and planning decisions.³²⁰
- Researchers agreed that with respect to the enormous size of the fires the number of fatalities was relatively low. According to scholars, this is mainly due to the prevention and preparedness measures in California aimed at informing citizens about the risks of fire and preparatory action that can be taken before and during a wild fire.
- In addition, the quick governmental decision to evacuate large areas with citizens immediately after a fire broke out was definitely effective for minimising the total amount of fatalities. Furthermore, the way citizens informed each other about the

³¹⁸ Maditinos and Vassiliadis, 2011, pp. 41-52.

³¹⁹ As mentioned before, official documents of the Greek authorities were not accessible for partners.

³²⁰ Keeley, Safford, Fotheringham, Franklin and Moritz, 2009.

wildfires via face-to-face interactions and social media also may have contribute to the relatively low injuries and fatalities related to the fires.³²¹

The 2007 Southern California wildfires provide evidence suggesting that wildfire prevention management and preparation is successful for reducing the number of fatalities and the amount of damage. It also shows how the rapid warning of those living in the affected areas stimulates self-resilience: most citizens evacuated immediately after the warning and informed each other via social media.

6.3 CONCLUSION

The aim of this chapter has been to utilise two case studies, the 2007 Greece wildfires and the 2007 California wildfires, to try to understand lessons learned from emergency response capabilities.

In general, the management of the 2007 California wildfires is evaluated in research as much more successful (in terms of response capabilities), taking into account the magnitude of the fires, compared to the 2007 Greece wildfires.³²² Although the land burned was almost three times more than that in Greece, only nine people died in California, while 84 in Greece. According to disaster scholars, therefore, authorities in California handled the disaster in a more effective way than in Greece. According to investigations the effective management was the outcome of the preparation planning together with the successful execution of this planning during the mega fires period. California is an area where wildfires are a common phenomenon. Thus, people and authorities have accepted this reality and learned how to live under these circumstances. Local fire authorities considered much of their success in response to these mega fires as being directly due to their situation awareness and preparedness. The main steps that they reported as being the keys to their success included maintaining a keen awareness of the weather while preparing to implement a response plan in case of a fire.³²³

Prevention

Due to some catastrophic accidents, in California much more attention is paid to forest fire prevention management (making protection zones, maintaining emergency roads, building watching points) than in Greece. However, in both areas the risks of wildfires cannot be completely mitigated because most of the fires are caused by human activities (deliberately or by accident). Researchers note that in both cases more attention should be devoted to investigate fire causes and the contributing factors underlying these causes as well as continuous patrol during high risk periods to discourage arson and detect new fire events on time.³²⁴

Suppression means and tactics.

Since wildfires cannot be completely prevented, the availability of sufficient fire suppression resources is needed. Time is of the essence as only small wildfires can be successfully suppressed. This requires the rapid discovery of a starting fire as well. Ordinary citizens, who are often the first to notice a starting fire, should respond as quickly as possible by warning the authorities and providing sufficient information about the exact location of the fire. But, as

³²¹ Maditinos and Vassiliadis, 2011, pp. 41-52.

³²² Ibid.

³²³ Ibid.

³²⁴ Ibid.

the Greece wildfires have shown, it is not enough to have an appropriate number of resources, it is also important to know how to use these resources and how to manage them effectively.

In California much effort has been devoted to the cooperation between governmental actors and ordinary citizens. Since large-scale forest fires are likely to exceed the available fire response resources, the assistance from ordinary people is of vital importance and should be encouraged. At the same time, however, ordinary citizens should also be informed as to when the risks are too high for them to assist in fire suppression and as to what to do when in danger.

Community preparedness

The 2007 California case showed how important it is to educate and train citizens about the causes and risks of wildfires as well as the strategies and tactics to prevent and respond to them. In addition, even special fire-proof communities are built in wildfire prone areas, although these communities only suit wealthy citizens.

Community warning

Both the 2007 Greece wildfires and the 2007 California wildfires revealed the importance of effective communication capabilities in a crisis situation. Contrary to Southern California, in Greece little attention was devoted at warning the public at risk, as well as educating them ahead on how to interpret warning signs and how to respond to them.

What can we learn from this chapter for COSMIC? First, this chapter provides further evidence that point to the importance of communication between authorities and citizens as well as among citizens (via social media) themselves regarding their safety and security. To be able to successfully suppress wildfires, early detection is of vital importance. Most wildfires are detected by citizens. By using social media in combination with mobile devices, citizens may inform emergency services by sharing pictures, the location (via GPS) of the wildfire and real-time information about the spread. In addition, citizens could also inform each other by sharing real-time information about the fire spread and by providing tips regarding preventive and preparatory action to be taken. In addition, social media could be used in the search for citizens who do not respond to messages from relatives, friends or authorities and may be in danger.

7 CONCLUSION

The purpose of this report has been to define and characterise search and rescue operations in the different types of crisis. Based on the identification of types of crisis in D1.1 “Report on security crises with high societal impact”³²⁵, partners examined five different types of crises; man-made, earthquake, floods/storms, extreme temperature and wildfire. Specific case studies examined in this report are identified in the table below.

Table 7: Case studies included in this report

Man-made	2005 London attacks 2013 Boston attacks
Earthquake	1999 Greece 2010 Haiti
Floods/Storms	2010 Storm Xynthia – France 2005 Hurricane Katrina - USA
Extreme temperature	2003 France 2006 North America (California)
Wildfire	2007 Greece 2007 California

Whilst each of the case studies supplied important lessons learned regarding disaster preparedness and response, it is also important to consider the findings across the different types of crises examined in Chapter 2 to 6 in order to determine the common elements of the lessons learned from these case studies.

Standard operating procedures

Findings from the examination of case studies suggest that in the majority of situations, with the exception of the heatwave in France in 2003, standard operating procedures would have been in place to ensure the appropriate organisation of response efforts. Similarly, in Haiti following the earthquake in 2010, whilst Haiti did not (themselves) have standard operating procedures in place there were regional procedures in place for responding to a natural disaster. The case study regarding storm Xynthia showed that the different authority levels in France have several procedures, which have to be combined in the case of a national disaster. In 2010 this led to problems between the actors involved.

In some cases such as for instance, responding to man-made crises such as that in London, search and rescue operations were not aligned to a specific type of crisis, rather they were designed to respond to any major incident. During the earthquake in Athens the Xenokratris plan of Civil Protection was issued to handle any kind of disaster that occurred in Greece. In Haiti, all assistance offered to the country was part of global and regional organisations’ mandate’s to help in any type of crisis that certain countries such as Haiti may suffer. Similarly, many of the case studies examined that were linked to the United States (e.g., the case study examining the Boston attacks, Hurricane Katrina) involved a standard response mechanism as outlined in the US’s National Response Plan.

To an extent, findings from this analysis reveal that whilst standard operating procedures may have been in place prior to a crisis occurring, this is not to say that they will be optimally used, or strictly followed; rather, as a crisis unfolds the demands of the crisis may call for an alternative response. This can (in part) be linked to the magnitude of the crisis that stakeholders are faced with. For instance, the magnitude of the damage and the number of fatalities and victims between Katrina and Xynthia greatly differ. These differences challenge

³²⁵ Watson, H., Wadhwa, K., Finn, R., Kotsiopoulos, I., Yannopoulos, A., Groenendaal, J., Schmidt, A., de Vries, D and Helsloot, I., “Report on security crises with high societal impact”, *Deliverable 1.1 of the COSMIC project*, 31 July 2013.

the organisations affected in different ways. Although, as a result of the deficient preparation phase, Xynthia posed a serious task for authorities, volunteers and other actors, the response and recovery phases after Katrina were much more comprehensive.

Elsewhere, as seen with regard to the London bombings, for instance, whilst standard operating procedures were in place for documenting those involved in the attacks that were not injured, this did not mean that these details were collected; rather, lessons learned suggest that there was a failing on part of response organisations to adequately cater for, and record information of those people not injured in the attacks. The case studies about floods/storms and wildfires showed that procedures were mostly implemented, but that particular circumstances and relations between different actors led to problems in the execution of these procedures. For example the provision of information to citizens became one such problem. In the case of wildfires, the research demonstrated that while the procedures can be well prepared, the behaviour of individual citizens could amplify (by removing fuels or controlling vegetation) or lessen (by a lack of those measures) the success of them. In Greece, even though Xenokritis had been issued a year before the disastrous earthquake, bureaucracy and a hard to adapt national mechanism meant that the preparedness measures and operating procedures were not followed in an optimal way.

Thus, while standard operating procedures may be in place, this does not warrant that response organisations will be able to follow them fully.

Communication

Lessons learned regarding communication prior to and during crises are central to the activities of the COSMIC project. Findings from the analysis of different types of crises show that there are some common themes relating to communication influencing preparedness and response capabilities, although, notably the nature of the issue is not always the same. During risk and crisis communication factors such as transparency, quickness, completeness and correctness may be in conflict with each other. Journalists ask for quick information and on social media several rumours circulate. Authorities have to deal with those circumstances. Furthermore, when authorities are the sender, information is often only generated by traditional media, and, because of that, it does not reach the entire target group. When for example evacuation is one of the most important and outrageous measures, it is important that citizens and companies are timely informed about possible authority decisions and their implications. The cases concerning the floods and storms in France and the United States showed that the provision of information during these crises was not sufficient. Eventually, the evacuation developed chaotically.

As with many large-scale crises there were some notable issues relating to broadcasting capabilities being affected during a crisis, which may consequently, hamper the abilities of responders and members of the public to communicate following a crisis. This was seen following the man-made crises investigated in Chapter 2, where during both the London attacks in 2005 and the Boston attacks in 2013, cell phone networks were affected. In London this was further affected by the over-reliance of the emergency services on mobiles for communication, as well as the extensive use of mobile phones by members of the public in the area. Elsewhere, following the earthquake in Haiti (for instance) communication facilities were also damaged leading to difficulties in communication between different stakeholders. During the California wildfires, in 2007, telecommunication systems were destroyed, as a result communication between members of search and rescue teams faltered and the effectiveness in the response phase was declined.

The 2013 Boston attacks also highlighted the contribution of new media applications such as social networking sites in enabling authorities to communicate with members of the public following a large-scale incident.³²⁶ Although they cannot be solely relied upon in an emergency, such a means may become vital in helping ease the flow of information towards members of the public. This was highlighted as a problem following the 2005 London attacks where members of the public were not sufficiently informed on unfolding events (e.g. the impact of the attacks on the availability of public transport and the closure of certain areas).

In Chapter 6, partners investigated lessons learned from two wildfires; Greece and California, both of which occurred in 2007. Contrary to California, in Greece there was a distinct lack of communication with members of the public warning them of unfolding events. Similarly, in Chapter 5, partners identified problems with communicating with members of the public following the 2003 heatwave in Europe, where the lack of communication hampered the abilities of the public to respond to the increasing temperatures they faced. This was further compounded by the lack of announcements of alerts and advice from crucial media such as the news media, illustrating the importance of effective communication strategies among responding organisations, including broadcasting agencies and the public.

The need for effective communication at different stages of a crisis was also evident from the case studies examined in this report. The analysis of wildfire and heatwave cases revealed the importance of effective preparation activities, where communicating and educating members of the public is central to building resilience within the community so as to respond to a crisis. For instance, dissimilar to the wildfires in Southern California, in Greece little attention was devoted into warning the public of the risk they faced, as well as educating them ahead on how to interpret warning signs and how to adequately respond to them. Similarly, as identified in Chapter 5, in the event of a heatwave, the media could play a more extensive role in helping vulnerable groups (such as the elderly) to prepare more adequately for the risks they may had to face.

As a final point, the analysis also revealed the importance of more effective communication strategies among different types of stakeholders involved in responding to a crisis. Notably, the analysis of both earthquake case studies in Chapter 3 revealed that communication between humanitarian agencies and organisations could have been better organised. Furthermore, following the earthquake in Athens for instance, there was a distinct lack of communication between national bodies and civil society organisations which hampered the efficiency of operations in the field. In Haiti, the extent of foreign aid and assistance required a more efficient communication strategy to ensure the better use of resources.

Thus issues relating to communication are not simply tied to the (potential) failure of systems, but also the means with which this communication takes place to help warn and prepare the public, and furthermore coordinate relief efforts. As revealed in D2.1, there are a number of new media applications that may enhance communication abilities during a crisis situation. Lessons learned from the use of new media applications will be further developed in work package 2, together with other work packages, this will be further examined in work package 6 “Guidelines” of the COSMIC project.

³²⁶ Further in-depth information relating to the use of new media in responding to the Boston attacks will be discussed in COSMIC D2.2 “Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations”.

Affected community: lessons for response and preparation

The analysis of lessons learned from different case studies has revealed a number of important findings relating to the affected community in a crisis.

Crucially the 2005 London attacks revealed the failings of authorities to adequately manage and support the affected community (despite being a central point within the standard operating procedures). Such a failure points to a lack of coordination and communication between authorities and those members of the public that were affected by the attacks, illustrating the need for greater emphasis to be placed on considering the wider affected community rather than simply those that are directly injured or killed.

The wildfire case study demonstrated the importance of cooperation between government actors and ordinary citizens in both the preparation stage of a crisis and the need for greater training to help aid their response to a potential crisis. In California for instance it was evident that engaging the public in responding to the crisis would have helped response efforts; that said, there is a need of a risk assessment to determine the limits of risk which are unacceptable for exposing citizens to. Members of the public can also be of service by other means. For instance a study by Novak and Vidoloff, revealed how the activities of members of the public during the wildfires communicated relevant and up-to-date emergency related information to community members and emergency responders. The study also focused on the reception of such information by emergency responders, noting that while some responders were displeased with the posted raw data, they also acknowledged the citizens' "helpful role in meeting the voluminous requests for on-going information".³²⁷

Similarly, following the earthquakes in Haiti and Greece, preparedness levels were deemed to be low, despite, the initiation (a year before the earthquake) of civil protection policies in Greece. Preparation and defence from the damage caused by earthquakes were further hampered in Haiti as a result of the severe poverty and inadequate legislation concerning building regulations. Elsewhere following the Boston attacks, opportunities for authorities to learn from the experiences of other agencies who had dealt with acts of terrorism, along with training and other preparatory exercises were deemed as being a positive contribution to the abilities of the authorities to respond to the attacks.

Furthermore, it was deemed vital for authorities to better prepare communities for responding to other types of crises such as floods/storms. This was further evident in the need for greater collaboration within the community to respond to crises that were particularly threatening to certain vulnerable groups. For instance, following the 2003 and 2006 heatwaves examined in this report, it would have been of greater benefit to vulnerable groups, particularly the elderly, if communities had been better organised in supporting one another in dealing with the crisis. Furthermore, the absence of registries, where information about the elderly, the poor and the disabled could be stored, meant that the local agencies in both cases did not know the number and the whereabouts of individuals vulnerable to extreme heat. Thus poor organisational skills were also evident among authorities in their abilities to adequately deal with the effects of the heatwave.

³²⁷ Novak, J. M, and Vidoloff, K. G, 'New Frames on Crisis: Citizen Journalism Changing the Dynamics of Crisis Communication', *International Journal of Mass Emergencies and Disasters*, Vol. 29, No.3, 2011, pp. 181–202. [p. 191].

Thus in part, engaging with the affected community can help in the preparation, response and recovery of a crisis. This is currently reflected in the US approach to a “whole community” strategy to deal with crises: “a foundation for increasing individual preparedness and engaging with members of the community as collaborative resources to enhance the resiliency and security of our Nation through a Whole Community approach”.³²⁸ Following the Boston attacks, although there is (as yet) no direct evidence to suggest that citizen responders were cultivated by authorities, preliminary investigations did reveal that citizen responders played a crucial role in contributing to response efforts.

The importance of engagement among different stakeholders in the response to a crisis was also revealed when considering the two case studies examined on floods and storms. Following storm Xynthia in France it was evident that civil society organisations played a role in contributing to response efforts. This was lacking in the immediate aftermath of Hurricane Katrina, although this may be attributed to the scale of the crisis. Similarly, following the earthquake in Haiti, there were cases where response efforts were hampered by the lack of coordination and collaboration between authorities and civil society organisations.

As briefly summarised in this chapter, communication and the wider consideration of the affected community in the preparedness and response efforts to a crisis are of the utmost importance in enhancing our abilities to prepare for and respond to crises. The findings of this task will go some way towards complementing and assisting partners to further investigate the role of emergency response agencies (such as the police, fire department and healthcare professionals) in crisis management activities, a subject to be investigated in Task 1.3 “The role of emergency response agencies in crises” of COSMIC. As partners have shown so far, different types of crisis challenge the actors involved in different ways.

³²⁸ FEMA, “A Whole Community Approach to Emergency Management: Principles, Themes, and Pathways for Action”, *FEMA Resource and document library*, 30 July 2013. <http://www.fema.gov/media-library/assets/documents/23781?id=4941>

ACRONYMS

#	
07/07	7 th July 2005 London bombings
A	
ARS	Regional Health Agencies
B	
BBC	British Broadcasting Corporation
C	
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CDEMA	Caribbean Disaster Emergency Management Agency
CDERA	Caribbean Disaster Emergency Response Agency
CDM	Comprehensive Disaster Management
CEMP	Comprehensive Emergency Plan
CIC	Interministerial Crisis Cell
COGIC	Centre Opérationnel de Gestion Interministérielle des Crises
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
CWPP	Community Wildfire Protection Plan
D	
DPC	Department of Civic Protection
DX.X	Deliverable X.X
E	
EFFIS	European Fire Information System
EDT	Eastern Daylight Time
ESF	Emergency Support Functions
EU	European Union
EUFFTR	European Forest Fire Tactical Reserve
F	
FBI	Federal Bureau of Investigation
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Association
G	
GFC	Greek Fire Corps
GSCP	General Secretariat for Civil Protection
H	
HRT	Hellenic Rescue Team
I	
ICS	Incident Command System
ICP	Incident Command Post
IMT	Incident Management Team
L	
LESLP	London Emergency Services Liaison Panel
M	
MACC	Multi-Agency Coordination Center
MEMA	Massachusetts Emergency Management Agency
MIC	Monitoring and Information Centre
MINUSTAH	United Nations Stabilization Mission in Haiti
MMAA	Civil Defense Master Mutual Aid Agreement
MPS	Metropolitan Police Service

N	
NFCP	National Firewise Communities Program
NFP	National Fire Plan
NFCP	National Firewise Communities Program
NGO	Non-Government Organisation
NIMS	National Incident Management System
NOAA	National Ocean Atmospheric Administration
NRP	National Response Plan
NWS	National Weather Service
O	
OA	Operational Area
OCHA	Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
P	
PLA	Port of London Authority
PPI	Plan Particulier d'Intervention
PPR	Plan de Prévention de Risques Naturels
R	
RAF	Royal Air Force
RAWS	Remote Automated Weather Stations
RAYNET	Radio Amateur's Emergency Network
S	
SAR	Search and rescue
SAAD	Services to Help and Support for Home
SEMS	Standardized Emergency Management System
SEOC	State Emergency Operations Center
SOC	State Operations Center
SNGRD	National System for Risk and Disaster Management
SSIAD	Nursing Services At Home
U	
UN	United Nations
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
USAR	Urban search and rescue
USFS	US Forest Service
X	
XENOKRATIS	General Plan of Civil Protection